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Contribution to modelling safety instrumented systems and to assessing their performance Critical analysis of IEC 61508 standard

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To my parents

To my wife

To all those I care about

Thanks

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Abbreviations, acronyms

ALARP	As Low As Reasonably Practicable
BPCS	Basic Process Control System
DC	Diagnostic Coverage
CCF	Common Cause Failure
E/E/PE	Electrical/Electronic/Programmable Electronic safety-related systems
EN	European Norm
EUC	Equipment Under Control
FT	Fault Tree
HAZOP	HAZard and Operability study
HIPPS	High Integrity Pressure Protection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IPL	Independent Protection Layer
ISA	The Instrumentation, Systems and Automation Society
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
KooN	K out of N
LOPA	Layer Of Protection Analysis
MDT	Mean Down Time
MTBF	Mean Time Between Failure
MTTF	Mean Time To (first) Failure
MTTR	Mean Time To Repair
MUT	Mean Up Time
NF	French Norm
PDF	Probability of Failure on Demand
PFH	Probability of Failure per Hour
PN	Petri Net
RFF	Risk Reduction Factor
SFF	Safe Failure Fraction
SIF	Safety Instrumented Function
SIL	Safety Integrity Level
SIS	Safety Instrumented System
SRS	Safety Related System
UE	Undesired Event

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Introduction

1. Statement of the problem

The term ‘safety’ and the ‘risk’ with which it is often associated are familiar to us, because they are largely present in our daily lives. It is, however, clear that they are given many different meanings and therefore many definitions. This great heterogeneity can be explained by the varied and sometimes variable perception of the people being questioned, due to the diversity of their personal concerns, their training, their profession, their experiences and their local and time-related context, not to mention influence factors. It is therefore natural that these notions have, for many years, been the source of many different projects and reflections which produced multiple works and publications in all domains of knowledge relating to law, sociology, medicine, economics or sciences and techniques [Amalberti et al., 2003]. The topic of safety and risk is therefore vast and complex. At the same time, this thesis does not aim to present a new cross-functional contribution to this topic. Rather, we propose to conduct a critical analysis on a representative document for the standard-based approach from a safety sector, namely that of industrial risks. This focus obliges us to detail the relationship between the aforementioned general topic and that, more specifically, of our work. This will help us to define it and situate it properly.

If questions of safety seem to make the headlines more and more, it is because they are always linked to our society’s concerns and aspirations at the time. They are not a new phenomenon and only really emerge when they are sparked off by social rebuff. The conditions that expose such a rebuff are well-known: the triggering event for this social reaction must be perceived as unfair and abnormal. Even though we have to admit that occupational accidents no longer catch people’s attention as a priority, even though they are covered by sustained legislative actions [Decree no. 1016, 2001], major technological accidents [Directive SEVESO II, 1996], they continue to be perceived as unacceptable due to their generally disastrous consequences on peoples’ lives, on the environment and on the economy. It is then easy to understand that to meet society’s safety aspirations, the competent authorities had to provide legislation by firstly relying essentially on the post-analysis of how accidents occurred and what their consequences were. In order to simplify our point, we might consider that this approach to safety and the different ensuing regulations are the result of a certain materialisation of acquired experience, i.e. of experience feedback. These types of regulations are based on the concept of obligation of means in which only specific technical and/or organisational conditions have a legal obligatory value, and only they can therefore be sanctioned. In other words, the sole application of these specific rules will ensure a satisfactory level of safety and consequently, will release any company manager who has satisfied this obligation from all penal responsibility. In fact, jurisprudence has been quick to criticise the pertinence of this logic, by confirming the legal value of general conditions imposing only that results are obtained, without necessarily having to detail the means implemented to attain them. This approach, which does not substitute the preceding approach but complements it, is based on the concept of obligation to produce results [Law no.1414, 1991], which is significantly present in the aforementioned texts. This requires the qualities of forecast and anticipation from those in charge and the skills to analyse and model the system’s behaviour, sources of danger, and forecast analysis of the related risks from those who put into practice, in order to prevent occurrence and reduce the severity of the consequences, whilst remaining technologically feasible and economically acceptable.

In terms of managing risks, complete elimination is not entirely feasible and so the approaches aim to reduce them. When possible, risk reduction is conducted as far upstream as possible from the danger process [Lesbat et al., 1993], meaning at the source or as close to it as possible. To illustrate this, let us consider a production unit within a transformation or process industry. A Preliminary Risk Analysis (PRA), previously identified, among others, the sources of danger and the Undesired Event(s) (UE) likely to be caused or initiated by the process. The criticality for each UE places it in a two-dimensional risk space (probability, severity) and means we can appraise the extent of the efforts to be deployed to bring it to an acceptable or tolerable level. This reduction concerns, primarily, the probability of occurrence of the relevant UE and it is often obtained by successively laying several layers of protection between the danger source (the process) and potential objectives (persons, the installation itself, its environment).

There is a wide variety in the typology of the layers, ranging from control system which regulates the process with conventional safety devices, such as valves or sensors (for pressure, temperature, level, etc.) which trigger an alarm and is then followed by the appropriate operator intervention. These devices are increasingly supplemented by an extra layer known as the Safety Instrumented System (SIS). These SIS have sparked and continue to arouse growing interest from their effective or potential users and, of course, from equipment manufacturers. Their importance within these different communities lies in the level of the standards relevant to them, published over the last few years, whether of general vocation such as IEC 61508 [IEC 61508, 1998] or sector-based vocation such as IEC 61511 [IEC 61511, 2000] for process industries, IEC 62061 for machine safety [IEC 62061, 2002], European standards EN 50126 [NF EN 50126, 2000] and EN 50128 [NF EN 50128, 2002] which from now on have the status of French standards.

Regarding these standards, it is interesting to note that the approaches that they recommend are demonstrative, and for these purposes, highlight the aforementioned concept of having to attain a result.

The first standard mentioned is at the core of my doctoral research which was based on works, publications and congress sessions dedicated to it and above all exchanges which I have had with a handful of people who have worked hard to promote sensible use of this standard. The objectives that I have been given to provide the focus for the work presented in this report will be outlined in detail.

2. Objectives

It was on the instigation of Jean-Pierre Signoret that we actually discovered standard IEC 61508 and the interest it provoked and still provokes, despite the problems posed by understanding and/or interpreting its content. Among its seven volumes (IEC 61508-X, with $X = 1$ to 7), the sixth quickly held our attention, because annex B proposes over its fifty or so pages, not as announced, a method to calculate the probabilities of hardware failure for different SIS architectures, but only the analytical formulas resulting from this. These formulas, quite daunting at first glance, are presented directly, with no true explanation. So it seemed interesting and useful to run a critical and explanatory analysis and this, as much as Jean-Pierre Signoret demonstrated his fear of seeing people confronted with applying this standard, tempted precisely to apply these formulas systematically, as they are proposed in an official document, even if the latter does not have the rank of standard and they appear for information purposes only. This fear has unfortunately been justified in a short period of time.

This is why, chronologically, the first objective of this thesis was to analyse all these formulas with a view to explaining the basic hypotheses and find the mode of reasoning which led to their development. We might think that it would have been simpler to identify the author or authors of annex B and ask them for the appropriate information, but this was not possible until very late on and unfortunately, the approach was rather unsuccessful. Our first target was then upheld, in as much as it met a demand.

Let us recall that only hardware failures are considered in our work and, among them, essentially random failures. Failures qualified as systematic, and particularly failures originating from software are therefore excluded.

This first research area naturally led us to take a closer look at some definitions and key concepts in the standard. We then realised they needed to be clarified to guarantee common understanding of this document. Then, little by little, the idea of more extensive levelling of its more controversial parts took shape, even raising doubts on one of the standard's fundamentals constituting the mathematical relationship between the risk reduction factor which the SIS must assure and the SIL level (Safety Integrity Level) which will be defined below. This led us to set a second (no doubt ambitious) objective for the thesis, which requires the first objective to be completed and then moved on beyond it. This refers to attempting to write a report which is both a didactic contribution to a state of the art concerning the standard IEC 61508, more specifically volume 6, and an operational guide for anyone having to model SIS and evaluate performance in terms of SIL, if this criterion should be kept, which is likely.

3. Organisation of the work

The real chronology of the work conducted to satisfy the two objectives given above is not necessarily reflected in the organisation of the thesis report. It is outlined in detail below.

The first chapter presents the topic of the present doctoral research, through successive focuses. We start by giving accurate details of the meaning we assign to the key terms in *safety*, as they have several meanings. We then narrow down our centre of interest, passing from safety in the broadest sense, to functional safety, via a concise presentation of its reference document, standard IEC 61508. Then, a new focus draws our attention to the important functional safety section comprising the risk reduction step. This leads to defining overall safety instructions in terms of safety functions and safety integrity instructions for all systems which need to run these functions. Among these systems, we can distinguish Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS), which are the central subject of our work and, our final focus will bring us to defining two probabilities which measure the capacity of an SIS to run a safety function for a sufficient SIL in each of the two modes of operation which they might exhibit.

The two aforementioned probabilities are known as the average probability of failure on demand ($PF_{D_{avg}}$) and probability of failure per hour (PFH), whilst the operating modes mentioned above, which correspond to them, are low demand mode and high demand or continuous demand mode of operation.

Critical analysis for the analytical models presented in the IEC 61508-6 standard, which help us calculate $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH , then the detailed proposal from appropriate holistic

models and the description of their different operations constitute two major contributions to our doctoral contribution.

If standard IEC 61508 provides a formalised and rigorous approach to determining the required SIL levels and it is interesting from this organisational point of view, it does not present any less significant disadvantages regarding its applicability. These disadvantages arise particularly from the sometimes vague and ambiguous character of the statement of certain concepts and major definitions in this standard. So, it has seemed necessary to us to dedicate the second chapter of this report to clarifying these concepts and definitions and providing more details on the double nature of the limits which restrict the use of analytical formulas proposed in volume 6, before analysing the latter in detail.

We can also note that one of the key-points of this chapter is the light that we throw on the *PFH*, providing details of its nature.

Chapter 3 synthesises our work on the demonstration of the analytical formulas used to obtain the average value of the *PFH* for the main *KooN* architectures. For that purpose, we recommend and implement a step which is supported by “piecewise Markov” models, known as multi-phase Markov models, to derive classic Markov models from them. Using the stationary regime for the latter leads to these formulas.

One important point for us, which has never been explained to the best of our knowledge, is highlighting that the models from the second type are not equivalent to the first. They simply give a good approximation of their average behaviour via their own asymptotic behaviour.

Chapter 4 is a continuation of the preceding chapter, but deals with calculating the *PFH* for the same architectures as before, which are this time requested permanently (continuous demand). For each of the holistic models, for which we recommend usage (fault tree, Markov graph, Petri nets) we will illustrate ability to calculate the *PFH* for all or some *KooN* architectures. We will also show that one and the same model can be used each time to determine both the *PFH* and the PFH_{avg} . These quantities also express one as a function of the other, which is not mentioned in the standard.

The second part of the fourth chapter is given over to studying a simple SIS for which the architecture is not reduced to either one of the elementary architectures analysed up to then or to one of their combinations. This study helps highlight the limited character of the applicative domain for the analytical formulas examined during this and the preceding chapter.

Standard IEC 61508 contains interesting points or raises other issues than what we have studied. Among them, four captured our attention. We will examine them successively in this fifth and final chapter, giving it a “patchwork” effect. Firstly we will present the step which, in our opinion, could have been at the origin of formulating the analytical expressions for PFH_{avg} and *PFH* proposed in annex B of the IEC 61508-6 standard. This follows a constant relating to taking into account the architectural constraints recommended by the standard and for the use of the safety failure fraction (*SFF*), which follows on from it. Then we examined the possible impact that SIS channel safe failures might have on its PFH_{avg} and its *PFH*, as well as the possible impact of spurious trip failures on the frequency of the undesired event whose occurrence should be alerted by the SIS. Finally, to close this last chapter, we will present a brief reconsideration of a widely shared idea according to which the risk reduction

factor provided by a set of sequential protection layers is equal to the product of the individual reduction factors.

The presentation of this entire thesis work ends in a general conclusion summarising the different contributions which have come from it and which should provide a better understanding and rational use of standard IEC 61508. At least, we hope so. Whilst there is still a lot of work to be done, there is also the perspective for later studies.

Chapter 1

**From overall safety to functional safety and from functional safety
to Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS)**

1.1. Introduction

The trendy term *global* or *overall safety* actually puts across a legitimate concern, shared by everyone in charge, regardless of their level, of keeping potential objectives, whether they are people, populations, property and equipment or the environment, safe from aggressions, intentional or otherwise. The first type of aggression is traditionally security-related but this is, from now on, increasingly included in industrial risk prevention steps. The second type of aggression, meaning unintentional aggressions encompassing accidents which we might consider as instantaneous and localised events and chronic and different types of phenomena including pollution threats, which essentially are linked to public health, sanitary safety and protecting the environment.

“Security” does not enter into our field of doctoral research, because we are only interested in dangerous phenomena which are industrial accidents and their prevention. In this respect we are talking about technological risks [La lettre T.I, 2006] [Dubois-Maury, 2002] [Leroy et al., 1992] which are often revealed to be major risks [Directive SEVESO II, 1996] [Loos et al., 2002]. To provide more details on our centre of interest, we could say that it tackles the inherent risks for process industries and how to control them.

In this type of industry, the predominant source of danger is the process itself through its uncontrolled deviations, which are always possible. The breadth of these deviations is normally limited, regulated by a control system, which can nevertheless fail. In this case, the failing regulating action of the control system is replaced by an intervention from an operator and/or safety systems. Among these we find Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) which are at the very heart of functional safety. It is this global safety subassembly which provides the framework for our work on SIS.

Several terms have been used in this introduction which will appear throughout this report, such as danger, risk, accident or undesired event, safety, functional safety, system, SIS. In order to avoid any ambiguity regarding their meaning here, in the next section of this first chapter we are proposing to give a precise definition of each of them and then also give details on the standard framework governing functional safety and finally, describe a classic step to reduce risks highlighting the role played by SIS.

1.2. Proposed definitions

If we are required to provide more details on the meaning attributed to the aforementioned terms, it is because they have several meanings. Consequently they have already been the subject of many works which tend to define them precisely and if possible generally, or even universally! Once again, we will not presume to propose our own terminology for them, but we are choosing to simply recall the definitions which emanate from reflections made several years ago within two renown ‘schools’. We might also review certain definitions given in the NF EN 61703 standard [NF EN 61703, 2002].

The first school produced a methodology for Analysing Malfunctions in Systems, known as MADS [Lesbats et al., 1993] [Portail du Risque] [Périllon, 2007], whilst the second, known as Society for the Advancement of Systems Safety in France (3SF) previously published a glossary dedicated to terms used in the safety domain [3SF, 1974]. There are other sources which have produced and edited these definitions [Wybo, 1998] [Seillan, 2007], but we are going to tackle the two which we have mentioned.

1.2.1. Notion of system

As announced in the introduction, SISs are at the centre of the work represented in this report. One of their conclusions is the LEGO type, modular approach, proposed in the IEC 61508-6 document which is not very flexible and has reduced applicability. In our opinion, the only valid approach is to model SISs as systems and operate these models quantitatively in the same optic. This is why the idea of system is firstly defined according to the view from J. L. Le Moigne [Le Moigne, 1984] who is one of the benchmark authors for the MADS group, a mixed work group from University of Bordeaux1/CEA.

According to this author, a system can be seen as:

- something (anything presumed to be identifiable),
- that does something (activity, operating),
- in something (environment),
- for something (purpose, project),
- by means of something (structure = activity support),
- and which is transformed over time (evolution).

Figure 1.1: Attributes of the word *system*

This very general definition immediately tells us that we can apprehend a system by:

- its “positive” purpose (accomplishing a mission) by modelling it through an event tree, or its “negative” purpose (generating an undesired event, see 1.2.2) by resorting to the fault tree model, which is the dual of the preceding concept;
- the fact it operates via a functional block-diagram, used in the initial phase of a FMEA study, for example;
- its structure represented by a PID (Piping Instrumentation Diagram), in the case of a HAZOP study;
- its evolution towards nominal and downgraded operation states or failure, using a behavioural model, such as Markov graphs or Petri nets.

This multiform definition of the word system clearly illustrates the fact that a system is more than the sum of its parts. Not taking into account this admission explains the limited scope of the aforementioned LEGO approach.

1.2.2. Notion of undesired Event (UE)

In this respect we can return to the definition given by the MADS group under the name of undesired event (UE). An UE is a “*phenomenon likely to cause undesired effects on the individual, the population, the ecosystem and the installation. They result from and are applied to: the structure, the activity, the evolution of natural and artificial systems. This definition explains at least two categories of undesired events: those attributed to the danger source system, but also to the effects that the latter cause on the target danger system*” (See paragraph 1.2.3).

Among the words which we wish to define more accurately, system and undesired event are primordial, because they logically introduce definitions of other key words which are danger, risk and safety (figure 1.2), which are going to be explained now.

Figure 1.2: Strong relationships

1.2.3. Notion of danger (hazard)

As a preface, let us take the example of a domestic gas water heater. Its purpose is to provide hot water on demand at a convenient temperature. The UEs (more precisely UE-source) likely to be engendered by this type of device are known. This includes gas leaks, non evacuation of combustion gas (CO, CO₂), supplying water at an excessive temperature (faulty regulation), explosion due to internal over-pressure (faulty regulation and valve blocked or over calibrated). So we can say how a water heater like this is dangerous: it is dangerous because it is likely to cause all the UE mentioned above! This admission reminds us of the definition of the word danger proposed by 3SF for a given system: “*The danger inherent in a system is defined by the list of the undesired events which it is likely to cause.*”

The qualitative and descriptive nature of the danger clearly appears in this definition. In an attempt to target this nature more precisely, we can refer to the “reference model”, called “danger process,” proposed by the MADS group. Just its graphic representation is given and succinctly commented below.

Figure 1.3: The danger process

The basis for this model is made up of four interacting entities, directly linked to the concept of system.

- We call any undesired transaction between a system and its environment “danger flux” We will talk about flux in matter, energy or information.
- The origin of this flux is called “danger source system” and we can consider that any break in equilibrium concerning its structure and/or its activity and/or its evolution can constitute what we call a “UE-source”.
- The part which undergoes the impact of the danger flux is called “target-system.” Its equilibrium break can therefore constitute a “UE-target.”
- We call the active environment susceptible to influence on the source and target systems and on the danger flux “field of danger”.

Having given these definitions, we can consider that a safety analysis would consist of studying the danger process, meaning matching a source-system to a target-system by means of phenomena called danger flux, in an active environment called danger field.

Furthermore, examining figure 1.3 and the comments following it shows that we can only talk about danger if we can answer the following three questions beforehand: danger for who, why (potential objectives)? Danger from whom, or what (source)? Danger, how (flux)? So a heater located in an isolated environment does not constitute a danger source-system, except for itself.

Now we can see how the notions of danger and undesired event bring about the notion of risk.

1.2.4. Notions of risk and risk reduction

The risk can be considered as a certain quantification of the danger associating a measurement of the occurrence of a undesired event with an estimation of how serious its

consequences are. This definition, which is close to the definition offered by A. Villemeur [Villemeur, 1988], indicated, as announced, that the idea of risk cannot be dissociated from the ideas of danger and undesired event.

If we only retain its probability of occurring P and the severity G of its consequences as components of an UE and if we assimilate these two components into the two Cartesian coordinates for a point, any UE can be represented by its specific image on a plane equipped with two graduated orthogonal or scaled axes. This plane is the risk space. Furthermore, in the domain of analysis and risk control and also their perception, the traditionally used marking illustrates the relationship between G and P .

This relationship is shown on a graph by a straight line or a downward curve. It is derived from the curve known as Farmer [Lievens, 1976] [Kumamoto, 1996] and illustrates dividing risk space into two disjoint subsets, corresponding respectively to the domains of acceptable risk and unacceptable risk.

Figure 1.4: The risk space

As the image of an UE is supposed to belong to the unacceptable risk zone, it appears that schematically there are two ways of envisaging a risk reduction procedure inherent to this UE:

- either plan measures which will limit the severity of the consequences for an UE, which we could not prevent from happening. This refers to a reduction in the *constant probability* (which will be equal to the unit from occurrence) sometimes called mitigation [Ellia Hervy, 1997] or more often protection (downward vertical arrow);
- or, to avoid dealing with the consequences of this type of event, design and implement measures intended to prevent it occurring. This time, this refers to a reduction of the risk at *constant severity* (horizontal line) raised by a preventive action.

Now, in the safety domain, as in many others, it is unanimously admitted that it is better to prevent than cure. This means that it is better to set up a more rigorous prevention policy the more serious the consequences of the UE occurring are deemed. This old common sense adage has led certain prevention officers to formalise a risk control technique known as

“barrier technique”. This refers to interposing a series of barriers between the source-system and the target-system, which are as independent as possible, assigned to prevent either the UE-source occurring and therefore the UE-target (impact on the target), or just to prevent the UE-target occurring. In the first case, all these barriers are preventive in terms of the two UE considered, whilst in the second case they act as protection barriers for the UE-source and prevention barriers for the UE-target.

To conclude this paragraph, we can add that the fault tree model lends itself well to the illustration of the barrier allocation procedure [Boya et al., 1998] [Dutuit et al., 2002] and that the principle of interposing them can be found in the LOPA method (Layers of Protection Analysis) [Dowell, 1998] which is presented in paragraph 1.4. It remains, for the time being, to look more closely at the idea of safety for a system and to define functional safety for an SIS, in liaison with the safety role that it might have to play.

1.2.5. Notions of safety for a system and functional safety for an SIS

- Following the example given for reliability and availability in different standards, the safety of any system can be defined in terms of aptitude. The following definition can be proposed:

Definition: the safety of a system is its aptitude to function or malfunction without causing a undesired event for itself or its environment, notably human.

- As for functional safety, it is defined in neighbouring, but differentiated, terms in standards IEC 61508-4 (paragraph 3.1.9) and IEC 61511-1 (paragraph 3.2.25); the second uses specific terms from the process industries domain.

For the first it is:

A subset of the overall safety relating to the equipment under control (EUC) and the EUC control system that depends on the correct functioning of the Electrical/Electronic/Programmable electronic (E/E/PE) safety-related systems, safety-related systems based on other technologies and external risk reduction devices

For the second it is:

A subset of the global safety relating to the process and to the Basic Process Control System (BPCS), which depends on the SIS and other protection layers working correctly.

The two preceding definitions seem too general however, because they do not give clear details on correct operation of the E/E/PE safety-related system or SIS. In order to alleviate this lack of accuracy, we are proposing the following definition following the same logic as before.

Definition: the functional safety of an SIS is linked to its aptitude to correctly perform the safety function allocated to it, meaning to maintain or return the process to a safe state, following the occurrence of a specific (undesired) dangerous event.

Given that standard IEC 61508 constitutes the standard for our work and that the IEC 61511 standard is a major break down of this, we think it is wise to make a few more points a little clearer, as this knowledge is necessary to situate our contribution better.

1.3. IEC 61508 standard

1.3.1. Scope

This is an international standard which was conceived as a generic standard containing a set of information and directive lines aiming to improve safety by using E/E/PE systems which are the SIS. It is part of a global safety approach which we can compare with the ISO 9000 and ISO 14000 systems which respectively deal with the domains of quality and the environment. It proposes an operational step to implement an E/E/PE system working from the study of the safety requirements specifically from an analysis and an evaluation of the risks, by taking into account all the stages in its life cycle. One of its design objectives was (and remains) that it be used as a reference document making it easier to draw up sector-based standards which should then form a consistent set.

The generic nature and the filiation of standard IEC 61508 appear in figure 1.5.

Figure 1.5: IEC 61508 standard and its sector-based derivatives

Standard IEC 61511 therefore appears among the IEC 61508 standard derivatives. The SIS are the main subject of these two standards, but they are considered differently depending on the professions they are being applied to (figure 1.6).

Figure 1.6: Relationship between IEC 61508 and IEC 61511

1.3.2. Structure of the standard and overall safety life cycle

One of the particular characteristics of standard IEC 61508 is that it uses a global safety life cycle model (figure 1.7) as a technical framework to systematically process the activities to be carried out to assure functional safety for the E/E/PE safety-related systems, from the initial specification phase until they are pensioned off, including design, installation, operation and maintenance.

We find the same type of representation for the safety life cycle in standard IEC 61511-1 (figure 1.8).

Figure 1.7: Overall safety life cycle (IEC 61508-1)

Figure 1.8: SIS safety life cycle phases (IEC 61511-1)

It is interesting to highlight that each of the different phases of these life cycles returns to one or several parts of standard IEC 61508 which has seven parts (IEC 61508-1 to IEC 61508-7). So by limiting ourselves to parts of the standard that focus on the domain covered by this doctoral work, we see that:

- Standard IEC 61508-1, which provides the global framework permitting functional safety, covers general instructions. It therefore deals with all the life cycle phases.
- The IEC 61508-2 standard, which covers instructions relating to E/E/PE safety-related systems, particularly deals with the phase of producing these systems, meaning phase 9 of the life cycle, particularly via procedures to be applied to validate the safety integrity* required for each safety function and via taking into account the architectural constraints*. This standard only deals with hardware.
- The IEC 61508-3 standard, dedicated to instructions relating to the software, also returns to phase 9. It was not the subject of the research presented in this report, which is exclusively focussed on the hardware, as we have already mentioned.
- Standard IEC 61508-4, which groups together the main definitions and abbreviations used in the 7 volumes of the standard, is not linked to any life cycle phase particularly, but all of them in general.
- Standard IEC 61508-5, entitled “examples of methods for determining levels of safety integrity” is centred on risk reduction. For this purpose, it returns to phase 4 of the life cycle, which cannot be considered independently from phase 3.
- Standard IEC 61508-6, which is the reference document for our research, as it provides the directive lines permitting us to apply standard IEC 61508-2 (and IEC 61508-3), also returns to phase 9 of the life cycle.
- Standard IEC 61508-7, which presents the techniques and measures which are likely to be used, for example, when validating the safety of E/E/PE systems, can be linked to phase 13 of the life cycle.

This quick look at the general structure of standard IEC 61508, in parallel with the different constitutional phases of the global safety life cycle, lead us to take a more specific interest in phases 3, 4, 5 and 9. Their content and their chronological succession will give more details about the ins and outs of our work. Phases, 3, 4, and 5 are located upstream of this, whilst the more weighty part corresponds to the domain covered by phase 9.

First of all, let us look at the first three phases.

1.4. From risk analysis to allocating safety requirements

Phases 3, 4 and 5 of the safety life cycle described in standard IEC 61508-1 develop the same topic as for standard IEC 61511-3, as it happens a step aiming to reduce the risks inherent to a well-defined installation. It is therefore a matter of identifying the danger sources and the undesired events which it is likely to cause and evaluate them (phase 3), in order to compare their criticality (severity, probability) with a limit value constituting the safety target to be met. If this criticality exceeds the previously set threshold value, it will then have to be reduced.

* These two terms are defined in chapter 2

The magnitude of this reduction leads to the definition of overall safety instructions (phase 4) in terms of safety functions and safety integrity instructions for all the systems which have to run these functions.

These overall instructions are then broken down into specific allocated safety instructions, always in terms of safety functions, into several different types of systems (phase 5): E/E/PE systems, systems based on another technology, external devices for risk reduction.

It then remains to demonstrate that each of the safety systems in charge of running a safety function is capable of doing so. This part of the risk reduction step, which deals with controlling them, returns to phases 6 to 9 of the safety life cycle. It will be presented in paragraph 1.5 and developed in chapters 3, 4 and 5 of this report, as the heart of our doctoral contribution.

This risk reduction step is illustrated synthetically by figure 1.9 as the result of standard IEC 61508-5 and reviewed by standard IEC 61511-3.

Figure 1.9: Risk reduction: general concepts

The actions to run to carry out this risk reduction are mentioned below, in chronological order. These actions are reviewed and explained below as described in annex B of standard 61511-3.

1.4.1. Determining tolerable risk

Stating that something is a tolerable risk level is no easy task for the people or authorities in charge, regardless of the importance of their responsibility. They have the moral duty and the legal, if not also financial, obligation to not expose potential objectives of their activities to a higher risk level than what is morally acceptable.

Governments and industrialists have explored numerous ways of deciding whether a risk level is acceptable or not, but they all generally require two stages [Marszal, 2001]. The first is a psycho and socio-metric study of the risks that people are willing to accept and for which

reasons. The aim of the second stage is to turn this qualitative and subjective appreciation of the risk into specific guidelines which are often quantitative (digital threshold values).

This is exactly the case for transformation or process industries which we are interested in. The most usual “philosophy” in this domain is to combine the search for maximum expected usefulness (cost/profit approach) and the approach that Marszal attributes to Pareto, according to which an industrialist can look to optimise the expected usefulness of his investment, but without exposing anyone (his employees, the neighbouring population) to an excessive growth in risk. This approach was formalised in Great Britain by the Health and Safety Executive under the name of ALARP (As Low As Reasonably Practicable) [IEC 61508-5, 1998] [Smith et al., 2001] [Wang et al., 2007] for which the principle appears on the diagram in figure 1.10.

Its principle is that there is a risk level which is not tolerable; beyond this no risk is at all justifiable and is therefore unacceptable. This corresponds to the top part of the diagram (zone I). Below this zone there is the ALARP zone (zone II), for which all risks can be accepted if the anticipated profit is sufficient.

Figure 1.10: ALARP Model*

To be more precise, and as shown on the diagram, the risk is only tolerable:

- if any extra reduction in the risk is incompatible or if its cost is clearly disproportionate to the improvement it can obtain, and
- if society gets an advantage from the activity, bearing in mind the associated risk.

The lower zone (zone III) shows the residual risk for which the level is considered as insignificant and, for this purpose, does not require extra reduction.

In order to apply the ALARP step, which, let us remember, concerns the risk and not one of its two components, it is necessary to establish several (generally 3 or 4) risk

* The tables A.1 and A.2 from the 61511-3 standard, which appear in the figure 1.10, correspond respectively to tables 1.1 and 1.2 presented in this thesis dissertation.

categories and to make each of them correspond to one of the three ALARP model zones (table 1.2). These categories actually take into account the critical nature of the undesired events for the type of process being studied. This kind of classification, given as an example, appears in table 1.1.

Probability	Risk class			
	Catastrophic consequence	Critical consequence	Marginal consequence	Negligible consequence
Likely	I	I	I	II
Probable	I	I	II	II
Possible	I	II	II	II
Remote	II	II	II	III
Improbable	II	III	III	III
Incredible	II	III	III	III

NOTE 1 See Table A.2 for interpretation or risk classes I to III.

NOTE 2 The actual population of this table with risk classes I, II and III will be application dependent and also depends upon what the actual probabilities are for likely, probable, etc. Therefore, this table should be seen as an example of how such a table could be populated, rather than as a specification for future use.

Table 1.1: Example of classification of accident risks [IEC 61511-3]

Risk class	Interpretation
Class I	Intolerable risk
Class II	Undesirable risk, and tolerable only if risk reduction is impracticable or if the costs are grossly disproportionate to the improvement gained
Class III	Negligible risk

NOTE There is no relationship between risk class and safety integrity level (SIL). SIL is determined by the risk reduction associated with a particular safety instrumented function, see Annexes B to F.

Table 1.2: Correspondence between categories and risk zones [IEC 61511-3]

These two tables, let us not forget, cannot be used in just any circumstance. They must be adapted to each specific situation or for each type of industrial sector, following discussions/negotiations for an agreement between all the parties involved in the current study. These discussions rely on national or international regulations, standards, company policies, knowledge of technical best practices and on each person's experience. The aforementioned agreement generally only appears after the ordinal qualifier attributed to each category of consequences (e.g. negligible to catastrophic) and to each category of frequencies (e.g. unlikely to highly probable undesired event) was illustrated by a specific example or a set of numerical values adapted to the industrial sector involved. We could, for example, conceive that "catastrophic consequences" corresponds to the death of one or several people or the total loss of the production tool, and the "unlikely" undesired event corresponds to an annual occurrence frequency between 1.10^{-4} and 1.10^{-3} .

So, having come to a consensus on the level of severity for a known accident to be able to draw the type of process concerned by the study from it (e.g. critical level), descending the corresponding column from table 1.1 leads us to risk category II, which is the ALARP zone. The latter then imposes, by reading the corresponding line from right to left, that to be tolerable, this accident can only be possible or unlikely. In compliance with the ALARP principle, the "unlikely" level is retained which leads to an annual occurrence frequency between 1.10^{-4} and 1.10^{-3} , according to our conventions. The value finally chosen within this

interval then determines the annual occurrence frequency of the event corresponding to the tolerable risk from figure 1.9.

1.4.2. From determining risks linked to the process to that of the required SIL

Having established the safety limit (tolerable risk), it is advisable to complete the other stages of the risk reduction procedure. Below we will describe these stages by following the framework of the pedagogic example presented in annex B of standard IEC 61511-3, which refers to a process using a vessel under pressure containing a flammable and volatile liquid (figure 1.11).

Figure 1.11: Pressurised vessel with its existing safety systems

Stage 2 involves producing the danger and risk analysis intended to evaluate the risk linked to the process, classified as existing risk* in the aforementioned standard. The HAZOP method (HAZard and OPerability study) [IEC 61882, 2001], highly used in petro-chemical industries in particular, can be implemented for this purpose. Let us suppose that it allows us to establish that the offset of the process's regulation and command system, the "BPCS" (Basic Process Control System) can cause internal overpressure in the vessel holding the flammable product, which, in turn, can lead to a undesired event from the control system (EUC - Equipment Under Control), for example spilling or releasing this product into the environment.

This overpressure is therefore the direct initiating event for the feared spilling or releasing event at an overall system level, grouping together the EUC and its control system, for which it is going to be necessary to compare the occurrence frequency with that of the predefined tolerable risk. It is therefore necessary to evaluate the occurrence frequency of the overpressure. As the latter could have other possible causes that the failure of the BPCS, a fault tree analysis [Stamatelatos, 2002], with the overpressure as the peak event, can be carried out. In this respect we are reminded that the input data for fault tree is the probability that each of its basic events will occur. These probabilities generally correspond to immediate unavailability measures. It is then possible to calculate occurrence frequencies for these same basic events and, working from them and the corresponding Birnbaum importance factors, firstly determine the occurrence frequency of the top-event (UE) depending on the time, then

*The adjective "intrinsic" seems more appropriate to us.

its average value over a specified period. We can suppose then that the fault tree analysis gives, for the over-pressure, an annual occurrence frequency of 0.1.

Having made this determination by not taking into account any safety functions, the following stages are going to logically integrate the existing safety devices.

Stages 3, 4 and 5 form a coherent set equipped with a unique purpose. They will not be presented separately in detail. If we do not consider the existing safety devices, the occurrence frequency for the over-pressure is that of the undesired event at the process level. As its value is clearly greater than the previously obtained tolerable threshold ($0.1 \gg 1.10^{-4}$), it is advisable to reduce it sharply using one or several safety functions, therefore demonstrating the need for them (stage 3). This or these safety functions will be assured by one or several layers of protection (phase 4). We thereby identify two independent layers comprising respectively:

- an over-pressure alarm (PAH) which warns an operator who, in turn, acts to curb this mounting pressure.
- a device to evacuate over-pressure (PL) such as a valve or a rupture disk.

We make the hypothesis that the evacuation device working correctly leads the rejected product towards a flare and that its failure disperses it in the environment.

In the case of the example given in the standard, the risk reduction contributed by these two protection layers is factor 5. This takes the annual reject frequency to around 0.1 to $1.9 \cdot 10^{-2}$. The latter value is obtained by adding the frequencies resulting from producing branches 4 and 7 (excluding the contribution of the safety function assured by the SIS) from the event tree represented in figure 1.12. This reduction is still insufficient as $1.8 \cdot 10^{-2} \gg 1.10^{-4}$. It is necessary to resort to a supplementary safety function. This will be integrated into an SIS (stage 5) whose contribution should permit us to assure the control of the required risk (stages 6 to 9) which passes, here, via a reduction of the UE occurrence frequency (spillage or release of the flammable product). It is therefore necessary to verify the capacity of the SIS to correctly execute the required supplementary safety function (figure 1.12).

In order to conclude this paragraph, we will recall that as a complement of the quantitative method to determine the SIL, presented here, the IEC 61508-5 standard presents two qualitative methods called risk graph (annex D of the standard) and dangerous event severity matrix (annex E of the standard) respectively.

The modalities of this verification, which are coded in standard IEC 61508-1, are reviewed in the following paragraph.

Figure 1.12: Dangerous event with a safety function which has a safety integrity level SIL2 and implemented in a safety instrumented system (SIS)

1.5. Determining the SIL for a SIF

1.5.1. From risk reduction to the SIL

One safety function carried out by an SIS is an instrumented safety function (SIF: Safety Instrumented Function). The probability of not being carried out is therefore closely linked to the probability that the SIS supporting it will fail. The latter is written $p(SIS)$. Now the SIF is only triggered if the SIS is requested, for example, after detecting a potentially dangerous deviation for a physical-chemical process parameter (*IE* initiating event) beyond a set-point value. If we write $freq(D)$ the frequency of this request or demand from the EUC, the occurrence frequency for the undesired event likely to emerge from the global system (EUC + SIS) can therefore be written: $freq(ER) = freq(D) \times p(SIS)$, as the SIS state is independent of the existence of a demand.

The occurrence of such an UE, remember, is only tolerated if we can prove that its frequency is less than a threshold value $freq(TE)$, where *TE* means “tolerable event.” This is translated by the following equation:

$$freq(UE) = freq(D) \times p(SIS) \leq freq(TE) \tag{1.1}$$

where:

$$\frac{freq(D)}{1/p(SIS)} = \frac{freq(IE)}{\Delta R} \leq freq(TE) \tag{1.2}$$

As an example, in paragraph 1.4.2, we retained the following average values for these two frequencies: $freq(IE) = 0.1 \text{ year}^{-1}$ and $freq(TE) = 1.10^{-4} \text{ year}^{-1}$. Giving a risk reduction factor (ΔR or *RRF* for Risk Reduction Factor) equal to 1000.

The following diagram, coming from annex C of IEC 61508-5 standard, takes into account the same risk reduction concept with different notations ($PF_{D,avg}$ for $p(SIS)$, Ft for $freq(TE)$ and F_{np} for $freq(D)$).

Figure 1.13: Necessary risk reduction performed by a single SIS

The IEC 61508-2 standard considers the average values of $p(SIS)$ in two different ways, depending on how the SIS is requested.

- **Low demand mode of operation**

Low demand mode, as defined in 3.5.12 of IEC 61508-4, is where the frequency of demands of operation made on a safety-related system (SIS) is no greater than one per year and no greater than twice the proof-test frequency [IEC 61508-4, 1998]*. In this case, $p(SIS)$ is the “average probability of failure on demand of the SIS.” We will see in chapter 2 that this refers in fact to its average unavailability, written PFD_{avg} (Average Probability of Failure on Demand).

The IEC 61508-1 standard then defines four safety integrity levels for the SIF supported by the SIL, via table 1.3.

Safety integrity level (SIL)	Low demand mode of operation (PFD_{avg})
4	$\geq 10^{-5}$ to $< 10^{-4}$
3	$\geq 10^{-4}$ to $< 10^{-3}$
2	$\geq 10^{-3}$ to $< 10^{-2}$
1	$\geq 10^{-2}$ to $< 10^{-1}$

Table 1.3: SIL in low demand mode [IEC 61508-1]

We can complete table 1.3 with a third column, following the example of what happens in standard IEC 61511-1. This third column indicates the risk reduction factor corresponding to each SIL (see table 1.4).

Safety integrity level (SIL)	Low demand mode of operation (PFD_{avg})	Risk reduction factor
4	$\geq 10^{-5}$ to $< 10^{-4}$	10000 to 100000
3	$\geq 10^{-4}$ to $< 10^{-3}$	1000 to 10000
2	$\geq 10^{-3}$ to $< 10^{-2}$	100 to 1000
1	$\geq 10^{-2}$ to $< 10^{-1}$	10 to 100

Table 1.4: SIL in low demand mode [IEC 61511-1]

* A critical analysis of this double criteria is made in paragraph 2.3.1.

By synthesising this last table and the formula (1.2), we can express the risk reduction factor, RFF , as a function of SIL:

$$RFF = \frac{1}{PFD_{avg}} = \frac{1}{1.10^{-SIL}} = 1.10^{SIL} \quad (1.3)$$

Note: We will see in chapter 2 that this fundamental relationship has to be reconsidered in the case of SIS association.

- **High demand or continuous mode of operation**

This second mode, as defined in 3.5.12 of IEC 61508-4, is where the frequency of demands for operation made on a safety-related system (SIS) is greater than one per year or greater than twice the proof-test frequency*. In this case, $p(SIS)$ is called “probability of dangerous failure per hour” for the SIS. It is also an average value written PFH (Average Probability of Failure per Hour). In chapter 2 we will see that this is the average value for the unconditional intensity of the SIS failure. The equation (1.1) must be replaced by the equation below:

$$freq(UE) = p(SIS) = PFH \leq freq(TE) \quad (1.4)$$

In this case the IEC 61508-1 standard also defines four safety integrity levels for the SIF via table 1.5.

Safety integrity level (SIL)	High demand or continuous mode of operation (PFH)
4	$\geq 10^{-9}$ to $< 10^{-8}$
3	$\geq 10^{-8}$ to $< 10^{-7}$
2	$\geq 10^{-7}$ to $< 10^{-6}$
1	$\geq 10^{-6}$ to $< 10^{-5}$

Table 1.5: SIL in high or continuous demand mode [IEC 61508-1]

These two tables synthesise the key-information which we have completed within this first chapter. It explains the relationship between the SIL for a SIF and an attribute (PFD_{avg} or PFH) of the SIS within which it is integrated.

However, this determination of the SIL of a SIF, obtained probabilistically by calculating the average value of the PFD or PFH did not offer sufficient accuracy guarantees, according to the standard. It would therefore be advisable to confirm or correct the value found in this way for the SIL by applying another different type of determining method. This second way is described in the next paragraph.

1.5.2. Architectural constraints

The IEC 61508-2 standard places a limit on the hardware safety integrity that can be claimed for an E/E/PE safety-related system. The highest safety integrity level can be claimed for a safety function, and hence for an E/E/PE safety-related system, is limited by the hardware fault tolerance of the subsystems that carry out that safety function and by its safe failure fraction.

* See previous footnote.

The standard then defines these two new terms:

- A hardware fault tolerance of index N means that $(N+1)$ faults could cause a loss of the safety function.
- The safe failure fraction (SFF) is defined as the ratio of the average rate of safe failures plus dangerous detected failures (see chapter 2, paragraph 2.3.5) of the subsystem to the total average failure rate of the subsystem.

The approach presented in the annex C of the IEC 61508-2 standard relies on two tables reproduced below (tables 1.6 and 1.7).

Safe failure fraction (SFF)	Hardware fault tolerance		
	0	1	2
< 60 %	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
60 % - < 90 %	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
90 % - < 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4
\geq 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

An SIS can be considered to be type A if its behaviour in the presence of faults is well determined, if the failure modes of its constituent parts are well defined and if the data on their failures from feedback is known with good reliability.

Table 1.6: Architectural constraints on type A SIS

Safe failure fraction (SFF)	Hardware fault tolerance		
	0	1	2
< 60 %	Unauthorised	SIL 1	SIL 2
60 % - < 90 %	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
90 % - < 99 %	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
\geq 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

An SIS can be considered to be type B if one of the three conditions governing type A is not met.

Table 1.7: Architectural constraints on type B SIS

For each sub-system of an SIS which is helping to create an SIF, we calculate the SFF and the anomaly tolerance ($N = 0$ to 2). Crossing these two orthogonal entries gives, for each of the preceding tables, the maximum value of the SIL which we can announce for each sub-system. The maximum authorised value for the SIL of the safety function is obtained by applying the combination rules illustrated in sub-paragraph 7.4.3.1.6 of standard 61508-2.

The objective declared in the standard concerning taking into account the architectural constraints is that, for all sub-systems and therefore for the SIS, it permits a robust architecture to be obtained which takes the complexity into account. Without wanting to anticipate the conclusions given in chapter 2 of this report, we can already declare that it seems to us that the use of the SFF does not meet the announced objective.

Finally we have to recall that as well as determining the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ or PFH indicators and architectural constraints concerning random material failures, the standard asks us to consider

the existence of systematic failures in order to control them using qualitative instructions. Remember that these failures do not enter into the field covered by this work.

In order to conclude this first chapter, one last piece of information must be given for better understanding of the organisation and operation of an SIS. This is explained in the next paragraph.

1.5.3. Organisation and operation of a SIS

By returning to figure 1.12, we can easily discover the typical constitution of a SIS. This is composed of the following three sub-systems:

- ***Sub-system S (Sensor)***: this is made up of a set of input elements (sensors, detectors) which monitor the evolution of the physical-chemical parameters representing the process performance (temperature, pressure, flow, level, etc.). If at least one of these parameters exceeds a set level and remains there, this deviation constitutes which was called demand or solicitation emanating from the EUC process. It is detected by the sensors involved that send a signal to the LS sub-system.
- ***LS sub-system (Logic Solver)***: this sub-assembly of logic elements carries out the decision making process which is completed by activating the third sub-system FE. The LS sub-system can be a dedicated programmable logic controllers (PLCs) or a micro-computer equipped with specific software.
- ***FE sub-system (Final Element)***: these elements act directly (emergency stop valves) or indirectly (solenoid valves) on the process to neutralise its deviation by generally stopping the system (safe state) for a length of time which must be specified for each safety function [IEC 61508-6].

If assuring the safety of an installation and the safeguard of its environment, particularly human, is the primary objective given for standard IEC 61508 and its users, the latter must, furthermore, monitor the good operational availability of their installations, as indicated in standard IEC 61511. In other words, correct analysis of the performance for the SIS requires studying not only their capability to meet a safety demand from the EUC but also the consequences of them possibly being triggered at the wrong time.

A more realistic example of SIS is given in figure 1.14.

Figure 1.14: An example of SIS

1.6. Conclusion and summary

In this first chapter we have first of all looked at the definitions for fundamental terms in the domain of safety in order to raise, if possible, any ambiguity regarding the meaning that we give them in the remainder of this report. We then provided details on the outline and organisation of standard IEC 61508 which is the reference document for our doctoral work.

Using the idea of tolerable risk and identification / evaluation of inherent risks in the studied process, the second part of chapter 1 helped us to determine risk reduction performances expected for the safety instrumented system at least partially responsible for controlling them.

This progressive focus has concentrated our attention on these SIS which are the central focus of our research.

In order to study them as exhaustively as possible, it is going to be necessary to analyse and give more details on the main concepts and definitions attached to it, because they are not exempt from ambiguity. This will be the topic of the next chapter.

Chapter 2

Prior clarification on certain definitions and fundamental concepts from the IEC 61508 standard

2.1. Introduction

If, as we have already said, the IEC 61508 and 61511 standards provide a formalised and rigorous step to obtain the SIL in line with the safety rules which are given and from this very interesting and efficient organisational point of view, they do not present any less significant disadvantages regarding its applicability.

The statement of certain concepts and major definitions is vague and sometimes ambiguous. Furthermore, the probabilistic approach proposed (not imposed) in volume 6 to calculate two performance indicators for the SIS which are $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH is marred by two important disadvantages. The first is that this approach is based on analytical formulas given without explanatory comments or justification. The second disadvantage lies in their restricted field of application.

Before processing $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH as probabilistic calculation in chapters 3 and 4, we will look in this second chapter at clarifying certain concepts and key-definitions from IEC 61508 standard by often comparing them with their corresponding section of IEC 61511 standard.

We also propose to demonstrate, at the end of the chapter and based on simple examples, the relatively restricted scope of the validity domain for the analytical formulas given in annex B of the IEC 61508-6 standard for the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ from the different SIS architectures used.

To try and make this clearer, we must first of all remember or give more details regarding the definitions of some fundamental quantities for the reliability/availability of the components and systems on the basis of which the aforementioned concepts and definitions have been developed. This will be the topic of the next section.

2.2. Reminders concerning some fundamental reliability/availability quantities

The definitions below concern a well defined system S , whose constitutive components are considered as new when $t = 0$ and “as good as new” after their repair. The moment of the first failure of S is T . T is therefore also the life time of S , if S is not repairable. It is a continuous random variable.

2.2.1. Reliability [NF X 60-500, 1988]

- **Definition** – The reliability of S is its aptitude to accomplish a required function, under given conditions and for a given time interval.
- **Measurement** – The reliability of S at time t is measured by the probability, written $R_S(t)$, that S does not fail over the duration $[0, t]$. We therefore have:

$$R_S(t) = \text{prob}(t < T) \quad (2.1)$$

- **Note** – To make things easier, although abusing the language, we often call reliability the probability $R_S(t)$.

So, the unreliability or distribution function is expressed as the probability of the complementary event:

$$F_S(t) = 1 - R_S(t) = \text{prob}(t \geq T) \quad (2.2)$$

The curve for $R_S(t)$ is decreasing monotone and we have:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} R_S(t) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} R_S(t) = 0 \quad (2.3)$$

- **The failure density $f_S(t)$** or probability density of the random variable T is defined as follows:

$$f_S(t) = \frac{dF_S(t)}{dt} \quad (2.4)$$

For sufficiently small increases dt , $f_S(t) dt$ expresses the probability that S will fail between t and $t + dt$, knowing that it was working at $t = 0$.

- **The hazard rate $r_S(t)$ or failure rate**, now written $\lambda_S(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$\lambda_S(t) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{prob}(S \text{ fails between } t \text{ and } t + dt / C)}{dt} \quad (2.5)$$

where event C means that S experienced no failure during the time interval $[0, t]$.

As before, for sufficiently small increases dt , we can deduce from the preceding expression that:

$$\lambda_S(t) dt = \frac{\text{prob}[(t < T \leq t + dt) \cap (t < T)]}{\text{prob}(t < T)} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\lambda_S(t) = \frac{1}{dt} \frac{\text{prob}(t < T \leq t + dt)}{\text{prob}(t < T)} = \frac{f_S(t)}{R_S(t)} = \frac{-\left[\frac{dR_S(t)}{dt}\right]}{R_S(t)} \quad (2.7)$$

By integrating each member of the equality (2.7), we obtain:

$$R_S(t) = \exp \left[- \int_0^t \lambda_S(u) du \right] \quad (2.8)$$

2.2.2. Availability [NF X 60-500, 1988]

- **Definition** – The availability of S is its aptitude to be in a condition to accomplish a required function, in given conditions and at a given moment (resp. over a given interval of time), whilst supposing that external resources are provided. This definition concerns instantaneous availability (average resp.).

- **Measurement** – The availability of S at moment t is measured by the following probability:

$$A_S(t) = \text{prob}(\text{S is in operating state at moment } t) \quad (2.9)$$

- **Note** – The corresponding lack of availability (unavailability) can be deduced:

$$Q_S(t) = 1 - A_S(t) \quad (2.10)$$

We therefore have:

$$A_S(t) = R_S(t), \quad \text{if S cannot be repaired} \quad (2.11)$$

$$A_S(t) \geq R_S(t), \quad \text{in the general case} \quad (2.12)$$

- **Conditional failure intensity** $\lambda_S^v(t)$

This is formally defined by:

$$\lambda_S^v(t) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{prob}(\text{S fails between } t \text{ and } t + dt / D)}{dt} \quad (2.13)$$

where the event D means that S was working at $t = 0$ and it is also working at time t .

$\lambda_S^v(t)$ is sometimes known as *Vesely's failure rate* [Cocozza, 1997].

- **Unconditional failure intensity** $w_S(t)$

This intensity is formally defined by:

$$w_S(t) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{\text{prob}(\text{S fails between } t \text{ and } t + dt / E)}{dt} \quad (2.14)$$

where event E means that S was working at time $t = 0$.

$w_S(t)$ is sometimes called *failure frequency* [Schneeweiss, 1981] [Amari, 2000]. In the case of non-repairable systems, we have:

$$w_S(t) = f_S(t) \quad (2.15)$$

Equalities (2.13) and (2.14) respectively induce (2.16) and (2.17).

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_S^v(t) dt &= \text{prob}(\text{S fails between } t \text{ and } t + dt / D) \\ &= \text{prob}[A / D] = \text{prob}[A / E \cap F] = \text{prob}[(A / E) / F] \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

where event F means that S was working at moment t .

$$w_S(t) dt = \text{prob}(\text{S fails between } t \text{ and } t + dt / E)$$

So:

$$w_S(t)dt = \text{prob}(A / E) = \text{prob}(B) \quad (2.17)$$

Conditional event B can be expressed in the following way:

$$B = (B \cap F) \cup (B \cap \bar{F}) \quad (2.18)$$

If, now, we suppose that a single failure can also emerge between t and $t+ dt$, the event $(B \cap \bar{F})$ cannot happen, because it corresponded to a repair followed by a failure in interval dt . In these conditions, the equality (2.18) shows that the composite event $(B \cap F)$ is reduced to event B, which means that the equality (2.16) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_S^v(t).dt &= \text{prob}(B / F) = \frac{\text{prob}(B \cap F)}{\text{prob}(F)} = \frac{\text{prob}(B)}{\text{prob}(F)} \\ &= \frac{\text{prob}(A / E)}{\text{prob}(F)} = \frac{w_S(t).dt}{A_S(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

• **Marginal importance factor** $MIF_{S,c}(t)$

This factor ($MIF_{S,c}(t)$ for Marginal Importance Factor) is often called the Birnbaum importance factor $I_{S,c}^B(t)$ [Birnbaum, 1969]. It is expressed formally as the partial differential of the unavailability of system S , $Q_S(t)$, compared to the unavailability $Q_c(t)$ of its constituent components.

$$MIF_{S,c}(t) = I_{S,c}^B(t) = \frac{\partial Q_S(t)}{\partial Q_c(t)} \quad (2.20)$$

To make the notation lighter, we write $Q_S(t) = p(S)$ and $Q_c(t) = p(c)$, where the letter S, which designates the studied system, also represents its structure function. If components c are independent and they have binary behaviour, $Q_S(t)$ can be expressed as a binary function of $Q_c(t)$. The expression (2.20) can then be developed in compliance with Shannon's decomposition of the S function or, more directly, according to the theorem of total probabilities:

$$\begin{aligned} MIF_{S,c}(t) &= \frac{\partial p(S)}{\partial p(c)} = \frac{\partial [p(c).p(S/c) + p(\bar{c}).p(S/\bar{c})]}{\partial p(c)} \\ &= \frac{\partial [p(c).(p(S/c) - p(S/\bar{c})) + p(S/\bar{c})]}{\partial p(c)} \\ &= p(S/c) - p(S/\bar{c}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

All the states for which the system S fails can be broken down into two subsets S_1 and S_2 . The first is all the states for which the repair of component c repairs the system S and the

second is all the states for which it is not the case or for which c does not fail. In terms of structure function, this gives:

$$S = c A + B \quad (2.22)$$

$$\text{with} \quad S/c = A + B \quad \text{and} \quad S/\bar{c} = B \quad (2.23)$$

These last two functions describe the preceding states $S_1 \cup S_2$ and S_2 respectively. We see that:

$$S/c = A + S/\bar{c} \quad (2.24)$$

We can calculate the probability $p(S)$ from the expression (2.24):

$$\begin{aligned} p(S/c) &= p(A) + p(S/\bar{c}) - p[A.(S/\bar{c})] \\ &= p(A) + p(S/\bar{c}) - p(A) p\left[\frac{(S/\bar{c})}{A}\right] \\ &= p(S/\bar{c}) + p(A) \left[1 - p\left[\frac{(S/\bar{c})}{A}\right]\right] \\ &= p(S/\bar{c}) + p(A) \cdot p\left[\frac{\overline{(S/\bar{c})}}{A}\right] \\ &= p(S/\bar{c}) + p[A.\overline{(S/\bar{c})}] \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

Comparing equalities (2.21) and (2.25) leads to a new expression for the marginal importance factor:

$$\begin{aligned} MIF_{S,c} &= p(S/c) - p(S/\bar{c}) = p[A.\overline{(S/\bar{c})}] = p(A.\bar{B}) \\ &= p((A+B).\bar{B}) = p[(S/c).\overline{(S/\bar{c})}] \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

$MIF_{S,c}$ is therefore the probability that the system S is in a critical working or failed state in relation to c [Dutuit et al., 2005]. More explicitly, $MIF_{S,c}(t)$ is the probability that S is, at time t , working so that failure of c will put it in a breakdown state, or is failed so that repairing c will set it working again.

We write as $CRIT_{S,c}(t)$ the probability that the system S is in a critical operating state regarding component c at time t , meaning in a state for which S is not in breakdown, but for which failure c would put it in breakdown. We can then deduce from it:

$$CRIT_{S,c}(t) = A_c(t) \cdot MIF_{S,c}(t) \quad (2.27)$$

where $A_c(t) = p(\bar{c})$ is the instantaneous availability of component c .

For sufficiently low incremental values dt and supposing that S was working at time $t = 0$, the probability that the system will fail between t and $t + dt$ can be written:

$$prob(S \text{ fails between } t \text{ and } t+dt) = w_S \cdot dt = \sum_{c \in S} CRIT_{S,c}(t) \cdot \lambda_c^v(t) \cdot dt \quad (2.28)$$

We end up with the following expression, which has been shown to have practical use [Dutuit et al., 2005] [Cocozza, 1997]:

$$w_S(t) = \sum_{c \in S} MIF_{S,c}(t) \cdot w_c(t) \quad (2.29)$$

where $w_c(t) = \lambda_c^v(t) \cdot A_c(t)$, in compliance with the equality (2.19). For a component equipped with a constant failure rate $\lambda_c(t) = \lambda_c$, we have [Kumamoto, 1996]:

$$w_c(t) = \lambda_c \cdot A_c(t) \quad (2.30)$$

The definition and notions recalled in this section are going to make it easier for us to tackle the following section dedicated to clarifying certain concepts and definitions which appear throughout standard IEC 61508. Their inaccurate or even confusing nature has also already been emphasised in numerous writings [Zhang et al., 2003] [Hokstad et al., 2004] [Signoret, 2005a] [Innal et al., 2006].

2.3. A necessary clarification

This clarification firstly concerns the meaning of the two modes of operation (low demand and high or continuous demand) already evoked in paragraph 1.5.1 of the preceding chapter, as well as searching for a criterion that helps to distinguish them without ambiguity. But does this criterion actually exist and is it really useful? We will then examine the notions of safety integrity, $PF_{D_{avg}}$, PFH and safe failure fraction (SFF).

2.3.1. Low demand mode of operation and high demand or continuous mode of operation

Let us start by recalling the definitions given in the reference documents, standards 61508 and 61511, in order to open the debate.

2.3.1.1. "Official" definitions

- Project on standard IEC 61508 [Misumi et al., 1999]
 - *Low demand mode* corresponds to the case where the demand frequency is lower than the proof-test frequency.
 - *High or continuous mode* corresponds to the case where the demand frequency is significantly higher than the proof-test frequency.

- Current IEC 61508 standard
 - *Low demand mode*: where the frequency of demands for operation made on a safety-related system is **no*** greater than one per year and no greater than twice the proof-tests frequency.
 - *High or continuous demand mode*: where the frequency of demands for operation made on a safety-related system is greater than one per year or greater than **twice*** the proof-tests frequency.
- Current IEC 61511 standard
 - *Demand mode*: where a specified action (for example, closing a valve) is taken in response to process conditions or other demands. In the event of a dangerous failure of the safety instrumented function a potential hazard only occurs in the event of a failure in the process or the BPCS (Basic Process Control System).
 - *Continuous mode*: where in the event of a dangerous failure of the safety instrumented function a potential hazard will occur without further failure unless action is taken to prevent it.

2.3.1.2. Comments

A first general comment can be formulated concerning the questionable quality of the French translation of the standard and, particularly, the non-uniformity of these three pairs of definitions. A second comment will emphasise that there is no clear difference made between the high demand mode and the continuous mode. For the analyst to appreciate no doubt?

As far as the definitions given in the provisional version are concerned, we can remark on the dissymmetrical nature of their duality: the expression (simply) “less than” is used for the low demand mode, whilst the “significantly” greater expression appears in the definition relating to high or continuous demand mode. Furthermore, how can we interpret the adverb “significantly”? Does it indicate a factor of 2, 3, 5, 10 or more? Finally, is the reference to the frequency of the proof-tests sufficient or relevant to be able to discriminate the two operating modes in all cases? In fact, an SIS assuring a SIF is made up of at least three sub-assemblies (sensors, logic unit, actuators) characterised by times and test periods which are often different. In these conditions, what is the frequency of the proof-tests to be considered?

By comparison, in the current version of the IEC 61508-4 standard, the conditions affecting the frequency of the demand, which define the two operating modes, are clearly expressed in dual forms of each other, at least in the English language version. This is an advantage from the point of view of definition uniformity. The other side of the coin is that these two definitions refer to a threshold value (annual demand frequency equal to 1) and a ratio of frequencies equal to 2, given without any justification. What is the origin of this and do they really have universal value, in other words are they valuable for all cases which we are likely to meet?

As for the IEC 61511-1 standard, it sets the occurrence conditions for an UE (the pleonastic expression *potential hazard* is used) so much so that it defines the operating

* The words in bold do not appear in the current French version of the IEC 61508-4 standard !

modes. It stands out however that the low demand mode is characterised by the fact that an UE can occur if a demand emanating from the process or the BPCS appears whilst the SIS is already unavailable, whilst for the high or continuous demand mode, the occurrence of an UE can result from a single failure in the SIS.

The point of view expressed in this standard is interesting, because it brings to light that the characteristics of the SIS involved in the demand mode (low demand) is its (average, as we will see) availability whilst its reliability is linked to the continuous mode.

We can, however, remark that if all references to an annual frequency greater than or less than 1 no longer appear in the test for the two operating modes, this was maintained in attached note 2 (page 44 of bilingual IEC 61511-1 standard). It remains unjustified.

The review of the different definitions for the low demand and high or continuous demand modes, which we have just covered, did not give us a really satisfying answer to the question that we raised: *is there a clear definition for each of these two modes, based on a specific and discriminating criterion?*

We are going to attempt to answer this question during the next sub-paragraph.

2.3.1.3. Search for a discriminating criterion

As demand is omnipresent in the three definitions given above, it is sensible way to integrate it into the behavioural model for the SIS studied, as done by several authors [Misumi et al., 1999] [Bukowski, 2006]. They all chose a Markov model. We will do the same, although more explicitly. In fact, each sub-assembly of a SIS can undergo non detectable faults on line, which can only therefore be discovered and repaired during proof-tests following their occurrence (hidden failures). The behaviour of this type of periodically tested system, monitored over several test periods, cannot be correctly reported by a classic Markov model. This requires the use of a multi-phase Markov model [Innal et al., 2006], if you have to use a Markov model at all. Strictly speaking, its name is ambiguous, or even incorrect, because incorporating proof-tests into the model makes it non Markovian, if we consider it as a whole. This multi-phase model is in fact piecewise Markovian [Bukowski, 2001], as its behaviour is Markovian between each couple of regeneration moments t_i [Kumar et al., 2008]. These moments are such that $t_{i+1} - t_i = T$, interval between two consecutive tests. Out of habit, we will, however, continue to classify this model as multi-phase Markovian. In chapter 3 we will show that this kind of model easily allows us to obtain the average value for the unavailability for the SIS studied but, more interestingly, we will also see that a good approximation of this average value can be provided by the asymptotic value of the SIS unavailability calculated on the basis of a classic Markov model deduced from the multi-phase model.

To clarify this idea, let us consider the case of a SIS equipped with the simplest of architectures, the 1oo1 architecture. The corresponding multi-phase model is given to figure 2.1 and its continuous approximation is represented in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1: Multi-phase Markov model of a SIS with 1oo1 architecture

Figure 2.2: "Approached" Markov model of a SIS with 1oo1 architecture

By integrating the process demand, we obtain the model from figure 2.3, which we will comment on. The unavailability states KO(DU) and KO(DD) from the model in figure 2.2 have been added (state 3).

Figure 2.3: "Approached" Markov model for a SIS (1oo1) integrating the demand

Each of the states from the preceding graph is identified by three labels. The top label indicates the state of the SIS (OK for on state; KO for failure state), the middle label indicates the nominal state of the EUC (OK), the withdrawal state in safety (STOP) or the accident state (ACCIDENT). The lower label corresponds simply to numbering the different states for the overall system (SIS + EUC).

The λ_d parameter is the rate that the demand occurs, whilst λ_D is the sum of the dangerous fault rates which are detected (λ_{DD}) and undetected (λ_{DU}).

μ_r is the inverse of the average duration of a return in EUC operation after it has been stopped by the SIS reacting to a demand, whilst μ is the inverse of the average duration of SIS unavailability, following a detected or undetected failure.

State 2 corresponds to the SIS stopping the process (EUC withdrawn into safe state: safe shutdown) which is supposed to have reacted as soon as the demand occurred.

State 4 is in fact an absorbing state, as it corresponds to an extended or definitive stop due to an accident. However, to be able to evaluate the frequency of such an accident beforehand, it would be necessary to have a sufficient number of identical systems to the one we are studying and monitor the nominal or accidental evolutions over a consequent temporal period, and then use the resulting feedback. As this cannot be envisaged, we can simulate the behaviour of this virtual assembly of systems by reiterating the behaviour of the studied system immediately after the accident occurred a great many times. The transition between states 4 and 1 is therefore, almost immediate (μ_R has a very high value), because nothing else can modify the system's state after the accident, except for its complete restoration for which the duration is considered as neutral (masked time).

We will verify in paragraph 2.3.3 of this chapter that the average behaviour, over a sufficiently long period, of the modelled system by the multi-phase Markov graph is correctly returned by the asymptotic behaviour of its continuous Markov model. This means we can calculate the average value of the frequency of the accident, w_{acc} :

$$w_{acc} = p_3(\infty) \cdot \lambda_d = p_1(\infty) \cdot \frac{\lambda_D}{(\lambda_d + \mu)} \cdot \lambda_d \quad (2.31)$$

Now $p_1(\infty) \cdot \lambda_D$ is the average value w_{SIS} of the frequency of the SIS failure. We therefore obtain:

$$w_{acc} = \frac{\lambda_d}{(\lambda_d + \mu)} \cdot w_{SIS} \quad (2.32)$$

- For the continuous mode of operation, we have $\lambda_d \gg \mu$, giving:

$$w_{acc} \approx w_{SIS} \quad (2.33)$$

This equality shows that the accident will occur as soon as the SIS breaks down. Which complies with the statement of the condition given in IEC 61511-1 standard.

Furthermore, by assimilating the occurrence rate λ_d for the demand at its frequency f_d , the condition $\lambda_d \gg \mu$ can be written:

$$f_d = \frac{1}{T_d} \gg \mu = \frac{1}{MDT_{SIS}} \quad (2.34)$$

$$\text{So: } MDT_{SIS} \gg T_d \quad (2.35)$$

where MDT_{SIS} is the average of the SIS unavailability durations and T_d is the average duration between two successive demands.

Now, we will show in chapter 3 that for the 1oo1 architecture involved and considered alone, the MDT is expressed as follows:

$$MDT_{SIS} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR \quad (2.36)$$

Taking account of the fact that $\lambda_{DU} = (1-DC) \cdot \lambda_D$ and $\lambda_{DD} = DC \cdot \lambda_D$, the preceding equality is simplified:

$$MDT_{SIS} = (1-DC) \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \quad (2.37)$$

Depending on the numerical values allocated to these parameters in IEC 61508 standard ($DC = 0.6 ; 0.9 ; 0.99$, $T_1 = 730$ hr at 87600 hr, $MTTR = 8$ hr), we systematically check that:

$$MDT_{SIS} < \frac{T_1}{2} \quad (2.38)$$

Jointly taking into account the inequalities (2.34) and (2.38) leads us to:

$$f_d \gg \frac{2}{T_1} = 2 \cdot f_{TP} \quad (2.39)$$

where f_{TP} is the frequency of the periodic tests.

Therefore, for the specific case of the 1oo1 architecture, we find the condition defining the high or continuous demand mode of operation, which is given in the current IEC 61508 standard. We understand the origin of factor 2 which is evoked there and which is also mentioned in note 2 attached to the definition given in standard 61511-1.

However, it is important to remember that the expression (2.39) has only been established for the 1oo1 architecture. For the 1oo2 architecture, for example, factor 2 is replaced by factor 3. Furthermore, if the term T_1 is also found in the 1oo2 architecture and all the other $KooN$ configurations, this is due to the simple reason that all the components of this kind of architecture are identical and tested simultaneously on the same dates. This is not the case for components belonging to the different sub-systems making up an SIS. As the explicit reference to factor 2 and at unique test period T_1 are only valid for the 1oo1 architecture, they should not figure in the definition of the continuous demand mode of operation. Subsequently, they should not appear in low demand mode either.

Before concluding, let us look at this last mode.

- For this mode of operation, we can no longer neglect μ in front of λ_d but to the contrary consider that μ is greater than λ_d . In this case, the general expression (2.31) which we must return to can be written as follows:

$$w_{acc} = p_3(\infty) \cdot \lambda_d \approx \lambda_d \cdot PFD_{avg} \quad (2.40)$$

Because $p_3(\infty)$ corresponds to the average value of the SIS unavailability and therefore of its PFD , as we will soon see.

If we refer to the inequality (1.2) we can see that PFD_{avg} is equal to the inverse of the risk reduction factor, that we had written RRF . This observation is, however, only valid for a

given SIS architecture acting alone, meaning without being associated with other protection layers. We will come back to this point.

To conclude this part dedicated to the two modes of operation for SIS, we are proposing a new criterion to help us distinguish between the two, or even three, modes of operation, regardless of the SIS architecture being studied. If the use of this criterion seems to be difficult or not relevant, a more general solution could then be envisaged. This will be the focus of our second proposal.

• **Proposal 1**

Working from the diagram below which generalises figure 2.3, it represents the graph showing states-transitions for a SIS, integrating the demand and the common cause failures.

Figure 2.4: States-transitions generic graph for a SIS integrating the demand.

States 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 represent respectively the nominal operating state (NOS), all the critical ‘on’ states regarding the SIS unavailability (COS/U), all the critical failure states regarding the accident (CFS/A), the safe shutdown (SS) state and the accidental state.

By examining it, we can easily conceive that what distinguishes low demand from high demand is how easy it is to move down from state 3 to state 2 or state 5.

If the probability of returning to state 2 is (clearly?) greater than the probability of going towards state 5, we are in low demand domain. The opposite case characterises high demand domain. Comparing these probabilities returns to comparing λ_d to parameter $\mu_{3,2}$, which is actually the inverse of the SIS’s *MDT*.

We can then propose the following classification (table 2.1: w_d represents the frequency of the demand and $\mu = 1/MDT_{SIS}$).

Modes of operation	Criteria
Low demand	$\mu > \lambda_d \Leftrightarrow \lambda_d \cdot MDT \approx w_d \cdot MDT < 1$
High demand	$\mu \leq \lambda_d \Leftrightarrow \lambda_d \cdot MDT \approx w_d \cdot MDT \geq 1$
Continuous demand	$\mu \ll \lambda_d \Leftrightarrow \lambda_d \cdot MDT \approx w_d \cdot MDT \gg 1$

Table 2.1: One way of distinguishing the different demand modes for a SIS

Two criticisms can from now on be formulated when we meet this criterion:

- As opposed to the period T_1 for the tests mentioned in the current definitions of the modes of operation for SIS, the MDT is not directly accessible data. It is necessary to calculate it, but this is exactly what contributes to giving this criterion its general character.
- What does the “ $\gg 1$ ” symbol represent in numerical terms (very large in front of the unit)?

Raising the inherent ambiguity when estimating the magnitude size attached to this symbol is not actually fundamental, because it only concerns the *continuous demand* mode, which we can apprehend most easily.

Having identified the type of demand, it remains to verify that the basic condition (1.2) or $freq(TE) = w_{tolerable}$, rewritten in compliance with the ratio (2.3) for the continuous or high demand or the ratio (2.40) for the low demand is satisfied. So:

$$w_{acc} = w_{SIS} \leq w_{tolerable}, \text{ for continuous demand} \quad (2.41)$$

$$w_{acc} = w_d \cdot PFD_{moy} \leq w_{tolerable}, \text{ for low demand} \quad (2.42)$$

• **Proposal 2**

If the preceding proposal is not upheld we can then choose a step which might seem iconoclastic and presumptuous because it crosses the constraints linked to exact identification of SIS solicitation modes and the need to calculate the PFD_{avg} or the PFH (see paragraphs 2.3.3 and 2.3.4) to check whether the level of integrity for the SIS studied reaches the required SIL.

This method requires

- knowing or estimating the frequencies w_d and $w_{tolerable}$;
- constructing the states-transitions model for the assembly (EUC + SIS) which therefore integrates the demand into the image of the graph which is represented in figure 2.4;
- deducing from it the failure frequency $w_{EUC+SIS}$ which is therefore the w_{acc} ;
- and compare it with $w_{tolerable}$.

This highlights the system approach and the concept of result obligation. Its logic is simple, clear and general.

2.3.2. Safety integrity

The IEC 61508-4 standard defines this as: Probability of a safety-related system satisfactorily performing the required safety functions in all specified conditions within a stated period of time

The definition given in the IEC 61511-1 standard is almost identical with the important exception of adding the qualifier "average" for the probability. This gives the fact that safety integrity is the average probability of a safety instrumented system satisfactorily performing the required safety instrumented functions in all the specified conditions within a stated period of time

It is interesting to compare these two definitions to what is given in the French standard X 06-501 for reliability [NF X 06-501, 1984]: reliability is a device's aptitude to accomplish a required function in the usage conditions and for a determined period of time.

This same standard completes this definition by adding that the term "reliability" is used as a characteristic indicating a probability or a fraction of success.

This addition is welcome, because it helps us to distinguish the ability (reliability or safety integrity) of an entity to accomplish a given function from its measurement (the probability). This is not the case for IEC 61508-4 and IEC 61511-1 standards which therefore reduce safety integrity to its measurement. This contradicts the relevance of taking into account the architectural constraints introduced in the associated IEC 61508-2 standard to counterbalance the exclusive use of probabilities, which were judged to not be reliable enough!

Finally, if we can agree to recognise the similarity evoked between the safety integrity and reliability, we might be surprised to see that the main indicator used in the standard to measure safety integrity for an entity in its low demand mode of operation has nothing to do with its reliability but exclusively its average availability ($PF_{D_{avg}}$). The IEC 61511-1 standard also mentions the average value of the safety integrity: "average probability of a safety instrumented system satisfactorily performing the required safety instrumented functions under all the stated conditions within a stated period of time."

One way of getting over the aforementioned ambiguities and contradictions could be, as proposed by Jean-Pierre Signoret, to define safety integrity for an entity as the confidence that we have in its ability to carry out its expected function over a specified time period and in equally specified conditions. This ability would be evaluated by comparing its average measurement (we keep the $PF_{D_{avg}}$) with the four safety integrity levels (SIL) which are well known, the confidence in this ability being even greater the lower its average probabilistic measurement. This proposal is interesting, even if the words confidence and reliability have the same meaning. Its only disadvantage lies in the fact that confidence is highly subjective and it is not the confidence but its subject, meaning the ability, that is measured. Why don't we return to the initial definition of the standard replacing "probability" with "ability" and adding an explanatory note saying that this ability is the average availability of the entity concerned measured by the complement to 1 of the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ in the case of low demand mode and its reliability measured indirectly by the PF_{FH} in the high demand or continuous demand case?

2.3.3. Average probability of failure on demand

2.3.3.1. Nature of the PFD

This average probability written PFD_{avg} is not defined in volume 4 of IEC 61508 standard, which is nevertheless given over exclusively to definitions and abbreviations. However it is currently admitted and recognised that this probability is simply the *average unavailability of an E/E/PE safety-related system*, which makes it incapable of carrying out its safety function correctly, when it is requested for this purpose by a demand from the equipment under control (EUC). The name used in the standard (*PFD*) is even less appropriate because it makes you think that it designates a probability of failure per demand, usually designated by the Greek letter Gamma (γ).

We can also note the *idea of average unavailability is formally distinguished from asymptotic* (when this exists) or *stationary unavailability*. This distinction, which is particularly imposed for periodically tested systems which do not have a stationary regime, is *systematically ignored*, both in the standard and by some authors attempting to calculate the *PFD* of the different SIS basic architectures [Zhang et al., 2003] [Beuguin et al., 2007] [Guo et al., 2007].

We think it is useful to clarify this point by showing that actually, under certain conditions, asymptotic unavailability can constitute a good approximation of average unavailability. We are going to illustrate this fact on the basis of two elementary cases which are elements making up all the architectures of SIS studied afterwards.

The first case is a component for which dangerous failures are immediately detected (DD for Dangerous Detected) then repaired straight away. The second is a component for which the failures remain hidden and are only detected during the next proof-test (DU for Dangerous Undetected) then repaired immediately.

In compliance with the assumptions retained in standard 61508, the failure rates λ_{DD} and λ_{DU} are considered as constants. This is not necessarily the same for repairs, as the standard does not mention the repair rate, but the average repair or restoration duration (*MTTR*). *Uncertainty remains* therefore regarding the law governing the repair duration: exponential law or repair duration considered as constant? Both cases are looked at below for each type of component.

2.3.3.2. (λ_{DD}, μ) or (λ_{DD}, τ) type component

The expression for the instantaneous availability $A(t)$ of the first type of component is well known for each of the two variants taken into consideration [Pagès et al., 1980] [Rausand et al., 2004].

- Variant 1 (constant failure rate and repair rate)

$$A_1(t) = \frac{\mu}{\lambda_{DD} + \mu} + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_{DD} + \mu} \cdot e^{-(\lambda_{DD} + \mu) \cdot t} \quad (2.43)$$

$$\text{We can immediately deduce } A_1(\infty) = \frac{\mu}{\lambda_{DD} + \mu} \quad (2.44)$$

The characteristic allure of the $A_1(t)$ curve is represented in figure 2.5 by discontinuous lines.

- Variant 2 (constant failure rate and constant repair duration τ)

$$A_2(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{DD}^k}{k!} (t-k\tau)^k \cdot e^{-\lambda_{DD}(t-k\tau)} \cdot u(t-k\tau) \quad (2.45)$$

$$\text{with } u(t-k\tau) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{si } t \geq k\tau \\ 0 & \text{si } t < k\tau \end{cases}$$

The asymptotic unavailability $A_2(\infty)$ is easily expressed as a function of the corresponding MUT and MDT :

$$A_2(\infty) = \frac{MUT}{MUT+MDT} \quad (2.46)$$

Because there is only one operation state for the component in question, we have:

$MUT = MTTF = \frac{1}{\lambda_{DD}}$. Because there is also only one failure state for this same component, we also have $MTTR = MDT = \tau$. We therefore obtain:

$$A_2(\infty) = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_{DD} \cdot MDT} \quad (2.47)$$

We can see, with no surprise, that $A_1(\infty) = A_2(\infty)$, because in the first case $\mu = 1/MTTR = 1/\tau$.

Curves $A_1(t)$ and $A_2(t)$ are represented in figure (2.5) for a given set of parameters λ_{DD} and $MTTR$.

Figure 2.5: Curves $A_1(t)$ and $A_2(t)$

We can see that if $A_1(t)_{\lambda, \mu}$ differs from $A_2(t)_{\lambda, \tau}$, the common limit value at $A_1(\infty)$ and $A_2(\infty)$ is nevertheless attained quickly after a few τ , if $\lambda_{DD} \cdot \tau = \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\mu} \ll 1$.

We can also remark that $A_2(t)$ oscillates around its limit value $A_2(\infty)$ whilst coming increasingly closer.

For both cases studied and for sufficiently large $t = T$ before τ , the measurement of the space under the curve $\int_0^T A_i(t) dt$ is very close to the air $A_i(\infty) \cdot T$. We can therefore deduce from it:

$$A_{avg} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T A_i(t) dt \approx \frac{1}{T} \cdot [A_i(\infty) dt \cdot T] = A_i(\infty) \quad (2.48)$$

This is of course the same for average and asymptotic unavailabilities. This classic result shows that for (λ, μ) or (λ, τ) type components and for systems made up of these components, it is justified to assimilate the average unavailability calculated over a sufficiently large duration, and therefore the $PF_{D_{avg}}$, for the corresponding asymptotic unavailability. What about the second type of components?

2.3.3.3. Periodically tested components

The characteristic parameters of a component of this type taken into consideration in IEC 61508 standard are the failure rate λ_{DU} , its test period T_1 and its $MTTR$. Considering the numerical values used in IEC 61508-6 standard for these parameters ($\lambda_{DU} \in [5.10^{-10} \text{ hr}^{-1}$ to $2.5.10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}]$; $MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$; $T_1 \in [1 \text{ month to } 10 \text{ years}]$), we can assimilate the curve for the variations of the immediate unavailability depending on the time $\bar{A}(t)$ of a periodically tested component on a saw tooth graph, with a well known allure (fully drawn curve on figure 2.6).

Figure 2.6: Curve $\bar{A}(t)$ for a periodically tested component

We can easily deduce from this the average value of this unavailability over any period $T = k T_1$, with $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$:

$$\bar{A}_{avg}(0, T) \approx \bar{A}_{avg}(0, T_1) \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU} \cdot T_1}{2} \quad (2.49)$$

In compliance with what was declared in sub-paragraph 2.3.1.3, the average behaviour of a periodically tested component, which fails to be correctly rendered by a multi-phase Markov model, can be approximated by the asymptotic behaviour of a classic Markov model for which we have previously determined the return rate for the partial or total failure states.

This latter model is called the approached Markov model. The evolution of the unavailability over time which is deduced from this is represented on a dotted line in figure 2.6.

For the elementary case we are looking at, the approached Markov model is given in figure 2.7. The return rate μ here is such that its inverse has a value neighbouring $T_1/2$ (see chapter 3). We can deduce the value of the asymptotic unavailability for the component:

$$\bar{A}(\infty) = \frac{MDT}{MUT+MDT} \approx \frac{\frac{T_1}{2}}{\frac{1}{\lambda_{DU}} + \frac{T_1}{2}} \quad (2.50)$$

In the frequent case where $\frac{T_1}{2} \ll \frac{1}{\lambda_{DU}}$, the expression (2.50) is simplified and provides the same result as given in (2.49).

Figure 2.7: Classic Markov model to only be used in stationary regime

The title for diagram 2.7 reminds us that we should not make the mistake of assimilating instantaneous unavailability for a periodically tested entity, calculated using a multi-phase Markov model (solid line curve in figure 2.6), with instantaneous unavailability for this same entity calculated using its approached Markov model. Only average unavailability values calculated from the first model and the asymptotic unavailability from the second are compatible.

2.3.3.4. Systems made up of proof-tested components

If we abide by the restrictive usage instructions for the approached Markov model, it therefore appears that it effectively allows us to obtain a good approximation of the average unavailability for a periodically tested component. But, is what is true on the scale for a component considered individually always at the level of a system made up of several components of this type? In other terms, can we use the model from figure 2.7 to construct the approached Markov model for a system made up of periodically tested components in order to deduce from it an approximation of its average unavailability? The answer is no, as illustrated by the following counter example.

Let us consider a system made up of two identical components ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_{DU}$) operating in active redundancy and periodically tested at the same successive moments kT_1 , where $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$. We can suppose that there are enough repairmen. The Markov model for this type of system is known. It is represented below.

Figure 2.8: Markov model resulting from the approached individual model

The symptomatic unavailability of the system can be easily deduced, by always considering that $\frac{T_1}{2} \ll \frac{1}{\lambda_{DU}}$.

$$\bar{A}_S(\infty) = \left(\frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_{DU} + \mu} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_{DU} + \frac{2}{T_1}} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{\lambda_{DU} \cdot T_1}{\lambda_{DU} \cdot T_1 + 2} \right)^2 \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU}^2 \cdot T_1^2}{4} \quad (2.51)$$

Now, the average value of the unavailability for this kind of system is known. It is easily calculated over the period T_1 . We obtain:

$$\bar{A}_{avg}(0, T_1) \approx \frac{1}{T_1} \int_0^{T_1} (\lambda_{DU} \cdot t)^2 dt = \frac{\lambda_{DU}^2 \cdot T_1^2}{3} \quad (2.52)$$

We can immediately see that the asymptomatic unavailability (2.51), calculated from the Markov model for a system, drawn up directly on the basis of the approached Markov model for the periodically tested component does not constitute a good approximation of average unavailability for this system.

This is generally the same when we calculate the average value for the *PFD* of a system directly from the values found for the *PFD_{avg}* of its components. In the elementary case we examined (1oo2 architecture), this error is therefore due to the fact that we have considered that the average value of a product of mathematical functions, even simple functions, was equal to the product of the average values of these functions. This is not the case, as a general rule. We have already indicated this problem [Innal et al., 2006] which is often not detected [Summers, 2000].

Let us remember that to be able to exploit it, the approached Markov model for the system should be constructed case by case, after the return rates from its partial or total failure states have been determined following an analysis of the conditions governing each return.

So, for the case being looked at, the right approached Markov model is shown in figure 2.9, for which $\mu_1 = 2/T_1$ and $\mu_2 = 3/T_1$ (see chapter 3).

Figure 2.9: Approached Markov model from the studied system

We can deduce from it:

$$\bar{A}_S(\infty) = \frac{2 \lambda_{DU}^2}{2 \lambda_{DU}^2 + 3 \lambda_{DU} \mu_2 + \mu_1 \mu_2} \approx \frac{2 \lambda_{DU}^2}{\mu_1 \mu_2} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}^2 \cdot T_1^2}{3} \quad (2.53)$$

We find the result given (2.52).

To finish with the methods to calculate the average unavailability ($PF_{D_{avg}}$) for a system made up of periodically tested components, we can state that the value of this type of unavailability can be:

- calculated exactly from the multi-phase Markov model (see chapter 4),
- estimated exactly using a Petri net model animated by a Monte-Carlo simulation (see chapter 4),
- approximated validly by the asymptotic unavailability value resulting from an approached Markov model, for which we will have already determined the return rates for the failure states.
- however, it cannot be approximated by the value of the asymptotic unavailability obtained from a Markov model drawn up over the only basis of the parameters λ and μ belonging to the approached Markov model for the typical component making up the system. This is true in the very general case where the average duration to repair the components is negligible compared to their test period.

Finally we can note that if the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ is recognised as being the major indicator for an SIS's ability to fulfil its safety function in low demand mode of operation, it is only *a partial indicator, like any average and therefore insufficient*.

This important point is developed in paragraph 2.5.2.

2.3.4. Probability of dangerous failure per hour (PFH)

2.3.4.1. Preliminary considerations

As before, no definition of this probability of failure per hour appears in the summary of CEI 61508-4 standard dedicated to definitions. One indication of its nature is however given as a footnote (CEI 61508-1: Note 4 – page 64 of the bilanguage version): “The parameter in table 3 for high demand or continuous mode of operation, probability of a dangerous failure per hour, is sometimes referred as the frequency of dangerous failure, or dangerous failure rate, in units of dangerous failures per hour.”

This definition is ambiguous however, because it gives the wrong idea that a failure frequency and a failure rate are equivalent ideas. *We will raise this ambiguity in a short while.* Two ways of calculating it, also not equivalent, are also explicitly mentioned, in two other volumes:

- The calculation procedure described in paragraph B.3.1, on page 74 of the IEC 61508-6 standard is recalled *in extenso* below: the overall probability of a dangerous failure (understood per hour) for a safety function of a E/E/PE system relating to safety is determined by calculating the dangerous failure rates for all the sub-systems assuring the safety function and by adding these individual values.
- Note 5 located at the foot of page 64 of IEC 61508-1 standard states that to obtain this probability, we must determine the failure probability of the safety function during the mission time and divide this probability by the mission time.

Let us look at each of them.

The first procedure does not take into account the real architecture of the SIS studied, as it assimilates it in all cases into a generalised series-architecture. It therefore leads to an over-estimation of the “equivalent” failure rate for the overall system and consequently an under-estimation of its reliability, which is conservative but penalising.

The second definition-procedure lacks rigour in its statement. What is “the probability of the safety function failing during the mission time”? That could be, at most, perceived as an average unavailability. It seems more likely, or even certain that the authors of this statement were thinking about the distribution function $F(t)$ which is only the unreliability of the SIS assuring the safety function (“...no repair can take place...”). Let us look at what this interpretation gives.

2.3.4.2. *Would it be possible to assimilate the PFH at the average value of a failure rate?*

If the probability of the safety function failing during the mission time T actually designated the unreliability $F(T)$ of the SIS, we would get:

$$PFH = F(T)/T \quad (2.54)$$

This formulation can arouse surprise because it seems that it is enough to calculate the PFH value over a long duration T to obtain a low, or even very low, value and therefore very advantageous for this probability, as $F(T)$ was limited from above by the unit, the ratio $F(T)/T$ tends towards zero when T increases.

Can we get out of this dead-end by explaining $F(T)$ as shown below? We are going to demonstrate that this is not possible.

$$PFH = \frac{F(t)}{T} = \frac{1-R(t)}{T} = \frac{1 - \exp\left(-\int_0^T \lambda(t) dt\right)}{T} = \frac{1 - \exp(-\lambda_{avg} \cdot T)}{T} \quad (2.55)$$

If, furthermore, $\lambda_{avg} \cdot T \ll 1$, the preceding expression is simplified:

$$PFH \approx \frac{\lambda_{avg} \cdot T}{T} = \lambda_{avg}(0, T) \quad (2.56)$$

The probability of failure per hour could therefore be assimilated to the average value of the failure rate $\lambda(t)$, calculated over the duration T and from then on called average failure rate, for ease, but not without risk. In fact, this average rate can in no way be used to calculate the reliability of the SIS concerned for all durations different from T .

Another disadvantage of this formulation lies in the fact that $\lambda(t)$ is expressed by an indeterminate form when t increases sufficiently, as shown by the expression (2.7). Calculating λ_{avg} no longer makes any sense. This allows us to answer no to the question set as the title to this paragraph.

This said, we can interpret the nature of *PFH* in another way. Let us look at that.

2.3.4.3. Would it be possible to assimilate the *PFH* to the average value of a probability density?

The equation (2.54) can actually be expressed as a function of the equality (2.4) as follows:

$$PFH = \frac{F(T)}{T} = \frac{\int_0^T f(t) dt}{T} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(t) dt = f_{\text{avg}}(0, T) \quad (2.57)$$

The *PFH* for an entity can be considered as the average value of its probability density, calculated over a given period T .

As for the preceding case, the value of f_{avg} obviously depends on the duration T over which it is calculated, but it is different on two points: obtaining it is not subject to satisfying a condition ($\lambda_{\text{avg}} \cdot T \ll 1$) and its limit is defined. The problem is that this limit is nil when the duration T becomes very large. As it is not conceivable to have a null *PFH*, nor can we validate the interpretation according to which this *PFH* would be the average value of a probability density.

In order to raise the hypothesis of a null limit, we should turn to other parameters, with a similar nature to the preceding ones, but for whom the domain of validity would go beyond the one of non repairable entities. We can then think of conditional and unconditional failure intensities, previously and respectively defined by ratios (2.13) and (2.14). Let us examine them.

2.3.4.4. Would it be possible to assimilate the *PFH* at the average value of failure intensity?

Which, from the unconditional failure intensity $w(t)$ or the conditional failure intensity $\lambda'(t)$ is the most suitable to represent *PFH*, via their average value?

It seems undeniable to us that the *PFH* is none other than the average value of $w(t)$, for which the other common name is “failure frequency” [Kumamoto, 1996] [Misumi et al., 1999]. Our assertion is justified by the following three considerations:

- $w(t)$ is identified at $f(t)$ in the cases of non repairable entities.
- The *PFH* is intimately associated with the “continuous demand” mode of operation for which a failure in the SIS automatically leads to a undesired event emanating from the monitored process, in the absence of other layers of protection. This simultaneity

appears in the relationship (2.41) which identifies the SIS's failure frequency with that of the undesired event (the accident): $w_{acc} = w_{SIS}$,

- The examination of the definition of $w(t)$ and $\lambda^v(t)$, also called "Vesely's rate", and the way of obtaining their average values over a duration T , reinforce our conviction.

In fact, the formal definitions of these two entities given in (2.13) and (2.14) are consistent with the following formulas giving their average values:

$$w_{moy} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T w(t) dt = \frac{W(0, T)}{T} \quad (2.58)$$

where $W(0, T)$ is the number of failures of the SIS expected over the duration T .

$$\lambda_{moy}^v = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \lambda^v(t) dt \approx \frac{W(0, T)}{TF} \quad (2.59)$$

where TF is the cumulated duration that the SIS has been working over duration T . This last equation is just an approximation and is only acceptable in a stationary regime.

Now, what interests the people in charge of the process is finding out the average number of accidents which could arise over a specified duration, which is often the system's lifetime, which of course encompasses both production periods and stoppages.

This common sense statement seems to us to definitively plead in favour of w_{avg} . From now on, we will consider that *the PFH is an average failure frequency or an average unconditional failure intensity*.

2.3.4.5. Other considerations

We can conclude paragraph 2.3.4 dedicated to the *PFH* with three comments.

- In the case of systems made up of components which can be completely and quickly repaired, the value of the accumulated operating duration is practically equal to T , meaning: $TF \# T$. It follows that w_{avg} is very close to λ_{moy}^v and therefore to $\lambda^v(\infty)$ because for this type of system, $\lambda^v(t)$ very quickly reaches its stationary or asymptotic value.
- When calculating the limit, when t tends towards infinity, of the two members of the equality (2.30), we obtain, when these limits exist:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} w(t) &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} (\lambda_v(t) \cdot A(t)) = \left(\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_v(t) \right) \cdot \left(\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} A(t) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{MUT} \cdot \frac{MUT}{MTBF} = \frac{1}{MTBF} \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

The conditions to satisfy to obtain the first limit are recalled in [Cocozza, 1997]. They work for all the SIS architectures that we have studied.

The equality (2.60) shows us that the value of w_{avg} , calculated over a high mission time T , tends towards $\frac{1}{MTBF}$ and there is therefore a straight line relationship between the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and the PFH for a given SIS architecture. This relationship appears by combining the result (2.60) and that from a part of (2.50) completed like this:

$$\bar{A}(\infty) \approx \bar{A}_{avg}(0, T) = PF_{D_{avg}} = \frac{MDT}{MTBF} \quad (2.61)$$

This combination leads to the following result, which is also revealed when, for the same architecture, we compare the analytical expressions of PFH and $PF_{D_{avg}}$ proposed in IEC 61508-6 document:

$$PF_{D_{avg}} = MDT \cdot \frac{1}{MTBF} = MDT \cdot PFH \quad (2.62)$$

This result is valid in the case where the SIS in question is not the only or last safety layer we have. If not, the limit of PFH_{avg} , calculated over a period T tending towards infinity, is equal to $1/MTTF_{SIS}$.

2.3.5. *SFF* (Safe Failure Fraction)

The notion of safe failure fraction appears for the first time in sub-paragraph 7.4.3.1.1 of the IEC 61508-2 standard. It is defined (for a sub-system) in annex C of this volume in the form of the following ratio:

SFF = Sum of the safe failure rates (including detected dangerous failures) / Sum of all the failure rates.

Without anticipating the negative conclusions formulated during chapter 5 partly dedicated to architectural constraints and the use of the *SFF*, we can already highlight several points which are worth, at least, justifying or explaining, in order to be included and accepted by standard users:

- If the detected dangerous failures are effectively considered as dangerous to calculate the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ they are assimilated into the safe failures to calculate the *SFF*.
We can admit this double belonging if it is explained that detecting dangerous failures on line leads systematically either to making the EUC safe during their repair or implementing compensatory measures to make sure that the manufacturing or production process is not interrupted, in complete safety.
- The aforementioned sub-paragraph clearly specifies that the *SFF* must be calculated for all the sub-systems which run the safety function. Now, apart from series sub-systems, no others can have a constant failure rate depending on the time, unless confined to the stationary regime, when this exists.
The preceding difficulty is outlined in annex C of IEC 61508-6 standard by ignoring the real architecture of the sub-systems in question and assimilating them all into the series-systems. This is a gross approximation, conservative yet penalising. If we have to keep the notion of *SFF*, it will be necessary to explain that it can only be conceived at component level.

- The *SFF* was introduced to compensate the supposed systematically dreadful effects (being optimistic) on determining the *SIL* which would be due to the inherent inaccuracy of the reliability data used during probabilistic calculation of the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and *PFH*. This defiance is paradoxical because what type of data is the *SFF* built on, if not the failure rates which are also used during random probability calculations?

Another notion which must be clarified involves the type of failures in the equipment to be registered to determine the different parameters of interest ($PF_{D_{avg}}$, *PFH* and *SFF*). This will be the topic of the next paragraph. Finer analysis of the relevance of the *SFF* and its use appear in chapter 5.

2.4. Proposal for failure classification

2.4.1. Classification appearing in the standard

The standard distinguishes random failures (hardware failures) and systematic failures. *Only the former are considered in this document.* In these conditions, on page 40 of volume 4, the standard distinguishes dangerous failures from safe failures:

- *Dangerous failure*: failure which has the potential to put the safety-related system in a dangerous state or a state where it cannot fulfil its function.
- *Safe failure*: failure which does not have the potential to put the safety-related system in a dangerous state or a state where it cannot fulfil its function.

Another difference comes from the fact that these failures can be detected, or not, by tests on line. The former are known as detected failures and the latter, which can only be revealed during proof-tests off line or when the EUC requests the SIS, are known as undetected failures. The following diagram is classically presented to summarise this double division.

Figure 2.10: Type of failures according to IEC 61508 standard

The simplicity of this classification leads to three comments:

- The first definition is not self-sufficient because it is “in drawers” (dangerous failure → dangerous state). It is better therefore to define what a dangerous state is beforehand. This is not done explicitly in the standard which brings us back to the ideas of a dangerous

situation and dangerous event. The idea of a undesired event would be more appropriate because this type of event is easier to identify as resulting from the presence of a dangerous state (the SIS is unavailable and therefore cannot fulfil its function) and the appearance of a demand from the EUC which must be protected.

- Safe failures are defined by opposition (here as opposed to dangerous failures), meaning by what they do not lead to. It would have been simpler to define them ‘positively’ which situates them better when compared to spurious trip failures *which are not even mentioned in the standard*. The latter failures correspond, for example, to inopportune triggering of a safety action. An example to illustrate this type of failure is the case of an overpressure sensing system which sends a signal to the decision unit which, in turn, controls closing the safety valves, when there is really no overpressure at all.
- This classification of failures leads to the definition of the corresponding failure rates, systematically used in the standard. This is a source of ambiguity, because if we can in general easily qualify the failure rate of a component as dangerous or safe, this is not the same case for a system, even a simple system. This explains why *the option of accurately defining the different states in which we can find a system is preferable to the option of defining its dangerous and safe failure rates directly*. The definition of the latter and the possible failures in the system will moreover be possible to identify beforehand from its potential states, as we will soon see.

2.4.2. Classification proposed by SINTEF

In the [SINTEF, 2006] manual this organism proposes a finer and more realistic classification than before, as it takes into account the spurious trip failures and the non-critical failures which are defined below. This classification is summarised by the following tree structure:

Figure 2.11: Failure classification according to SINTEF

To summarise, the PDS method by SINTEF considers three types of failure at component level: dangerous, spurious trip and non critical.

- Dangerous failures are those appearing in the standard and they are therefore divided into detected failures (λ_{DD}) and undetected failures (λ_{DU}).
- The spurious trip failures are a subset of safe failures and they are also divided into detected failures (λ_{STD}) and undetected failures (λ_{STU}).
- Non critical failures (λ_{NONC}) are those which have no affect on the two main functions of the EUC system, meaning its ability to produce (production availability) and its ability to not cause undesired events (safety).

So, in other terms and according to the PDS method “dangerous and spurious trip failures are considered critical, as they affect basic/main functions (ability to shut down on demand and ability to maintain production when safe).”

Working from this classification, a failure rate classification was deduced, summarised below:

- λ_{DD} and λ_{DU} are defined in the IEC 61508 standard.
- λ_{STD} is the detected spurious trip failure rate. This corresponds to λ_{SD} in the IEC 61508 standard.
- The sum ($\lambda_{STD} + \lambda_{NONC}$) corresponds to λ_{SU} of the IEC 61508 standard.
- The sum ($\lambda_D + \lambda_{STD} + \lambda_{STU}$) is called λ_{crit} .

SINTEF then proposes for the *SFF* a slightly different expression from the standard where the total λ is replaced by λ_{crit} , being:

$$SFF = 1 - [\lambda_{DU} / \lambda_{crit}] \text{ instead of } SFF = 1 - [\lambda_{DU} / \lambda]$$

This should barely influence the numerical results, and more importantly does not contribute any extra justification to the relevance of this measure.

The most founded criticism which we can formulate for the SINTEF classification is that it considers spurious trip failures as a sub-category of safe failures, even if they are said to be critical (regarding production availability). The often evoked examples of untimely triggering of an airbag or the untimely reversal of thrust flow in a reactor in full flight are sufficient to show that this classification is less reducing.

2.4.3. Classification proposed by TOTAL

J.P.Signoret proposes a typology for failures which is different from above [Signoret, 2005b] [Signoret, 2006b]. He distinguishes failures which increase the probability of taking a SIS to a dangerous state, from failures that reduce this probability. Within the first type of failures we distinguish the non safe failures which tend to lead the SIS into a more dangerous state than the nominal state, but without actually driving it into a dangerous state, and dangerous failures, properly speaking, which tip the SIS into a dangerous state. In the same way, within the second category we can distinguish safe failures which take the SIS into a less dangerous state than the nominal state, which do not impose stopping the monitored system (EUC), and spurious trip failures which lead to inopportune stoppage of the controlled system.

Another way of describing the preceding division is to say that the first type of failures tends to inhibit the SIS's expected function in the event of a demand, whilst the second type tend to anticipate triggering this function, meaning even before a demand appears.

Regardless of its formulation this division, which always differentiates detected from undetected failures, seems to be more accurate to us than the others and it has the advantage of relying on another division, which is generally easier to understand, which involves all the

states in which the SIS can be. This explanatory link between the different types of failures and their different possible states for the SIS is illustrated by the following diagrams.

The first (Figure 2.12) is produced by J.P. Signoret [Signoret, 2006b]. It represents the functional and dysfunctional behaviour of a system in 2oo3 configuration. We can clearly distinguish between the grading of states likely to be affected by the system, as well as the safe failures (λ_s) and dangerous or unsafe failures (λ_{ns}) for its elements.

Figure 2.12: Behavioural model for a 2oo3 system

In order to confront what has just been presented, we can propose a second diagram (figure 2.13), which can be easily generalised. In the case of a $KooN$ ($0 < K < 3$ et $0 < N < 4$) system, this synthetically illustrates both aforementioned failure categories at the same time (which tend to either inhibit the safety function of an SIS or anticipate its triggering) and the grading of the states now affected by the system. To make it easier to compare this model with the preceding model, the titles for the different states of the latter are marked on the tree diagram.

Figure 2.13: Links between inhibiting failures (anticipating resp.) and resulting states for a $KooN$ system.

We can thereby deduce the expression for the roots generating the preceding tree diagram (figure 2.14).

Figure 2.14: Roots generating links in the $KooN$ systems

2.5. Limitations for the analytical formulas giving the PFD

2.5.1. Context and objective of this particular study

Although we are constantly reminded that annexe B of volume 6 of CEI 61508 is for informative and not mandatory purposes, a great many people working within the framework of this standard are tempted to apply or are applying formulas presented there *without wondering beforehand whether they are really valid*. They doubtless think that the fact that these formulas have been published in an official document must guarantee their relevance and now they just have to be applied to satisfy the standard-related conditions. Now, this way

of thinking, which highlights the concept of obligation of means, is likely to lead to erroneous evaluations (mainly of the PFD_{avg}) which could prove dangerous. This leads to the objective of this short section which aims to show, on the basis of two simple examples, how the domain of application for the aforementioned formulas is limited; these limits having been imposed by respecting *restrictive hypotheses which also affect the behaviour of the components taken individually and the behaviour of the systems*. These two aspects are illustrated in the following paragraphs.

2.5.2. Limitations revealed at component level

For all the cases looked at in the IEC 61508-6 document, the individual behaviour of components is only governed by the following parameters: the dangerous failure rate λ_D , the diagnostic coverage DC , the interval between consecutive periodic tests T_1 and the average of the repair durations $MTTR$. *This does therefore not take into account important parameters such as the duration of the tests, possible unavailability of the component during these tests and their effectiveness* (they might not detect dangerous failures in tested components). We can easily understand that it is difficult, or even impossible, to integrate the latter parameters in an analytical formula, whilst they have already been taken into consideration in specialised software to process fault trees, such as the one used for the ARALIA calculation engine. This is not merely anecdotal, as shown in the different results relating to calculating the PFD_{avg} below. They clearly demonstrate *the superiority of a system or holistic method, such as the fault tree, over the analytical approach*; this advantage being shown even in the field of application for the formulas. The case considered involves the 1oo1 architecture.

- **Field of application for the formulas**

The values for the parameters taken into account are as follows:

$\lambda_D = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $DC = 85\%$; $T_1 = 4380\text{hr}$ (6 months); $MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$. The formula in question is repeated below:

$$PFD_{avg} = \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR$$

The values obtained are very close: $8.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (formula) and $8.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (fault tree).

If the formula gives a slightly conservative value, it only gives that, meaning an average value which does not report on the amplitude of PFD variations over time, as shown in figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15: PFD (t)

Although the idea of SIL is only applied to the safety function performed by an SIS and not to its components or sub-systems, we have put levels SIL1 and SIL2 on the preceding graph. We can see that even if the PFD_{avg} for the studied 1oo1 architecture is in the SIL2 area, this architecture spends a large part of its time (39.9%) in SIL1 area. *This fact completely escapes the analytical approach.* These first results are grouped together in table 2.2.

Methods	Formula (standard)	Fault tree
Parameters		
PFD_{avg}	8.41 E-3	8.36E-3
PFD_{max}	?	1.65E-2
Duration of stay in SIL2 zone (as a %)	?	55.5
Duration of stay in SIL1 zone (as a %)	?	39.9

Table 2.2: A few results relating to the 1oo1 architecture (basic case)

- **Extended field of application for the formulas**

The limited applicative scope of the formulas (obviously) appears more clearly when we go beyond the restrictive hypotheses constraining them. Table 2.3 groups together the results obtained after fault tree processing of the preceding case enriched by taking into account the x , σ , and π parameters which respectively indicate the unavailability of the component during the test, the probability that the test will detect the dangerous failure and its duration. Here $x = 0$; $\sigma = 0.9$; $\pi = 1\text{hr}$.

Methods	Formula (standard)	Fault tree
Parameters		
PFD_{avg}	8.41 E-3	1.016E-2
PFD_{max}	?	1
Duration of stay in SIL2 zone (as a %)	?	49.75
Duration of stay in SIL1 zone (as a %)	?	49.72

Table 2.3: A few results relating to the 1oo1 architecture (extended case)

We can see the penalising effect over all the indicators in question (PFD_{avg} , PFD_{max}) for integration in the fault tree model for realistic parameters. Of course this effect escapes the analytical approach which, for example, can only provide one *value* which this time is *not conservative for PFD_{avg}* .

2.5.3. Limitations revealed at system level

The deficiencies of the analytical approach which are demonstrated at a component level are naturally also found at system level. Adding new limitations which translate the inability of the analytical approach to process the case of the staggered tests, diversified redundancies and sharing resources. These limitations are moreover explicitly quoted at the start of annex B of IEC 61508-6.

We are going to illustrate the first two of them below by looking at the case of a 1oo2 architecture.

- **Staggered tests**

The two channels each have the characteristics of the previously analysed 1oo1 configuration, being $\lambda_D = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $DC = 85\%$; $T_1 = 4380\text{hr}$ (6 months); $MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$, to which we add the parameters β and β_D relating to common cause failures which are detected (β_D) and undetected ($\beta = 2 \beta_D = 0.2$).

The system approach, which we recommend, relies on the fault tree represented in figure 2.16 for this case. The results which come from it and those obtained by applying the formula proposed in the standard are grouped together in table 2.4.

Figure 2.16: Fault tree relating to the 1oo2 architecture valid for simultaneous and staggered tests

Test and methods	Simultaneous tests ($T_1 = 4380 \text{ hr}$)		Staggered tests ($T_1 = 4380 \text{ hr}; \Delta T = 2190\text{hr}$)	
	Formula	Fault tree	Formula	Fault tree
<i>PFDAvg</i>	1.74E-3	1.72E-3	?	8.80E-4
<i>PFDMax</i>	?	3.47E-3	?	1.75E-3

Table 2.4: Results relating to a homogeneous 1oo2 architecture

On reading the previous table we can see that test staggering helps to reduce average and maximum values of $PFDA(t)$ by half. In other words, the only value which is capable of providing the analytical approach for the case studied is two times too pessimistic, in the case of the staggered tests.

- **Diverse redundancy (heterogeneous components)**

This time we are considering a 1oo2 architecture made up of two different types of channel. The first has the characteristics described above, whilst the characteristics of the second are given below:

$$\lambda_D = 4.10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}; DC = 60\%; T_1 = 8760\text{hr (1 year)}; MTTR = 8 \text{ hr.}$$

Processing it in this case via the preceding fault tree does not create any problems. It is enough to modify the parameters relating to one of the channels and neutralise the contribution of the common cause failures, because we consider that the two channels have no common material or organisational characteristic. On the other hand, the standard does not supply any formula corresponding to this case, so we can see that one current practice is to use the value originating from the standard-related formula relating to the 1oo1 architecture such as common probability affected on two basic events from the fault tree represented in figure 2.17.

Figure 2.17: Fault tree being used as the basis for an erroneous calculation of PFD_{avg}

*This way of working, fairly widespread let us remember, is erroneous** and leads to *non conservative results*, meaning here optimistic, as shown in table 2.5.

Method	Formula + Mini-Fault tree	Fault tree
<i>PFDavg</i>	5.92 E-4	6.50E-4

Table 2.5: Results relating to a heterogeneous 1oo2 architecture

2.5.4. A first impression

The aim of this short section 2.5 was, based on simple examples, to demonstrate that the *analytical formulas proposed in volume 6* of IEC 61508 standard could only be applied within the framework of restrictive hypotheses which involved both the *component level* and the *system level*.

* The average of a multiplication is not equal to multiplying its averages

The former impose:

- *a null test duration*, which excludes taking into account the availability or unavailability of the element during these tests.
- *perfect tests* (“i.e. all failures that remain undetected are detected by the proof test”);

The second exclude:

- *Staggered tests*;
- *diversified redundancies* (“the channels in a voted group all have the same failure rates and diagnostic coverage”; “for each subsystems there is a single proof test interval”)
- *sharing resources* (“multiple repair teams are available to work on all known failures”);

This brief reminder of the conditions restricting the use of analytical formulas of the standard shows that these same conditions also strongly restrict the interest during the analysis of typical architectures taken individually. We will see in chapter 3 that the observation is even more severe when it is a matter of modelling and evaluating complete SISs, which is, however, the scope of IEC 61508-6.

2.6. Conclusion and summary

The aim of this second chapter was to clarify certain concepts and major definitions given in the IEC 61508 standard in order to raise any ambiguity regarding their comprehension before implementing or using them.

If a consensus seems to have been reached on the definitions for safety integrity (*SI*) and the average failure probability on demand ($PF_{D_{avg}}$) this is not the case for the different SIS operating modes and the probability of failure per hour (*PFH*).

For the former, we are proposing a criterion to distinguish them. This criterion is based on the confrontation between two perfectly defined amounts: the demand frequency from the EUC and the average unavailability duration for the associated SIS.

Regarding the *PFH*, we propose to identify the unconditional failure intensity of the SIS. It will be measured by the long term average value of this intensity, which is equal to the inverse of the *MTBF* (average duration separating two successive failures), in the case where the SIS in question can be replaced by one or several layers of protection, and to the inverse of the *MTTF* (Mean Time To (first) Failure) in the opposite case.

Without anticipating the finer analysis which will be done in chapter 5 on the safety failure fraction (*SFF*), it already seems to us that the comments which it raised in paragraph 2.3.5 anticipate its disqualification as a relevant indicator.

There is one last point to discuss which we have examined: the type of failures. We can see that several classifications have been proposed which agree on splitting all the failures into two large categories. However, they differ in terms of names for sub-categories which each of them share. *It also seems prudent to us to reserve the classifications of “dangerous”*

and “safe” for elementary component failures and only distinguish the nature of the states at a systems level.

Finally, a brief complementary study has just shown that the hypotheses which condition obtaining analytical formulas giving $PF_{D_{avg}}$ for the SIS architectures proposed in the standard are constraining and strongly limit the field of application.

As the announced clarification has been attempted, it is best right now to cover the second part of the objective we have set! This refers to proposing a methodical step which explains how we can end up with analytical formulas given without justification in annex B (informative) of the IEC 61508-6 standard and give more details on the domain of validity.

The next chapter is thereby given over to determining the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ for the $KooN$ type architectures presented in the aforementioned annex, whilst chapter 4 is dedicated to their respective PFH .

Chapter 3

Analysis of the low demand mode of operation (determining the PFD_{avg})

3.1. Objective of the analysis and reminder of the general hypotheses

By placing ourselves in the validity domain for the analytical approach implemented in volume 6 of the standard, in this chapter we are proposing, on the basis of four SIS configurations (1oo1, 1oo2, 1oo2D and 1oo3), to demonstrate how their “low demand” mode of operation is processed by the three methodologies that we have studied. We only have theoretical knowledge of the first two (IEC 61508-6 and SINTEF) and have never implemented them in the field. On the other hand, we have shared the practice of the third with TOTAL, with J. P. Signoret, and we have also centred our academic activities on it. This methodology will from now on be known as the *holistic* approach in the rest of this report. As far as the first is concerned, we will force ourselves to *explain how the analytical formulas it proposes can be found* using which supplementary hypotheses. The subjacent hypotheses to the other two approaches will also be explained, but we can already mention that the three approaches suppose that failures obey the exponential model (constant failure rate) and that all components, once repaired, are “as good as new”. Furthermore, there are always enough repairers available.

To conclude this introduction, we will recall the fundamental supplementary hypothesis on which our demonstration is structured:

The average long term behaviour (meaning beyond its transient regime) of a system, made up partially or totally of periodically tested components and modelled by a multi-phase Markov model, can be approximated by the asymptotic behaviour of this same system although modelled by a classic Markov graph ($\lambda; \mu$) from which we have previously determined the return rate for the failure statuses.

This hypothesis has already been validated by the examples in paragraph 2.3.3 and it will be revalidated in paragraphs 3.2.1 and 3.3.4. However, to our knowledge, this hypothesis has surprisingly never been mentioned in the numerous works and publications presenting Markov models on the behaviour of an SIS [Zhang et al., 2003] [Guo et al., 2005] [Goble, 1998] [Goble, 2000] [Goble, 2005] [Rouvroye et al., 1999] [Knegtering et al., 1999].

In this chapter, only dangerous failures are considered in compliance with standard 61508-6.

3.2. 1oo1 Architecture

3.2.1. Standard approach (IEC 61508-6)

Remember that this basic architecture (figure 3.1) is composed of a single channel and that consequently all dangerous failures lead to the loss of the safety function.

Figure 3.1: Physical (a) and reliability (b) block-diagrams relating to the 1oo1 architecture

The preceding reliability block-diagram shows that the 1oo1 system has two failure modes which are mutually exclusive (dangerous detected DD and dangerous undetected DU). Furthermore, as this system is periodically tested (interval between tests equal to T_1), its behaviour during a task with a given duration is correctly described by a multi-phase Markov model, as already shown in figure 2.1, reappearing afterwards in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo1 architecture

To use this model, it is necessary to monitor that the values for the probabilities of occupying states at the beginning (b_i) of phase i are deduced from those obtained at the end (e_{i-1}) of the preceding period ($i-1$):

$$P_1(b_i) = P_1(e_{i-1}); P_2(b_i) = P_2(e_{i-1}) + P_3(e_{i-1}); P_3(b_i) = 0.$$

The analytical formulas deduced from this model are already “heavy” and their calculations require the use of adapted software: So, to make them more accessible, it is necessary to approximate, as announced, the preceding model by a classic Markov model which is ‘continuous’ or approached, given in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Continuous Markov model relating to 1oo1 architecture

It is advisable to mention that the duration of the repair inherent to state 3 is not exponentially distributed, but that this hypothesis gives the formula provided in the standard. We know that this is not the hypothesis used by the authors of the standard, but they have never officially declared this!

If the repair rate $\mu_{DD} = 1/MTTR$ is known, the second, μ_{DU} , must be determined via the instant t_{DU} corresponding to the average value of the instant that the first (and only) undetected dangerous failure occurs over the interval T_1 (figure 3.4) [Zhang et al., 2003].

Figure 3.4: Average instant when a DU failure occurs over $[0, T_1]$

The instant t_{DU} can quickly be determined by solving the following equation:

$$t_{DU} \cdot \int_0^{T_1} f(t) \cdot dt = \int_0^{T_1} t \cdot f(t) \cdot dt \quad (3.1)$$

where $f(t) = \lambda_{DU} \cdot \exp(-\lambda_{DU} \cdot t)$. By approximating all the exponential functions that result from it by their *second-order* Taylor series expansion [Innal et al., 2005], we obtain $t_{DU} \approx T_1/2$. At this stage, we should note that this result is only valid if $\lambda_{DU} T_1 \ll 1$. Furthermore, the preceding expression for $f(t)$ is only acceptable if the average duration for staying in state 2 is brief, meaning if $MTTR \ll T_1$. In these conditions, we obtain:

$$t_{c1} \approx T_1 - t_{DU} + MTTR = \frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR = \frac{1}{\mu_{DU}} \quad (3.2)$$

The continuous model's approximation of the multi-phase Markov model allows us to estimate the average probability of failure on demand (PFD) at the expense of two supplementary approximations:

- Assimilating the PFD_{1001} to the system's asymptotic unavailability (already seen),
- Assimilating its $MTBF$ to its $MTTF$.

We therefore obtain:

$$PFD_{1001} = 1 - P_1(\infty) = P_2(\infty) + P_3(\infty) = MDT / MTBF \approx MDT / MTTF \quad (3.3)$$

$P_1(\infty)$ refers to the continuous model, of course. By exploiting this model, we can easily deduce the following expressions:

$$MTTF = 1 / \lambda_D \text{ and } MDT = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \frac{1}{\mu_{DU}} + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \frac{1}{\mu_{DD}} = t_{CE} \quad (3.4)$$

From equations (3.3) and (3.4), we then get:

$$PFD_{1001} = \lambda_D t_{CE} = \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.5)$$

Expressions (3.2) and (3.5) are those given on page 52 of the IEC 61508-6 standard.

More direct and precise way of obtaining the preceding result is to resort to the fault tree formalism, which is the dual of the reliability block diagram model used in the standard. This way of operating is acceptable taking into consideration the values for λ_{DD} , λ_{DU} and μ_{DD} and the hypothesis required to determine μ_{DU} , which allows us to consider the *detected and undetected behaviour* of the 1oo1 architecture as being *practically independent*.

Figure 3.5: Fault tree relating to the 1oo1 architecture

The fault tree for the 1oo1 architecture is represented in figure 3.5 and its operations lead to the following result:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A}_S(\infty) &\approx \bar{A}_{DU}(\infty) + \bar{A}_{DD}(\infty) = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_{DU} + \mu_{DU}} + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_{DD} + \mu_{DD}} \\ &\approx \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} = \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

Expressions (3.5) and (3.6) are identical.

Let us make the most of the occasion to check on a first *KooN* architecture that the fundamental hypothesis recalled in paragraph 3.1 is well founded.

To do this, we process a first fault tree model for a 1oo1 architecture using specialised software in compliance with the multi-phase Markov model in figure 3.2, then a second one in compliance with the model in figure 3.3.

We obtain the saw tooth curve on figure 3.6 for the first and the continuous curve for the second, as we did before for the case of a mono-mode component (see figure 2.7).

Figure 3.6: Average behaviour / Asymptotic behaviour (1oo1 architecture)

To be more precise, we have calculated the average value PDF_{avg} on the basis of the saw tooth curve and the asymptotic value attained by the continuous curve $\bar{A}(\infty)$ from the following set of data: $\lambda = \lambda_D + \lambda_S$ (with $\lambda_D = \lambda_S$) = 5E-5 ; $T_1 = 1$ year, $DC = 0.6$; $MTTR = 8$ hours. They are very close to each other, which validates our hypothesis:

- $PDF_{avg} = 4.27 \text{ E-}2$
- $\bar{A}(\infty) = 4.22\text{E-}2$

3.2.2. SINTEF approach

Under the same hypotheses as before ($\lambda_{DU} \cdot T_1 \ll 1$ and $MTTR \ll T_1$), the [SINTEF, 2006] reference expresses the PDF_{avg} as follows, very close to what is given in (3.5), which is not surprising.

$$PDF_{1001} = \lambda_{DU} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} + \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.7)$$

In fact, for SINTEF, the name PDF_{avg} is reserved for the average unavailability due to undetected dangerous failures, which is the first term of the second member of (3.7), whilst its second term is called DTU_R (Down Time Unavailability due to Repair of (detected) dangerous failures).

3.2.3. Holistic approach

To model the behaviour of the systems and evaluate their interesting performances (reliability, average availability, production availability...), we recommend and for several years have implemented a rigorous system-approach, based on the use and operations of logic models (fault trees) or behavioural models (Markov graphs, Petri nets...), depending on the needs, for which the power of expression and calculation and flexibility go far beyond the limited possibilities of analytical expression presented beforehand, as we will see later on.

In this case, the behaviour of the proof-tested 1001 configuration system can be modelled accurately by a multi-phase Markov graph identical to figure 3.2. This model is then processed digitally using software in which a specific, high-performance algorithm is implemented.

A sample of results obtained this way and results from the formulas (3.5) and (3.7) are grouped together in table 3.1 below.

3.2.4. Comparing the results

We can see, without any surprise, that for this elementary case the three approaches give results which are very close to each other. We can also already remark that the results given by the standard are systematically slightly conservative (penalising), meaning (slightly) greater than the results from processing the Markov graph.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})			5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05
Approaches					
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	5.495E-3	1.099E-2	5.495E-2
		60	2.21E-3	4.42E-3	2.21E-2
		90	5.675E-4	1.135E-3	5.675E-3
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	5.4747E-3	1.09092E-2	5.2975E-2
		60	2.2067E-3	4.4068E-3	2.17735E-2
		90	5.673E-4	1.1341E-3	5.6527E-3
SINTEF	DC (%)	0	5.475E-3	1.095E-2	5.475E-2
		60	2.202E-3	4.404E-3	2.202E-2
		90	5.655E-4	1.131E-3	5.655E-3

Table 3.1: PFD_{avg} relating to the 1oo1 architecture ($T_1 = 4380hr$)

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})			5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05
Approaches					
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	1.097E-2	2.194E-2	1.097E-1
		60	4.4E-3	8.8E-3	4.4E-2
		90	1.115E-3	2.23E-3	1.115E-2
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	1.08899E-2	2.16212E-2	1.02070E-1
		60	4.3870E-3	8.7482E-3	4.27287E-2
		90	1.1142E-3	2.2266E-3	1.10659E-2
SINTEF	DC (%)	0	1.095E-2	2.19E-2	1.095E-1
		60	4.392E-3	8.784E-3	4.392E-2
		90	1.113E-3	2.226E-3	1.113E-2

Table 3.1 (cont.): PFD_{avg} relating to the 1oo1 architecture ($T_1 = 8760h$)

3.2.5. Conclusion relating to the 1oo1 architecture

Below we will summarise what it is advisable to remember about the preceding developments relating to the relevance of the analytical formula proposed by IEC 61508 standard for the 1oo1 architecture.

- *The formula (3.5) can only be obtained by following several hypotheses which are added to those stated in paragraph 2.5.4, with more general scope.* The most specific of them assimilates the average value of a system's unavailability, for which one of the two components is proof-tested, at the "equivalent" asymptotic value for the unavailability of a system for which the two components are (λ, μ) type. We have verified several times that this hypothesis can be received.
- These extra hypotheses are nevertheless acceptable, because verified for all ranges of parameter values $(\lambda, DC, MTTR, T_1)$ considered in the standard, as shown by the sound agreement which exists between the values for PFD_{avg} from the formula (3.5) and values which we can classify as "exact", obtained by exploiting the corresponding (multi-phase) Markov graph.

- The values for PFD_{avg} from the formula (3.5) are slightly conservative and therefore safe. They can therefore be used in their *validity domain* which, let us remember is *restricted*,

3.3. 1oo2 Architecture

3.3.1. Standard approach

This architecture is composed of two identical channels working in hot redundancy. It is therefore necessary for each of these channels to undergo a dangerous failure for the system to not ensure its safety function in the event of a request (IEC 61508-6, annex B).

Based on the representation given by the standard (figure 3.7), we can suppose that the chosen parameter calculation (PFD_{avg}) is done by considering separately the system's behaviour, meaning outside common cause failure, and its behaviour in the presence of common cause failure (CCF), and by simply adding their respective contributions, even if these contributions are not really independent, as shown by the multi-phase Markov model in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.7: Physical (a) and reliability (b) block-diagrams relating to the 1oo2 architecture

For this model, as for the preceding model (1oo1 architecture), the probability values for occupying states at the beginning (b_i) of phase i are deduced from those obtained at the end (e_{i-1}) of the period ($i-1$), as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_1(b_i) \\ p_2(b_i) \\ p_3(b_i) \\ p_4(b_i) \\ p_5(b_i) \\ p_6(b_i) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} p_1(e_{i-1}) \\ p_2(e_{i-1}) \\ p_3(e_{i-1}) \\ p_4(e_{i-1}) \\ p_5(e_{i-1}) \\ p_6(e_{i-1}) \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3.8: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo2 architecture

To obtain the analytical formula proposed in the IEC 61508-6 standard, we follow the same procedure as in paragraph 3.2.1.

- In a first stage, we approximate the “exact” multi-phase Markov model by a continuous model, by removing the *CCF* transitions (defined below) from state 1, and by adding the following three new transitions:
 - μ_{DU} between states 3 and 1 and states 5 and 2 respectively;
 - μ'_{DU} between states 6 and 1 (the numerical results obtained would be the same even if μ'_{DU} joined states 6 and 4, with however $\mu'_{DU} = 3/T_1$).

We consider that the overall *PFD* of the 1oo2 architecture, namely PFD_{1oo2} , is the sum of the two terms. The first, known as PFD_1 , is the result of all the individual failures from the two channels. The failures which simultaneously affect the two channels are therefore excluded. These failures (*CCF*) are represented on figure 3.8 by the transitions $\beta_D \lambda_{DD}$ and $\beta \lambda_{DU}$. The second term making up PFD_{1oo2} , known as PFD_2 , is rightly due to the *CCF* failures. The Markov model we therefore obtain is represented in figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Continuous Markov model relating to 1oo2 architecture (without CCF)

- The second stage is dedicated to determining the μ_{DU} and μ'_{DU} parameters. The first parameter has already been determined in equation (3.2): $\mu_{DU} = \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right)^{-1}$. The calculation of the second is concluded as follows:

As t_{c1} is the average duration of unavailability for the 1oo2 architecture due to successive undetected dangerous failures in both channels, appearing in the interval $[0, T_1]$ and t'_{DU} is the average occurrence moment of the second undetected dangerous failure over the same period. As before (paragraph 3.2.1) and with the same type of hypotheses, we can calculate t'_{DU} by solving the following equation:

$$t'_{DU} \cdot \int_0^{T_1} f(t) \cdot dt = \int_0^{T_1} t \cdot f(t) \cdot dt \quad (3.8)$$

with $f(t) = dF(t)/dt = d \left((1 - \exp(-\lambda_{DU} t))^2 \right) / dt$

By approximating all the exponential functions which are produced by their *third-order* Taylor series expansion [Innal et al., 2005], we obtain: $t'_{DU} \approx \frac{2}{3} T_1$ and finally:

$$t_{c1} = T_1 - t'_{DU} + MTTR = \frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR = \frac{1}{\mu'_{DU}} \quad (3.9)$$

The conclusion issued on meeting the value obtained for t_{e1} (1oo1 architecture) remains valid for t_{e1} from the 1oo2 architecture, meaning that the value $\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR$ is slightly optimistic.

- The third stage calculates the stationary probabilities of occupying the different states of the continuous model. We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_2(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}}; & p_3(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} \\
 p_4(\infty) &\approx \frac{(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}^2}{\mu_{DD}^2}; & p_5(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DU}\cdot\mu_{DD}}; & p_6(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}^2}{\mu_{DU}\cdot\mu'_{DU}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

- The mean down time MDT_1 is then calculated (stage 4) by solving the following matrix equation, in which index F indicates that this refers to failing states (failed states), $P_F(0)$ is the matrix of initial probabilities to calculate MDT_1 , M_F is the transition matrix reduced to these failed states and K_F is the matrix for the average sojourn times in these states:

$$-P_F(0) = M_F \times K_F$$

Once developed, this equation becomes:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{-p_2(\infty)\lambda_{DD}}{[p_2(\infty)+p_3(\infty)]\lambda_D} \\ \frac{-p_2(\infty)\lambda_{DU}-p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DD}}{[p_2(\infty)+p_3(\infty)]\lambda_D} \\ \frac{-p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}}{[p_2(\infty)+p_3(\infty)]\lambda_D} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -2\mu_{DD} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -(\mu_{DD}+\mu_{DU}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\mu'_{DU} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} K_4 \\ K_5 \\ K_6 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.11}$$

We therefore obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MDT_1 &= K_4 + K_5 + K_6 \\
 &= \frac{1}{(p_2(\infty)+p_3(\infty))\lambda_D} \left[p_2(\infty)\frac{\lambda_{DD}}{2\mu_{DD}} + p_3(\infty)\frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\mu'_{DU}} + \frac{p_2(\infty)\lambda_{DU}+p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}+\mu_{DU}} \right] \\
 &\approx \frac{1}{p_3(\infty)\lambda_D} \left[p_3(\infty)\frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\mu'_{DU}} + p_3(\infty)\frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} \right] = \frac{1}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\mu'_{DU}} + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we obtain:

$$MDT_1 \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} MTTR \quad (3.12)$$

By comparing this expression with the expression given in page 55 of volume IEC 61508-6, we verify that $MDT_1 = t_{GE}$ (3.13)

- Stage 5 is dedicated to calculating the asymptotic value of the failure frequency w_1 (see chapter 4) for the 1oo2 architecture in the absence of common cause failure CCF , which easily allows us to determine PFD_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 &= (p_2(\infty) + p_3(\infty)) \cdot \lambda_D = 2 \lambda_D \left[\frac{(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} + \frac{(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} \right] \\ &= 2 \lambda_D^2 \left[\frac{(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} MTTR \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

PFD_1 is deduced from the following relationship, taken from (2.61):

$$PFD_1 = \frac{MDT_1}{MTBF_1} = w_1 \cdot MDT_1 = w_1 \cdot t_{GE} \quad (3.15)$$

The preceding equation can be explained. We obtain:

$$PFD_1 = 2 \lambda_D^2 \left[\frac{(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} MTTR \right] \cdot t_{GE} \quad (3.16)$$

As $\beta \ll 1$ and $\beta_D \ll 1$, we can accept the following approximations:

$$\lambda_D = \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU} = (1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \approx (1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \quad (3.17)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} MTTR \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} MTTR \quad (3.18)$$

The last expression is known as t_{CE} in IEC 61508-6 and it can be inserted in the equation (3.16) to give the final expression for PFD_1 :

$$PFD_1 \approx 2 \left[(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \right]^2 t_{CE} t_{GE} \quad (3.19)$$

- Finally in the last stage we have to determine the contribution of CCF to the overall PFD for the 1oo2 architecture. This contribution is obtained by considering the behaviour of this architecture submitted only to CCF separately. The model corresponding to this contribution is represented in figure 3.10.

Because the two channels from this architecture fail simultaneously under the action of *CCF*, it is still supposed that their repair will start and finish in synchrony. So, the average durations of these repairs are similar to those obtained for the 1oo1 architecture, meaning $1/\mu_{DD}$ and $1/\mu_{DU}$ (see paragraph 3.2.1).

Figure 3.10: Continuous Markov model relating to 1oo2 architecture only submitted to *CCF*

By solving the system of algebraic equations reporting the asymptotic behaviour of the 1oo2 architecture, deduced from the preceding model (figure 3.10), we successively obtain expressions for MDT_2 and PFD_2 :

$$MDT_2 = [(\beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot (T_1/2 + MTTR))] / [\beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU}] \quad (3.20)$$

$$PFD_2 \approx MDT_2 / MTTF_2 = [(\beta_D \lambda_{DD} MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot (T_1/2 + MTTR))] \quad (3.21)$$

By adding the contributions given in (3.19) and (3.21) we finally obtain an approximation for the overall *PFD* of the 1oo2 architecture:

$$PFD_{1oo2} \approx 2 \left[(1 - \beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1 - \beta) \lambda_{DU} \right]^2 t_{CE} t_{GE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (3.22)$$

This is the expression given on page 55 of the IEC 61508-6 document. As previously for the 1oo1 architecture, several restrictive hypotheses and approximations are required to obtain it. Furthermore, it is relatively complicated to establish and it is not particularly likely that a ground engineer or a non expert consultant will be able to modify it to adapt it to architectures which are even only slightly different from those analysed in the standard.

3.3.2. SINTEF approach

The formula proposed by SINTEF can only be obtained if several conditions are satisfied. Let us list them:

- the two hypotheses stated in paragraph 3.2.2 must be followed again,
- PFD_{1oo2} is taken the same as the sum of the unavailability due to detected failures and the unavailability of undetected failures.
- each of the two preceding availabilities is itself the sum of the unavailability due to common cause failures and the unavailability due to independent failures.
- repair durations do not depend on the number of failed components,
- the conjunction of independent detected failures is not taken into account,
- the coefficient β linked to common cause failures is the same for detected and undetected failures.

In compliance with these hypotheses, the average PFD_2 value due to the CCF is reduced to:

$$\beta \left[\lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \lambda_{DU} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \right].$$

PFD_1 can be obtained easily considering the model from figure 3.9. According to SINTEF, PFD_1 is due to contributions from states 5 and 6,

$$p_5(\infty) \approx \frac{2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \cdot \lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DU} \cdot \mu_{DD}}, \text{ with } \mu_{DD} = \frac{1}{MTTR} \text{ and } \frac{1}{\mu_{DU}} \approx \frac{T_1}{2} \quad (3.23)$$

$$p_6(\infty) \approx \frac{2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}^2}{\mu_{DU} \cdot \mu'_{DU}}, \text{ with } \frac{1}{\mu'_{DU}} \approx \frac{T_1}{3} \quad (3.24)$$

Finally the overall PFD_{1002} proposed by SINTEF is obtained by adding the three previously determined contributions:

$$PFD_{1002} \approx \frac{T_1^2}{3} (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}^2 + 2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DD} \lambda_{DU} MTTR \frac{T_1}{2} + \beta \left[\lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \lambda_{DU} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \right] \quad (3.25)$$

We should however note that the expression really given by SINTEF differs from (3.25) by the fact that the factor $(1-\beta)$ from the first term is replaced there by $(1-\beta)^2$!

3.3.3. Holistic approach

In compliance with what was done for the 1001 architecture, we have compared the values for PFD_{avg} obtained by the application, respectively, from the formula (3.22) proposed in the standard, from the formula (3.25 modified) recommended by SINTEF and, finally, by processing the multi-phase Markov graph relating to the 1002 architecture. The latter has already been presented (figure 3.8) whilst a comparative sample of the results is given for table 3.2.

We can see a second time that the results from the formula (3.22) for the standard are systematically (but slightly) greater than those obtained by Markov processing. This is the same for the results given by the SINTEF formula, with only a few rare exceptions.

Although it has been emphasised that the fault tree is not the right model to calculate the average unavailability for a system where components have non binary behaviour and that it requires in a more general way the mutual independence of its basic events, it seems interesting to us, from an operational point of view, to confront the results issued by the application, in the event of the 1002 architecture, for the three methods of modelling and evaluating the systems that we currently use: the fault tree, the Markov approach and the Petri nets [Signoret, 2006c]. The fault tree model is given to figure 2.16 (paragraph 2.5.3), the Markov model appear in figure 3.8, whilst the Petri nets are represented in figure 3.11.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})				5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05
Approaches						
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	5.8E-4	1.2E-3	8.8E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	1.1E-3	2.3E-3	1.4E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	2.3E-4	4.6E-4	2.8E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	4.5E-4	9.0E-4	4.9E-3
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	5.6E-5	1.1E-4	6.0E-4
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	1.1E-4	2.2E-4	1.2E-3
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	5.804E-4	1.224E-3	8.451E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	1.121E-3	2.291E-3	1.325E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	2.249E-4	4.600E-4	2.699E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	4.433E-4	8.946E-4	4.779E-3
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	5.563E-5	1.119E-4	5.864E-4
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	1.109E-4	2.222E-4	1.132E-3
SINTEF	DC (%)	0	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	5.798E-4	1.224E-3	8.712E-3
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	1.121E-3	2.292E-3	1.351E-2
		60	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	2.254E-4	4.613E-4	2.724E-3
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	4.445E-4	8.973E-4	4.817E-3
		90	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	5.689E-5	1.145E-4	5.995E-4
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	1.134E-4	2.273E-4	1.158E-3

Table 3.2: PFD_{avg} relating to the 1oo2 architecture ($T_1 = 4380hr$)

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})				5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05
Approaches						
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.2E-3	2.7E-3	2.4E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.3E-3	4.8E-3	3.2E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	4.6E-4	9.7E-4	6.6E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	9.0E-4	1.8E-3	1.1E-2
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.1E-4	2.3E-4	1.3E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.2E-4	4.5E-4	2.3E-3
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.223E-3	2.690E-3	2.190E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.289E-3	4.767E-3	3.030E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	4.592E-4	9.590E-4	6.323E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.931E-4	1.817E-3	1.026E-2
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.114E-4	2.253E-4	1.230E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.211E-4	4.442E-4	2.300E-3
SINTEF	DC (%)	0	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.224E-3	2.708E-3	2.390E-2
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	2.292E-3	4.789E-3	3.213E-2
		60	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	4.600E-4	9.616E-4	6.472E-3
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	8.948E-4	1.823E-3	1.043E-2
		90	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.126E-4	2.279E-4	1.246E-3
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	2.236E-4	4.494E-4	2.331E-3

Table 3.2 (cont.): PFD_{avg} relating to the 1oo2 architecture ($T_1 = 8760hr$)

Figure 3.11: Petri nets relating to the 1oo2 architecture

Domain	Name	Definition/ Initial value
Real	LDDIN	$(\text{LAMBDA} * 0.5) * (1.0 - \text{BETAD}) * \text{DC}$
Real	LDUIN	$(\text{LAMBDA} * 0.5) * (1.0 - \text{BETA}) * (1.0 - \text{DC})$
Real	LDDCD	$(\text{LAMBDA} * 0.5) * \text{BETAD} * \text{DC}$
Real	LDDCU	$(\text{LAMBDA} * 0.5) * \text{BETA} * (1.0 - \text{DC})$
Real	BETA	-----
Real	DC	-----
Real	LAMBDA	-----
Real	BETAD	$\text{BETA} * 0.5$
Boolean	A_KO	false
Boolean	B_KO	false
Boolean	CCF_DD	false
Boolean	CCF_DU	false
Boolean	TEST	false
Real	1oo2_KO	$\# 1 == 0. \& \# 11 == 0.$

Figure 3.11 (cont.): The different used variables

As it was obligatory to consider all the basic events of the fault tree as independent, we apply probabilities to events e1, e3 and e5 measuring their intrinsic unavailability, so that $\left(\frac{\lambda}{\lambda+\mu}\right) \cdot \left(1 - \exp^{-(\lambda+\mu)t}\right)$, whilst the p(e2), p(e4) and p(e6) probabilities correspond to the unavailability of periodically tested components and the repair rate $\mu_{DD} = \frac{1}{MTTR}$.

The PFD_{avg} are calculated over a period equal to 10 years for each of the three approaches. The results appear in table 3.3.

Approaches		Markov multi-phase	Petri nets	Fault tree
$\lambda = 5E-5, \beta = 2 \beta_D = 20 \%$ $T_1 = 4380 \text{ hr}$				
DC (%)	0	1.325E-2	1.325E-2	1.327E-2
	60	4.779E-3	4.777E-3	4.796E-3
	90	1.132E-3	1.129E-3	1.143E-3

Table 3.3: Comparison of results given by the three holistic approaches for the PFD_{1002}

The results are given to the closest three decimals to refine their comparison. We can see, and this comes as no surprise, that the Markov approach and the Petri nets give very comparable results, whilst the fault tree provides slightly stronger and therefore more conservative values.

3.3.4. Last experimental validation of the fundamental modelling hypothesis

Following the example of what was done for the 1001 architecture in paragraph 3.2.1, we are going to verify experimentally that we can validly approximate the PFD_{avg} for an 1002 architecture for which the two channels are fitted with two incompatible failure modes ($\lambda_{DD}; \mu_{DD}$) and ($\lambda_{DU}; T_1/2 + MTTR$), modelled by a multi-phase Markov graph or a Petri net, by the asymptotic unavailability deduced from a continuous Markov model for this same architecture, defined by ($\lambda_{DD}; \mu_{DD}$) and ($\lambda_{DU}; \mu_{DU} = (T_1/2 + MTTR)^{-1}$).

We have chosen to model these two configurations using the same Petri net, modifying only the transition parameters relating to undetected dangerous failures (DU) to pass from one configuration to another.

The $PFD(t)$ and $\bar{A}(\infty)$ curves are represented in figure 3.12. They correspond to the following set of data:

$\lambda = 5E-5 \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\mu_{DD} = 0.125 \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $DC = 0.6$; $T_1 = 4380 \text{ hr}$ (1 year); $\beta = 2 \beta_D = 0.2$ (common cause). The window and the observation step are respectively worth $T = 5 \text{ years}$ and $\Delta t = 5 \text{ hr}$.

Figure 3.12: Average behaviour / Asymptotic behaviour (1oo2 architecture)

The curves appear as expected. We can deduce the values that we are interested in from them: $PFD_{avg} = 1.024 \text{ E-2}$ and $\bar{A}(\infty) = 1.017 \text{ E-2}$. As predicted, they are very close. This confirms the validity of the basic hypothesis in our demonstration. Furthermore, it is interesting to situate these two values compared to the value provided by the multi-phase Markov model: $PFD_{avg} = 1.026 \text{ E-2}$ (table 3.2).

3.3.5. Conclusion relating to the 1oo2 architecture

The formula (3.22) giving the analytical expression for the PFD_{avg} for the 1oo2 architecture proposed by the standard was obtained from the relatively heavy developments subject to numerous hypotheses and approximations which limit their interest. Let us remember them:

- This formula does not satisfy the general and realistic conditions listed in paragraph 2.5.4.
- This requires approximating an average probability by an asymptotic probability.
- Asymptotic probabilities coming from a “poor” behavioural model (continuous or approached Markov model) are also approximations.
- The final formula which we have thereby obtained differs formally from the standard and only complies at the expense of a last approximation.
- *In conclusion, the use of the analytical formula giving the PFD_{avg} for the 1oo2 architecture is only admitted to study independent modules of this type for which all the preceding restrictive conditions have been met.*

3.4. 1oo2D Architecture

3.4.1. Standard-based approach

This architecture is made up of two channels connected in parallel (see the physical and reliability block diagrams in figure 3.13). A “de-energized to trip” model (a power loss causes the monitored system to go to the safe position) was added to figure 3.14 to clarify the operation of the 1oo2D architecture, given in detail below.

In normal operation, when the safety function is requested, each channel can run it by simultaneously opening its own contact and the contact for the diagnostic module on the other channel. Furthermore, if the diagnostic tests find a fault in one of the two channels, the majority output voting is adapted so that the overall output state then follows that given by the other channel. In other words, if a detected fault occurs in a channel, its diagnostic module

opens its own contact, so that the overall output is the output from the other channel. If the diagnostic tests find faults in both channels or a discrepancy that cannot be allocated to either channel, then the output goes to the safe state. To detect a divergence like this, each channel can determine the state of the other channel independently.

Figure 3.13: Physical and reliability block-diagrams for the 1oo2D architecture

Figure 3.14: “De-energized to trip” electrical circuit for the 1oo2D architecture

The multi-phase Markov model relating to the 1oo2D architecture is represented in figure 3.15. The corresponding inter-phase transition matrix is given afterwards.

Figure 3.15: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo2D architecture

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_1(b_i) \\ p_2(b_i) \\ p_3(b_i) \\ p_4(b_i) \\ p_5(b_i) \\ p_6(b_i) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} p_1(e_{i-1}) \\ p_2(e_{i-1}) \\ p_3(e_{i-1}) \\ p_4(e_{i-1}) \\ p_5(e_{i-1}) \\ p_6(e_{i-1}) \end{bmatrix}$$

Once again, we are going to follow the same step as we did before for the 1oo1 and 1oo2 architectures, to try and find the analytical formulas proposed in the IEC 61508-6 standard.

- In a first stage, we approximate the “exact” multi-phase Markov model by a continuous model (figure 3.16), by removing state 6 from the former and its incident transition arcs (because we are only concerned by the system’s dangerous failures), as well as the transition arc relating to the common cause failure $\beta \lambda_{DU}$ leaving state 1 and adding two new transitions, with parameter settings μ_{DU} , between states 2 and 1 and states 5 and 3 respectively.

Figure 3.16: “Continuous” Markov model relating to 1oo2D architecture

Once again we can consider that the overall PFD of this architecture, called PFD_{1oo2D} , is the sum of two terms:

- PFD_1 determined from the model in figure 3.16;
- PFD_2 which can be attributed to common cause failures CCF , which are reduced, in this case, to $\beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right)$, because the detected dangerous failures for each channel lead open the contact on their respective diagnosis models. This brings the monitored systems into a safe state. In other words, the term $2 \beta_D \lambda_{DD}$ is eliminated.

- The second stage has already finished, because all the transitions have now been identified and known. We thereby have:

$$\frac{1}{\mu_{DD}} = MTTR, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_{DU}} = \frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR, \quad \frac{1}{\mu'_{DU}} = \frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR$$

- The third stage calculates the stationary probabilities of occupying the different states of the continuous model. Taking into account the respective orders of magnitude for the parameters λ_{DD} , λ_{DU} , μ_{DD} , μ_{DU} and μ'_{DU} , we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} p_2(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}}; & p_3(\infty) &\approx \frac{4(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} \\ p_4(\infty) &\approx \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}^2}{\mu_{DU} \cdot \mu'_{DU}}; & p_5(\infty) &\approx \frac{4(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \cdot \lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DU} \cdot \mu_{DD}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

- The mean down time MDT_1 (without the contribution of CCF) for the 1oo2D architecture is now calculated in compliance with what was done in paragraph 3.3.1.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{-p_2(\infty)\lambda_{DU}}{p_2(\infty)(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})+p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}} \\ -\frac{p_2(\infty)2\lambda_{DD}-p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}}{p_2(\infty)(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})+p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu'_{DU} & 0 \\ 0 & -(\mu'_{DU}+\mu_{DU}) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} K_4 \\ K_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.27)$$

By solving the matrix equation (3.27), we obtain:

$$MDT_1 = K_4 + K_5 \quad (3.28)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\mu'_{DU}} \left(\frac{p_2(\infty)\lambda_{DU}}{p_2(\infty)(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})+p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}} \right) + \frac{1}{\mu_{DD}+\mu_{DU}} \left(\frac{p_2(\infty) \cdot 2\lambda_{DD} + p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}}{p_2(\infty)(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})+p_3(\infty)\lambda_{DU}} \right)$$

Because $p_2(\infty) \gg p_3(\infty)$ and $\mu_{DD} \gg \mu_{DU}$, the equation (4.28) can be simplified as follows:

$$MDT_1 \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})\mu'_{DU}} + \frac{2\lambda_{DD}}{(\lambda_{DU}+2\lambda_{DD})\mu_{DD}} \quad (3.29)$$

Taking into account the fact that the λ_{DD} parameter, appearing within the model in figure 3.13, represents both λ_{DD} and λ_{SD} , we can also express (3.29) as follows:

$$MDT_1 \approx \frac{\lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right) + (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \cdot MTTR}{\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}} \quad (3.30)$$

This expression is given on page 57 of the IEC 61508-6 document under the title t'_{GE} .

- Stage 5 is dedicated to calculating the asymptotic value of the failure frequency w_1 for the 1oo2D architecture, which lets us easily determine PFD_1 :

$$w_1 = p_3(\infty) \lambda_{DU} + p_2(\infty) (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \approx p_2(\infty) (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \quad (3.31)$$

So:

$$w_1 \approx \frac{2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} \cdot (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \quad (3.32)$$

PFD_1 is then calculated via the following equality:

$$PFD_1 = \frac{MDT_1}{MTBF_1} = w_1 \cdot MDT_1 = w_1 \cdot t'_{GE}$$

$$PFD_1 \approx 2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \left[\lambda_{DU} \left(\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right) + (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) MTTR \right] \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (3.33)$$

- Finally, in the last stage, we obtain the overall PFD for the 1oo2D architecture by adding PFD_1 and PFD_2 contributions:

$$PFD_{1oo2D} \approx 2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \cdot (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \cdot t'_{GE} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (3.34)$$

If we compare this expression with the expression given on page 59 of the IEC 61508-6 standard, we can see that they are different. We can explain this difference. First of all, let us remember the formula given in the standard:

$$PFD_G \approx 2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left[(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} + (1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD} \right] \cdot t'_{CE} \cdot t'_{GE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR$$

$$+ \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (3.35)$$

$$\text{with } t'_{CE} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.36)$$

Then we can analyse the different parts of the formula (3.35).

- As explained beforehand the common cause $\beta_D \lambda_{DD} MTTR$ contribution must be eliminated, because it is written that “if the diagnostic tests find faults (detected dangerous failures) in both channels....., then the output goes to the safe state” (IEC 61508-6).
- We can confirm that the t'_{GE} expression seems correct to us. The presence of the λ_{DD} and λ_{SD} parameters in this formula is justified, because all combinations of a detected failure, dangerous or not, of a channel with an undetected dangerous failure on the other channel leads the 1oo2D architecture into a dangerous state.

- The case presented by the presence of the t'_{CE} parameter in (3.35) is different, because it only tackles one channel at a time. In fact, the two parameters λ_{DD} and λ_{SD} should not appear in the t'_{CE} expression, because in the 1oo2D architecture neither detected dangerous failures nor detected safe failures in a given channel, considered individually can lead it to a dangerous status. t'_{CE} is therefore reduced to:

$$t'_{CE} = \frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \quad (3.37)$$

- In the end, the last residual difference between the (3.34) and (3.35) formulas lies in the term between brackets on the second, meaning $[(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} + (1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}]$.

The first criticism which can be expressed on finding it is the asymmetrical presence of parameters λ_{DD} and λ_{SD} within it. The second criticism relates to the presence of the $(1-\beta_D)$ and $(1-\beta)$ factors. Because the term between brackets considered reports all the transitions leaving the critical states from the system (meaning states 2 and 3), it must include all the failure rates as a whole, such as $\lambda_i = (1-\beta)\lambda_i + \beta\lambda_i$ and not only $(1-\beta)\lambda_i$.

As a consequence and to be precise, the $(1-\beta_D)$ and $(1-\beta)$ factors must be replaced by the unit within the general terms between brackets for the expression (3.35).

To summarise this analysis given over to determining the PFD_{1oo2D} proposed in the IEC 61508-6 document, we will say that the following corrections must be provided.

- The term $\beta_D \lambda_{DD} MTTR$ must be removed.
- The λ_{DD} and λ_{SD} failure rate must no longer appear in t'_{CE} .
- The sum $(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} + (1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}$ must be reduced to $\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}$.

3.4.2. SINTEF approach

In the booklet presenting the method designed by SINTEF (PDS Method Handbook), the 1oo2D architecture is only quoted and succinctly processed in annex E. The following formula is proposed there:

$$\begin{aligned} PFD_{1oo2D} &\approx \left[2 \lambda_{DU}^{(i)} + \lambda_{DU}^{(d)} \right] \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \\ &\approx \left[2 (1-c^{(i)})(1-\beta)\lambda_D + (1-c^{(d)})\beta\lambda_D \right] \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

Parameters $c^{(i)}$ and $c^{(d)}$ which appear there respectively represent the diagnostic coverage rate for the independent failures and the dependent failures, when the comparison of the channels is carried out during diagnosis tests. Unfortunately we are not in a position to provide numerical results from this formula, because we do not have any data relating to parameters $c^{(i)}$ and $c^{(d)}$!

3.4.3. Holistic approach

We can remind you that this approach is a holistic type approach, meaning the system type as opposed to analytical models which deal with components or sub-systems. The behavioural model for the 1oo2D architecture is shown in figure 3.15.

A small sample of the numerical results is given in table 3.4. These results were obtained, on the one hand, by consulting table B3 in the IEC 61508-6 standard and on the other hand, by using the multi-phase Markov model represented in figure 3.13. It seems that the results obtained by the two methods are close to each other whilst the contribution from common cause failures is predominant (clear parts of the table) but slightly different when this distribution decreases and the failure rate λ grows (shaded parts of the table).

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})				5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05
Approaches						
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	3.700E-4	1.100E-3	1.8E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.300E-3	4.800E-3	3.2E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	9.400E-5	2.000E-4	1.5E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.800E-4	1.800E-3	9.3E-3
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	2.200E-5	4.500E-5	2.3E-4
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.200E-4	4.400E-4	2.2E-3
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	3.700E-4	1.032E-3	1.525E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.287E-3	4.763E-3	3.027E-2
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	1.122E-4	2.729E-4	3.194E-3
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.918E-4	1.815E-3	1.025E-2
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 2\%$	2.350E-5	5.020E-5	3.773E-4
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.200E-4	4.421E-4	2.292E-3

Table 3.4: Numerical results relating to the PFD_{avg} for the 1oo2D architecture ($T_1 = 8760\text{hr}$)

3.4.4. Conclusion relating to the 1oo2D architecture

Whether they are general or specific, the conclusions issued for the 1oo2 architecture remain valid for the 1oo2D architecture (see sub-paragraph 3.3.5). However in the latter case, the analytical expression for the PFD_{avg} , as proposed in IEC 61508-6 standard, seems to be formally erroneous, *unless the interpretation for this architecture differs from ours!* If this is not the case, it must be corrected, even if its numerical impact is generally weak. However, this impact is no longer negligible when the contribution from the common cause failures becomes less preponderant.

Furthermore, to conclude this third chapter, we must remember that using standard-based formulas (for information only) is only acceptable if their conditions for application have been carefully checked beforehand. *Their main disadvantage is that they only deal with the constituent parts of a safety instrumented system, considered individually, meaning independently from each other, whilst the idea of SIL is unquestionably associated with the safety function run by this system taken as a whole.*

3.5. 1oo3 Architecture

This architecture is not treated in the current version of the IEC 61508-6 standard but it will appear in the next edition. This explains why we have included it in this report.

The 1oo3 architecture is composed of three channels connected in parallel, operating in active redundancy. This means that this system will remain operational whilst at least one of its channels is working. The physical and reliability block diagrams corresponding to this architecture are represented in figures 3.17 and 3.18 respectively.

Figure 3.17: Physical-block diagram relating to the 1oo3 architecture

Figure 3.18: Reliability block-diagram relating to the 1oo3 architecture

3.5.1. Standard approach

On the basis of the representation which will be given by the next edition of the standard (figure 3.18), we have the confirmation that the calculation of the chosen parameter (PFD_{avg}) will still be done by considering separately the individual behaviour of the three channels and their behaviour in the event of common cause failure and by simply adding these two types of contribution. This is the procedure which has already been followed by the 1oo2 and 1oo2D architectures.

In order to lighten the calculations, we will work differently from before, basing ourselves on an approached Markov model, more compact than the model we would have deduced from the multi-phase Markov model in figure 3.20. We firstly consider the individual behaviour of the three channels, and deduce from that their contribution to the overall PFD of the 1oo3 architecture making this contribution PFD_1 . We will then add it to the contribution PFD_2 due to common cause failures.

- **Calculating PFD_1**

The compact but approached Markov model, from which we are going to deduce PFD_1 is represented in figure 3.19.

Figure 3.19: Approached Markov model relating to 1oo3 architecture

Each transition relating to failures integrates individual detected and undetected dangerous failures. We therefore have:

$$\lambda_D = (1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \quad (3.39)$$

Furthermore, in compliance with the classic Markov model and taking into account the fact that the numerical value of each μ_i is clearly greater than λ_D , we can assimilate μ_1 and μ_2 to the inverse of MDT relating to the 1oo1 and 1oo2 architecture respectively, given in (3.4) and (3.12) and that we recall below:

$$\frac{1}{\mu_1} = t_{CE} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.40)$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_2} = t_{GE} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left[\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.41)$$

The step which let us evaluate t_{CE} , in paragraph 3.2.1, and t_{GE} , in paragraph 3.3.1, can be reiterated to determine μ_3 . It leads to the following expression, known as t_{G2E} in the next edition of the standard:

$$\frac{1}{\mu_3} = t_{G2E} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left[\frac{T_1}{4} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR \quad (3.42)$$

The exploitation of the model from figure 3.19 lets us determine the asymptotic unavailability of the 1oo3 architecture:

$$\bar{A}_{1oo3}(\infty) = p_4(\infty) = \frac{6 \lambda_D^3}{6 \lambda_D^3 + 6 \lambda_D^2 \mu_3 + 3 \lambda_D \mu_1 \mu_2 \mu_3 + \mu_1 \mu_2 \mu_3} \approx \frac{6 \lambda_D^3}{\mu_1 \mu_2 \mu_3} \quad (3.43)$$

We have shown in sub-paragraphs 2.1.3.2 and 2.1.3.3 that we can estimate average unavailability for a system, calculated from a multi-phase Markov model by the asymptotic unavailability of this same system, but modelled by an approached Markov graph, such as the graph in figure 3.19. We can therefore deduce that:

$$PF D_1 \approx 6 \lambda_D^3 \cdot t_{CE} \cdot t_{GE} \cdot t_{G2E} \quad (3.44)$$

- **Calculating $PF D_2$ and $PF D_{1003}$**

The reliability block diagram from figure 3.18 induces necessarily that $PF D_2$ is the same as for the 1002 architecture (see equation (3.21)). Being:

$$PF D_2 = [(\beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot (T_1/2 + MTTR))] \quad (3.45)$$

We then deduce the $PF D_{1003}$ expression which is what is proposed in the next edition of the standard 61508-6.

$$PF D_{1003} \approx 6 \left[(1 - \beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1 - \beta) \lambda_{DU} \right]^3 t_{CE} t_{GE} t_{G2E} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (3.46)$$

This expression is an approximation and differs from the expression which would have been obtained working from the continuous Markov model deduced from the multi-phase Markov model in figure 3.20. However, they each give numerical values close to those obtained by treating the multi-phase model. This proximity of results can be seen by examining table 3.5.

3.5.2. SINTEF approach

We have not looked for the formula proposed by SINTEF, because that would have required extra in-depth analysis work on their evaluation step regarding the contribution of common cause failures.

The application of this formula, recalled below, leads to the results grouped together in table 3.5 under the title SINTEF.

$$PF D_{1003} = 0,3 \left[\beta \lambda_{DD} MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left[(1 - 1,7\beta) \lambda_{DU} \cdot T_1 \right]^3 + 3(1 - 1,7\beta) \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR \cdot \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2} \quad (3.47)$$

3.5.3. Holistic approach

This approach, let us not forget, is based on exploiting holistic models of functional and dysfunctional behaviour (multi-phase Markov or Petri net) for the architecture studied or for its dysfunctioning logic (fault tree). We have retained the multi-phase Markov model to evaluate the $PF D_{1003}$. It is represented in figure 3.20. The inter-phase transition matrix is given, below, for information purposes. This makes the connection between the probabilities of occupying the states at the end (e_{i-1}) of the phase ($i-1$) and those at the beginning (b_i) of the phase i .

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_1(b_i) \\ p_2(b_i) \\ p_3(b_i) \\ p_4(b_i) \\ p_5(b_i) \\ p_6(b_i) \\ p_7(b_i) \\ p_8(b_i) \\ p_9(b_i) \\ p_{10}(b_i) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} p_1(e_{i-1}) \\ p_2(e_{i-1}) \\ p_3(e_{i-1}) \\ p_4(e_{i-1}) \\ p_5(e_{i-1}) \\ p_6(e_{i-1}) \\ p_7(e_{i-1}) \\ p_8(e_{i-1}) \\ p_9(e_{i-1}) \\ p_{10}(e_{i-1}) \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3.20: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo3 architecture

The PFD_{1oo3} values obtained, by exploiting the preceding model and for different sets of parameters are also grouped together in table 3.5.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})			5.0E-06	1.0E-05	5.0E-05	
Approaches						
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.099E-3	2.209E-3	1.290E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.195E-3	4.398E-3	2.329E-2
	60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	4.395E-4	8.799E-4	4.532E-3	
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.789E-4	1.758E-3	8.897E-3	
	90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.106E-4	2.212E-4	1.108E-3	
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.212E-4	4.424E-4	2.214E-3	
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.097E-3	2.202E-3	1.236E-2
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.189E-3	4.379E-3	2.264E-2
	60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	4.384E-4	8.773E-4	4.480E-3	
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.764E-4	1.752E-3	8.791E-3	
	90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.099E-4	2.197E-4	1.099E-3	
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.197E-4	4.393E-4	2.194E-3	
SINTEF	DC (%)	0	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	3.300E-4	6.690E-4	4.786E-3
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	6.577E-4	1.320E-2	7.325E-3
	60	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.319E-4	2.643E-4	1.415E-3	
		$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	2.636E-4	5.275E-4	2.685E-3	
	90	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	3.339E-5	6.681E-5	3.359E-4	
		$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	6.679E-5	1.336E-4	6.693E-4	

Table 3.5: PFD_{avg} relating to the 1oo3 architecture ($T_1 = 8760hr$)

3.5.4. Comparing the results and conclusion relating to the 1oo3 architecture

The values for PFD_{1oo3} given in the ad hoc tables in the next edition of the IEC 61508-6 standard are, once again, close to those obtained by treating the corresponding multi-phase Markov model, whilst being systematically slightly higher than them. On the other hand, those provided by the SINTEF model clearly deviate. As we explained earlier, we cannot judge the relevance in the absence of a prior validation of the formula they come from.

3.6. Conclusion relating to calculating the PFD_{avg}

During this chapter dedicated to calculating the average probabilities of failure on demand, we can formulate the following conclusions:

- The analytical formulas, proposed in annex B of the IEC 61508-6 standard, to calculate the PFD_{avg} for the $KooN$ architectures, are approached formulas which we can find, at the expense of several restrictive hypotheses, by exploiting continuous Markov models, derived from piecewise Markov models, known as multi-phase.
- The aforementioned hypotheses, listed during this chapter, restrict the use of these formulas in studying SIS architectures for which the channels are mutually independent (no sharing repairers, for example) and homogeneous (same failure rate, same proof-test interval, same restoration time).
- Among these hypotheses, there is an implicit hypothesis which allows us to apply the approximation of rare events to the calculation of the PFD_{avg} for an SIS. Taking this equal to the sum of the PFD_{avg} for the three sub-systems making up the SIL (sensors, logic unit, activators).

- These hypotheses also include the mutual independence of the DU and DD failure modes for a same unit and the fact that individual failures and common cause failures were processed separately.

This done and under the aforementioned hypotheses, the application of these formulas to the simple architectures presented in the standard lead to results which are very close to those obtained via holistic models, known to be rigorous. The first results are generally slightly pessimistic compared to the second results.

In chapter 4 we will see that the observation is more severe when these formulas are applied to a complete SIS, made up of several sub-systems in series and submitted to more realistic operating conditions.

Before that, it is convenient to run a similar study to what has just been presented, but for which the objective is to find the analytical formulas given in the standard for the probability of failure per hour (PFH) for $KooN$ architectures. This work is presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 4

**Analysis of the high demand or continuous mode of operation
(determining the *PFH*) and case study**

4.1. Objective of the analysis

Echoing the image which was created in the preceding chapter for the low demand case, we are proposing to show how we can find the analytical formulas given for the *PFH* in section 6 of IEC 61508 standard, by looking at their domain of validity. We are doing this, as an example, for the same SIS architectures, meaning 1oo1, 1oo2, 1oo2D and 1oo3.

In this respect, the reader will have noticed that obtaining the PFD_{avg} expression for the studied *KooN* architectures involves, for each of them, their unconditional failure intensity, or in other words their *PFH*. In other terms, the *same holistic models*, which have let us calculate the *average value of the PFD(t)* for each of the preceding architectures *also provide their average PFH*. The numerical values from the standard-based and holistic approach are then compared.

As a lead up to the calculations to follow, we can remark that they are presented very succinctly in standard 61508-6 (in a single page for the five architectures being tackled: 1oo1, 1oo2, 2oo2, 1oo2D, 2oo3), and without any real explanation. The unspoken principle is that the writers have directly deduced the expression for the *PFH* from that of the PFD_{avg} via the equation (2.62) for which we found the origin in chapter 2 and that we recall below under reference (4.1):

$$PFD_{avg} = MDT \cdot PFH \quad (4.1)$$

We can explain further that, in compliance with the standard, only dangerous failures are considered in this chapter.

As a complement to the developments which led to establishing analytical formulas for the PFD_{avg} in chapter 3 and which will conclude below for the *PFH*, we will devote the second part of this chapter 4 to studying a SIS for which the architecture is not reduced to one of the simple typical schemas presented in the standard, or even one of their possible combinations.

The aim of this study is to test the capacity of the “standard-based” analytical approach to deal with realistic cases.

4.2. 1oo1 Architecture

4.2.1. Standard approach

Let us also remember the expression for the PFD_{avg} for this architecture, which we completed in (3.5) and (3.6):

$$PFD_{avg} = \lambda_D \cdot t_{CE} \quad (4.2)$$

Knowing that (3.4) establishes that $t_{CE} = MDT$, applying (4.1) and (4.2) leads to:

$$PFH_{1oo1} = \lambda_D \quad (4.3)$$

Now, according to the standard (second page of annex B), the “E/E/PE safety-related system always goes into a safety stop after detecting a dangerous fault, for the 1oo1 and 2oo2 majority logic groups operating in high or continuous demand mode.” This returns to consider detected dangerous failures as not being actually dangerous and therefore restricting λ_D to λ_{DU} . The equality (4.3) is therefore reduced to:

$$PFH_{1oo1} = \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.4)$$

This equality is what is given in the standard.

4.2.2. Holistic approach

We are going to make the most of the simplicity of this architecture to illustrate how each of the three holistic models which we are using works to determine the average value of the *PFH* for an SIS.

4.2.2.1. Fault tree

The *PFH*(t) for a system S , meaning its *unconditional failure intensity* is obtained by applying the fault tree for the *critical working states method*. For this, for each of its components c_i , we can calculate their own unconditioning failure intensity $w_i(t)$ and their Birnbaum importance factor $I_B(S, c_i)$. They we add together their respective products [Cocozza, 1997], [Dutuit et al., 2005], making:

$$w_S(t) = \sum_i I_B(S, c_i) \cdot w_i(t) \quad (4.5)$$

In our case, this calculation applied to the fault tree represented in figure 3.5 gives:

$$w_S(t) = \sum_i \left(p(S/c_i) - p(S/\bar{c}_i) \right) \cdot \lambda_i \cdot A_i(t) \quad (4.6)$$

where $p(S/c_i)$ and $p(S/\bar{c}_i)$ are the conditional probabilities that S will fail, knowing that respectively component c_i is or is not failed, $A_i(t)$ is the instantaneous availability of this component, $\bar{A}_i(t)$ then representing its instantaneous unavailability. We therefore obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} w_S(t) &= \left(1 - \bar{A}_{DD}(t)\right) \cdot \lambda_{DU} \cdot A_{DU}(t) + \left(1 - \bar{A}_{DU}(t)\right) \cdot \lambda_{DD} \cdot A_{DD}(t) \\ &= (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}) \cdot (A_{DD}(t) \cdot A_{DU}(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

The average value of the $PFH_{1oo1}(t)$ is then calculated classically:

$$PFH_{1oo1} = w_{moy}^S = (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}) \cdot \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T (A_{DD}(t) \cdot A_{DU}(t)) dt$$

Taking into account the numerical values attributed in the standard to the different parameters λ_{DD} , λ_{DU} , T , the parameter for the integral weighted by T is close to the unit. Where:

$$PFH_{1001} \approx \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.8)$$

By restricting λ_D to λ_{DU} , we get the expression (4.4)

4.2.2.2. Markov model

The method used is, as before, the critical working states method but this time applied to a Markov model. The expression for the *PFH*(*t*) is then as follows [Pagès et al., 1980]:

$$PFH(t) = w_S(t) = \sum_{i \in M_C} \Lambda_i \cdot p_i(t) \quad (4.9)$$

where M_C is all the critical working states and Λ_i the sum of the failure rates removing the critical working state i and finishing in a failed state. We then obtain the chosen value *PFH* directly:

$$\begin{aligned} PFH &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \left(\sum_{i \in M_C} \Lambda_i \cdot p_i(t) \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i \in M_C} \left(\Lambda_i \int_0^T p_i(t) dt \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i \in M_C} \Lambda_i \cdot TSC_i [0, T] \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Being, finally:

$$PFH = \sum_{i \in M_C} \Lambda_i \cdot PMS_i \quad (4.11)$$

where $TSC_i [0, T]$ and PMS_i respectively represent the cumulated sojourn time in the critical working state i , for an observation duration T , and the average probability of staying in this state.

Within the framework of the holistic approach, this method for determining *PFH* can however be obtained by applying the “continuous” Markov model. Let us look at it considering the model in figure 3.3. In this case, we clearly have $\Lambda_i = \lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD}$ whilst PMS_1 is estimated by the asymptotic value $p_1(\infty)$. Where:

$$\begin{aligned} PFH &= (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD}) \cdot \frac{MUT}{MTBF} \\ &\approx \lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

As before, if we neglect the contribution of the detected dangerous failures, then we find the formula $PFH_{moy} \approx \lambda_{DU}$ (4.13)

4.2.2.3. Petri net model

The Petri net relating to the 1001 architecture and the net modelling alternating periodic tests are represented in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Petri net relating to the 1001 architecture

By running a large number of behaviour simulations for this architecture over a given period T , we get the average number of launches N_{DD} and N_{DU} for the two parameter set transitions λ_{DD} and λ_{DU} . The average *PFH* value is deduced from it immediately, in compliance with the equality (4.14):

$$PFH_{1001} \approx \frac{N_{DD} + N_{DU}}{T} \quad (4.14)$$

4.2.3. Comparing the results and conclusion

We have calculated the average value of the *PFH* for the 1001 architecture using the three holistic models described previously and we have compared the results that they provide with each other and with those that the standard would have given if the term λ_{DD} had been kept in the *PFH* expression (see equation (4.3)). A succinct sample of these results is presented in table 4.1.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})			5.0E-06
Approaches			
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	2.5 E-6
		60	
		90	
Fault tree	DC (%)	0	2.47E-6
		60	2.49E-6
		90	2.50E-6
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	2.47E-6
		60	2.49E-6
		90	2.50E-6
Petri net	DC (%)	0	2.48E-6
		60	2.48E-6
		90	2.50E-6

Table 4.1: *PFH* relating to the 1001 architecture ($T = 8760\text{hr}$)

These numerical values for the *PFH* were obtained in the following conditions:

- For the fault tree, the interval over which this PFH_{1001} was calculated is the interval $[4T ; 5T]$. The system behaviour is stationary there.
- For the Markov and Petri net models, the *PFH* was calculated over the interval $[0 ; 10 T]$.
- 10^6 simulations were carried out over the Petri net model.

A brief examination of table 4.1 shows us:

- Very good agreement between the results obtained from the three holistic models, which are increasingly closer to the values from the formula (4.3) derived from the standard.
- *That the latter are not systematically conservative.*

4.3. 1002 Architecture

4.3.1. Standard approach

The 1002 architecture and its operation are described in sub-paragraph 3.3.1. To find the analytical formula for PFH_{1002} proposed in the standard, we can follow a classic approach similar to the one which gave us the expression for PFH_{1001} in chapter 3 (see equation (3.22)).

- We still work from the approached Markov model from figure 3.9 which we complete by giving it parameter set transitions $\beta_D \lambda_{DD}$ and $\beta \lambda_{DU}$ between state 1 and the failed states 4 and 6.
- We apply the formula (4.11). This gives:

$$PFH_{1002} = (\beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU}) \cdot p_{1,moy} + (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}) \cdot (p_{2,moy} + p_{3,moy}) \quad (4.15)$$

Now, we have shown in chapter 2 and 3 that we can, under certain conditions, assimilate the average values for the probabilities to their asymptotic values. The equality (4.15) can then be written:

$$PFH_{1002} \approx (\beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU}) \cdot p_1(\infty) + (\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}) \cdot (p_2(\infty) + p_3(\infty)) \quad (4.16)$$

- By explaining the values of the preceding probabilities in compliance with the expressions obtained in (3.10), under the hypothesis that $p_1(\infty)$ is close to the unit, we end up with:

$$\begin{aligned} PFH_{1002} &\approx \lambda_D \cdot \left[\frac{2(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}}{\mu_{DD}} + \frac{2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} \right] + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \\ &= 2 \lambda_D^2 \cdot \left[\frac{(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \frac{1}{\mu_{DD}} + \frac{(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \frac{1}{\mu_{DU}} \right] + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \end{aligned}$$

So:

$$PFH_{1oo2} = 2\lambda_D^2 \cdot \left[\frac{(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR + \frac{(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \right] + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.17)$$

The term between square brackets is very close to what is called t_{CE} in the standard. Furthermore, the first term of the right side of the equality (4.17) taking into consideration the contribution of the *PFH* for independent failures, we can thereby explain λ_D : $\lambda_D = (1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta)\lambda_{DU}$.

We finally end up with the following expression which is given in standard CEI 61508-6 in section B.3.2.2:

$$PFH_{1oo2} \approx 2 \left[(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \right]^2 t_{CE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.18)$$

4.3.2. Holistic approach

In order to lighten the proposal, only the Petri net and multi-phase Markov models were applied to the 1oo2 architecture. The Petri net model appears in figure 3.11, whilst the Markov graph is represented in figure 3.8.

The results obtained like this are compared in the following paragraph with the results provided by the analytical formula (4.18) proposed in the standard.

4.3.3. Comparing the results and conclusion

The conditions for obtaining average values for PFH_{1oo2} , grouped together in table 4.2 are as follows:

- Period between tests $T_1 = 8760$ hr (1 year). The values for other interesting parameters are given in the table.
- The PFH_{1oo2} values relating to the standard come directly from its table B.13.
- These coming from the treatment of the multi-phase Markov graph correspond to the averages calculated over a stable period of one year.
- The estimations for the PFH_{1oo2} given by the Petri net model required a million histories.

We can, once again, see the good general agreement between the results provided by the different approaches. We can also see the same phenomenon already observed in the case of the 1oo1 architecture, meaning that the average values given in the standard are not systematically conservative.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})				5.0E-06
Approaches				
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	2.9E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	5.4E-7
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.9E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	3.7E-7
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.4E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.8E-7
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	2.93E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	5.33E-7
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.93E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	3.65E-7
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.42E-7
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.79E-7
Petri net	DC (%)	0	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	2.97E-7
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	5.37E-7
		60	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.91E-7
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	3.66E-7
		90	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.46E-7
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	2.81E-7

Table 4.2: Results relating to PFH_{1002}

4.4. 1002D Architecture

The 1002D architecture and its operation were described in sub-paragraph 3.4.1.

4.4.1. Standard-based approach

The approach which finally gave us an analytical formula close to the one in the standard is what we followed previously for the 1001 and 1002 architectures.

- The departure point is the continuous Markov graph in figure 3.16, which is completed by the transition $\beta \lambda_{DU}$ between states 1 and 4.
- By applying formula (4.11) to it we obtain:

$$PFH_{1002D} = \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot p_{1,moy} + (2 \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}) \cdot p_{2,moy} + \lambda_{DU} \cdot p_{3,moy} \quad (4.19)$$

So, by assimilating the average values of the probabilities at their asymptotic values and by distinguishing λ_{DD} from λ_{SD} :

$$PFH_{1002D} = \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot p_1(\infty) + (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \cdot p_2(\infty) + \lambda_{DU} \cdot p_3(\infty) \quad (4.20)$$

- By explaining the values of $p_i(\infty)$ in compliance with the expressions obtained in (3.26) and taking into account the fact that $p_2(\infty) \gg p_3(\infty)$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} PFH_{1002D} &\approx (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \cdot p_2(\infty) + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot p_1(\infty) \\ &= (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \frac{2(1-\beta) \lambda_{DU}}{\mu_{DU}} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \end{aligned}$$

So:

$$PFH_{1002D} = 2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \cdot (\lambda_{DU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD}) \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.21)$$

This formula differs a little from the formula proposed in section B.3.2.4 of the standard, which we can recall below.

$$PFH_{1002D} = 2(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \cdot \left((1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} + (1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{SD} \right) t'_{CE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.22)$$

with t'_{CE} given by the equation (3.36).

These differences which also appear in the case of the PFH_{1002D} have been analysed at the end of paragraph 3.4.1. We will let the reader turn back but we think that one possible origin of these deviations lie in the two different interpretations of the structure and operation of the 1002D architecture.

4.4.2. Holistic approach

As for the preceding case, only the multi-phase Markov and Petri net models were applied to the 1002D architecture. The Markov model appears in figure 3.15 whilst the Petri net model is represented below, in figure 4.2.

4.4.3. Comparing the results and conclusion relating to the 1002D architecture

A small sample of results is given in table 4.3. The values resulting from the standard also reappear in its table B.13. Once again we can see good agreement between the results provided by the Petri net and multi-phase Markov models. However, they differ significantly from the first quoted, doubtlessly because of the reasons already mentioned regarding the PFH_{1002D} .

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})			5.0E-05	
Approaches				
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	6.9E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.5E-6
	60		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	2.5E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	4.1E-6
	90		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.4E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.8E-6
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	6.05E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	7.72E-6
	60		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	3.82E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	4.44E-6
	90		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.16E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	1.31E-6
Petri net	DC (%)	0	$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	6.05E-6
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	7.70E-6
	60		$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	3.83E-6
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	4.45E-6
	90		$\beta = \beta_D = 10\%$	1.16E-6
			$\beta = \beta_D = 20\%$	1.31E-6

Table 4.3: Results relating to the PFH_{1002D}

Figure 4.2: Petri net relating to the 1oo2D architecture

4.5. 1oo3 Architecture

The 1oo3 architecture and its operation are described in paragraph 3.5.

4.5.1. Standard approach

In order to find the analytical expression for the PFH_{1oo3} given in the standard, we work as for the other architectures we have already examined.

- Firstly, we only consider that the contributions from the independent failures of the three channels to determine the part of the PFH which can be attributed to them. Calling this part PFH_1 .

This can be easily calculated from the diagram in figure 3.19:

$$PFH_1 = w_{avg} \approx p_3(\infty) \cdot \lambda_D = \frac{6 \lambda_D^2}{\mu_1 \mu_2} \cdot \lambda_D = \frac{6 \lambda_D^3}{\mu_1 \mu_2} \quad (4.23)$$

With, let us remember (see paragraph 3.5.1):

$$\frac{1}{\mu_1} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left[\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR = t_{CE} \quad (4.24)$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_2} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \left[\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right] + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR = t_{GE} \quad (4.25)$$

- Secondly, we can determine the PFH_2 contribution in the same way by returning to the common cause failures, using the approached Markov model in figure 4.3:

Figure 4.3: Markov model relating to the CCF for the 1oo3 architecture

$$PFH_2 = p_1(\infty) \cdot (\beta \lambda_{DU} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD}) \quad (4.26)$$

Taking into account the permanence of the hypotheses which condition the standard-based approach, we consider that $p_1(\infty) \approx 1$. Where:

$$PFH_2 \approx \beta \lambda_{DU} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} \quad (4.27)$$

We can deduce the literal expression of the complete PFH for the 1oo3 architecture, which is what is given in the next version of the IEC 61508-6 standard:

$$PFH_{1003} \approx 6 \left[(1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \right]^3 t_{CE} t_{GE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.28)$$

4.5.2. Holistic approach

The multi-phase Markov model relating to the 1003 architecture appears in figure 3.20. Its treatment has led to a sample of results which are compared, in the next paragraph, to those presented in table B of the future IEC 61508 standard.

4.5.3. Comparing the results and conclusion relating to the 1003 architecture

The numerical values for the *PFH* resulting from the analytical formula proposed in the future edition of the IEC 61508-6 standard for the 1003 architecture are close to those obtained via a holistic model, as shown in table 4.4. The first are, this time, slightly higher than the second and therefore conservative.

Failure rate λ (h^{-1})				5.0E-05
Approaches				
IEC 61508 standard	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	3.4E-06
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	5.6E-06
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.9E-06
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	3.6E-06
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.4E-06
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.8E-06
Markov multi-phase	DC (%)	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	3.113E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	5.347E-6
		60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.870E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	3.564E-6
		90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.383E-6
			$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.751E-6

Table 4.4: Results relating to the PFH_{1003}

4.6. Conclusion relating to calculating the *PFH*

The analytical formulas proposed in annex B of the IEC 61508-6 standard to calculate the *PFH* for $KooN$ architectures are, like those relating to PFD_{avg} , approached formulas. We can find each of them by exploiting the same continuous Markov models, derived from multi-phase models.

The subjacent hypotheses for this double determination are, of course, those which were mentioned in chapter 3 regarding PFD_{avg} . Within the framework of these hypotheses, we have seen that the application of analytical formulas giving the *PFH* for a system gives numerical results close to those obtained via holistic models. *However, we will note that, as opposed to the case of the PFD_{avg} , the first are not systematically higher than the second.*

Finally, there is the question of knowing if this analytical approach can go beyond the hypotheses framing it. In order to look further at this point and draw conclusions on its ability

to deal with realistic cases, we will apply it to the case study described below in the second part of this chapter.

4.7. Comparative study of a SIS

4.7.1. Description of the case study

A simple protection system against over-pressure (HIPPS pour High Integrity Pressure Protection System) was chosen as a reference example to compare the respective aptitudes for the analytical formulas proposed in the IEC 61508-6 and the holistic models, which we use regularly, to calculate the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and the PFH correctly for a SIS. This system is represented in figure 4.4. It has already been the subject of an article [Dutuit et al., 2008].

Figure 4.4: A simple HIPPS architecture

This system is therefore a simple, yet typical, example of HIPPS intended to protect downstream part of a production system against an overpressure due to its upstream part. We will describe it succinctly below.

When the pressure in the downstream part exceeds the given threshold level, this overrunning is detected by the three PSH_i sensors, which send an information signal to the LS logic sub-system (Logic Solver) with majority redundancy 2oo3. In turn, this a signal to solenoid valves SV1 and SV2 which release the hydraulic pressure which kept shutdown valves SDV1 and SDV2 open. These are therefore closed, which has the effect of lowering the pressure in the downstream part of the installation.

This HIPPS is classically made up of three sub-systems arranged in series. The first of them is the module composed of the three PSH_i transmitter-sensors. Their undetected dangerous failures are only detected during control tests run every month (730 hours). Each of the three sensors has an estimated failure rate of $4.4e-7 \text{ hr}^{-1}$. During these tests, the sensors are unavailable.

The second sub-system is the logic unit in 2 out of 3. Its detected failure rate and its repair rate are respectively worth $5e-6 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ and 0.125 hr^{-1} .

The third sub-system is equipped with an architecture in 1 out of 2 (1oo2). Each of these two channels are composed of a solenoid valve SV_i and a safety shutdown valve SDV_i. The undetected dangerous failure rate for the first is worth $8.8e-7 \text{ hr}^{-1}$. They are tested for the first time one month after putting them into operation, then every two months (1460 hours). They are unavailable for the duration of the tests (1 hour). The SDV_i valves present two failure modes. Their failures causing the blockage in position (failure to move) are detected by “partial stroking tests.” The corresponding failure rate is equal to $2.66e-6 \text{ hr}^{-1}$. The first test is carried out, for SDV₁, one month after putting it into service and two months for SDV₂. Then, the two valves are controlled every two months. We can note that production is stopped after detecting this kind of failure. The closure failures for these valves are only detected during “full stroking tests”. The failure rate relating to this second failure mode is worth $8.9e-7 \text{ hr}^{-1}$. The first of these tests takes place respectively three months after putting the SDV₁ into operation and six months for SDV₂. Then the interval between tests is the same for these two valves and equal to six months. As previously, production is stopped as soon as this second type of failure is detected. In other words, the risk no longer exists during the following repairs. We can therefore consider them as masked.

All the reliability data and characteristics which have just been evoked are grouped together in tables 4.5 and 4.6.

Parameters	Failure mode	$\lambda_{DD} (\text{h}^{-1})$	$\lambda_{DU} (\text{h}^{-1})$	DC	Interval between tests (h)	Time of first test (hr)	β (CCF) %
Components							
PSH1	Fails to send a signal	0	$4.4e-7$	0	730	730	5
PSH2	Fails to send a signal	0	$4.4e-7$	0	730	730	
PSH3	Fails to send a signal	0	$4.4e-7$	0	730	730	
SDV1	Failure to move	0	$2.66e-6$	0	1460	730	10
SDV2	Failure to move	0	$2.66e-6$	0	1460	1460	
SDV1	Failure to fully close	0	$8.9e-7$	0	4380	2190	10
SDV2	Failure to fully close	0	$8.9e-7$	0	4380	4380	
SV1	Failure to move	0	$8.8e-7$	0	1460	730	10
SV2	Failure to move	0	$8.8e-7$	0	1460	1460	
Logic solver	Failure to act	$5.0e-6$					

Table 4.5: Reliability parameters for HIPPS components

Parameters	Repair time (hours)	Test time (hours)	Availability of components during tests
Components			
PSHs	8	1	no
SDVs	8	0	yes
SVs	1	1	no
Logic Solver	8	----	----

Table 4.6: Other reliability characteristics for HIPPS components

4.7.2. Application of analytical formulas

4.7.2.1. Calculating the PFD_{avg}

We recently submitted a similar case to the above to one of the members of the MT3 work group emanating from the commission in charge of the IEC 61508 standard. We therefore return to the procedure that they chose to apply to this case. We thereby obtain the reliability block diagram represented in figure 4.5 and all the results from table 4.7.

Figure 4.5: HIPPS reliability block-diagram

CCF contribution		5,00%			10,00%
Configuration	2oo3		1oo1	1oo2	
LDD	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	5.00E-06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
IDD for branch	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	5.00E-06	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
MDT/element	9	9	8	8	
Equivalent MDT	9	9	8	7	7
Configuration PFD	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	4.00E-05	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
IDU	4.40E-07	2.20E-08	0.00E+00	8.90E-07	4.43E-07
LDU for branch	4.40E-07	2.20E-08	0.00E+00	4.43E-06	4.43E-07
Proof test period, T/element	730	730	0	4380	
Equivalent proof test period	730	730	0	2047	2047
Configuration PFD	1.03E-07	8.03E-06	0.00E+00	2.74E-05	4.53E-04
PFD (revealed)	4.00E-05				
PFD (unrevealed)	4.88E-04				
PFD	5.28E-04				
Allowed SIL (PFD)	3				

Table 4.7: Results obtained by applying formulas from the standard

We can now comment on these results by mentioning, case by case, all the hypotheses required to implement the analytical formulas:

- The standard-based approach leads all users to consider each of the sub-systems making up the SIS studied separately and to add their respective contributions to obtain the overall PFD_{avg} . This first approximation, which highlights the hypothesis of rare events, is often acceptable but this is not the case for the Markov hypothesis of sharing the activity of a single repair operator. The persistence of this limitation must be verified, if repair durations are considered as constant.
- Calculating the PFD_{avg} for the sensors' sub-system is carried out by ignoring the β factor in front of the unit, and the average repair duration in front of $T_1/2$ or $T_1/3$, which is generally acceptable, but also by not taking into account the unavailability of the sensors during their tests, which is more worrying. *This omission reveals an important gap in the analytical approach which will lead, as we will see, to getting a value for the PFD_{avg} which is not only wrong but particularly not conservative, meaning optimistic, which can be dangerous.*

Finally, the application of formulas leads to the following result for the PFD_{avg} of the sensors' sub-system: $PFD_{PSH} = 8.13E-6$. This value includes contributions from individual failures and common cause failures.

- The calculation for the logical unit PFD_{avg} is correct. We obtain: $PFD_{LS} = 4E-5$.
- The case of the sub-system comprising activators, solenoid valves and safety shutdown valves is more interesting. It actually illustrates *the difficulty if not the inability of the analytical approach to process systems' configurations which differ from "standard" architectures presented and analysed in the standard* as independent entities and submitted to simplified operation conditions. To be able to approximately model the real behaviour of the activators' sub-system in compliance with the standard's philosophy, the procedure described below has been proposed, but it does not appear in IEC 61508-6.
 - Each branch of this 1oo2 architecture sub-system is considered as a unique macro-component, for which the dangerous failure rate is taken as equal to the sum of the rates corresponding to the components making it up and for which the interval between tests is the weighted mean of the intervals between individual tests:

$$T_{branche} = \frac{\lambda_{SV} \cdot T_{SV} + \lambda_{SDV/FM} \cdot T_{SDV/FM} + \lambda_{SDV/FC} \cdot T_{SDV/FC}}{\lambda_{SV} + \lambda_{SDV/FM} + \lambda_{SDV/FC}} \quad (4.29)$$

where FM and FC return respectively to "fail to move" and "fail to close".

- The formula proposed in the standard for the 1oo2 architecture is then applied and gives: $PFD_{valves} = 4.80E-4$.

We can deduce the overall PFD_{avg} for the SIS (HIPPS) by adding together the PFD_{avg} for its three constituent parts. So:

$$PFD_{SIS} = 8.13 E-6 + 4E-5 + 4.80E-4 = 5.28 E-4 \quad (\text{SIL3}) \quad (4.30)$$

4.7.2.2. Calculating the *PFH*

This step is identical to what was followed previously to calculate the PFH_{avg} . This requires calculating the *PFH* for each of the three sub-systems making up the HIPPS and adding these three contributions together to obtain the system's overall *PFH*. So:

$$PFH_{SIS} = PFH_{PSH} + PFH_{LS} + PFH_V \quad (4.31)$$

where PSH, LS and V indicate the sub-system for the sensors, the logic unit and the activators (valves) respectively.

- **Calculating PFH_{PSH}**

This sub-system is the 2oo3 type. Applying the formula given in section B.3.2.5 of the standard, recalled below, gives, depending on the numerical data grouped together in tables 4.5 and 4.6, the value displayed in (4.33).

$$PFH_{2oo3} \approx 6 \left[(1-\beta_D)\lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \right]^2 t_{CE} + \beta_D \lambda_{DD} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \quad (4.32)$$

So:

$$PFH_{PSH} \approx \beta \lambda_{DU} = 2,2 E-8 \quad (4.33)$$

- **Calculating PFH_{LS}**

We obtain directly:

$$PFH_{LS} \approx \lambda_{DD} = 5 E-6$$

- **Calculating PFH_V**

As we indicated at the end of paragraph 4.3, the case of this sub-system is particular. Its architecture is 1oo2 type, but we can only apply the formula corresponding to the standard after having assimilated each of its two branches to a unique macro-component for which we will have determined the reliability parameters beforehand. For them we find the following values (see paragraph 4.7.2.1) for the dangerous failure rate and the interval between tests:

$$\lambda_{DU} = 2.66 E-6 + 8.9 E-7 + 8.8 E-7 = 4.43 E-6$$

$$T = 2047 \text{ hr}$$

By applying the analytical formulas from the 1oo2 architecture, we obtain:

$$PFH_V \approx 2 \left[(1-\beta)\lambda_{DU} \right]^2 \frac{T}{2} + \beta \lambda_{DU} \approx 4,43 E-7 \quad (4.34)$$

Where the overall *PFH* for HIPPS, according to (4.31):

$$PFH_{SIS} \approx 5.465 E-6 \quad (4.35)$$

4.7.3. Applying holistic models

As opposed to the standard-based approach described previously, which is based on the combination of typical architectures (called LEGO approach by some authors), we recommend modelling the behaviour of the SIS studied, taken as a whole, and direct exploitation of this model [Signoret, 2005a]. This double task is done using holistic models.

In this case we are dealing with, two models have been successively applied to the SIS presented in paragraph 4.7.1 to simultaneously calculate its PFH_{avg} and its PFH : the fault tree and the Petri nets.

4.7.3.1. Fault tree model

The fault tree relating to the SIS studied appears in figure 4.6. Although it is very simple the different types of failures for components are clearly represented there, including their individual failures and the common cause failures.

Figure 4.6: Fault tree relating to the HIPPS of interest.

Figure 4.7 shows the curve over time for instantaneous unavailability of the HIPPSS over a limited observation duration, but sufficient to demonstrate its periodic character. We can explain that this curve should have been truncated in terms of amplitude, because its maximums have reached the unit.

Figure 4.7: Time evolution of instantaneous HIPPS unavailability

We can also see that this type of curve is not the usual fault tree processing software on the market, because this kind of possibility first of all requires “implementing” a model drawn up from the behaviour of the periodically tested components and then, choosing a temporal sample of the curve to obtain a specific value for the PFD_{avg} . The ARALIA software has this capacity.

- **Calculating the PFD_{avg} and other indicators**

The calculations run using this software over an observation time of 20,000 hours have given an average value for the overall PFH for the HIPPS equal to $1.639e-3$. According to the standard, this corresponds to a SIL2. At first glance, this result might seem surprising, if we remember the distribution under $PFH(t)$ curve for the different SIL zones. On examining figure 4.7, we can actually see that the HIPPS spends most of its time in SIL3 zone because, to be more exact, the variations of its PFH remain more often than not within the $[1e-4, 5e-4]$ interval. This observation is confirmed by the contents of table 4.8. Results concerning the average value of the PFH obtained, which corresponds to a SIL2 and its domain of variation which is almost completely included in the SIL3 zone, are not actually contradictory. This apparent incoherence is explained if we remember the maximum value, equal to the unit, regularly attained by the unavailability of some components in the system, during their periodic tests. Their impact on the PFH_{avg} for the HIPPS is decisive, despite the brevity of the duration of these tests (one hour).

SIL	Cumulated sojourn times in the different SIL zones (%)
SIL0	$1.36e-1$
SIL1	$1.22e-4$
SIL2	$1.22e-5$
SIL3	94.4
SIL4	5.48

Table 4.8: Distribution of cumulated sojourn times in the different SIL zones.

- **Calculating the PFH**

This calculation is done on the basis of the formula (4.5) giving the following result:

$$PFH_{SIS} = 5.487 \text{ E-6.} \quad (4.36)$$

We will now look at the Petri net model before comparing and commenting on all the results in paragraph 4.7.4.

4.7.3.2. Petri net model

- **Calculating the PFD_{avg}**

To confirm the results obtained beforehand, via a fault tree, a Petri net model was built (see figures 4.8 to 4.15 and table 4.9) and exploited. One million iterations were made during the Monte Carlo simulation implemented to simulate the behaviour of the HIPPS over a period of 20000 hours. The statistics exploitation of this important sample led to the following estimation: $PFD_{avg} = 1.636E-3 \pm 5.4E-6$. This value corresponds well to a SIL2 and is very close to the result obtained previously via the fault tree.

- **Calculating the PFH**

The estimation of the average frequency of the statistical event occurring which represents the unavailability of the HIPPS called HIPS_PFD (in table 4.9) provides the value of the SIS's PFH: 5.471E-6. Taking into account the availability of the sensors and solenoid valves (SV) during their respective tests, the variable values PSHs_PFD and SDVs_Svs_PFD have been replaced by:

- $PSHs_PFD = ite(@2)((\#1==0),(\#4==0),(\#7==0),1.0,0.0)$.
- $SDVs_Svs_PFD = ite(@2)((\#26==0|\#212==0),(\#54==0|\#261==0),1.0,0.0)$.

where 'ite' is the abbreviation of "if then else". So ite (e1, e2, e3) is worth e2 if the Boolean expression e1 is true and e3 if not. e2 and e3 are two expressions of the same type (Boolean, whole, real). @(*K*)(e1, ... ,e*N*) is true if at least *K* expressions out of *N* are true.

Figure 4.8: Petri net relating to the PSH1 sensor

Figure 4.9: Petri net relating to the CCF for PSHi sensors

Figure 4.10: Petri net relating to proof-tests on the PSH1 sensor

Figure 4.11: Petri net relating to the LS logic unit

Figure 4.12: Petri net describing the behaviour of the SDV1 valve

Figure 4.13: Petri net relating to the proof-tests (FM) on the SDV1 valve

Figure 4.14: Petri net relating to the CCF for the SDV1 valve

Figure 4.15: Petri net relating to the proof-tests (FC) on the SDV1 valve

Scope	No	Definition / Initial value
Real	BETA_PSH	0.05
Real	BETA_SDV	0.1
Real	BETA_SV	0.1
Integer	I, J, K, L, M, N, O, P, Q	0
Real	LAMBDA_PSH_DU	4.40E-07
Real	LAMBDA_SDV_FC_DU	8.90E-07
Real	LAMBDA_SDV_FM_DU	2.66E-06
Real	LAMBDA_SV_DU	8.80E-07
Real	LLS_DD	5.00E-06
Real	LPSH_CCF	(LAMBDA_PSH_DU)*BETA_PSH
Real	LPSH_DU_IN	(LAMBDA_PSH_DU)*(1.0-BETA_PSH)
Real	LSDV_CCF_FC	LAMBDA_SDV_FC_DU*BETA_SDV
Real	LSDV_CCF_FM	LAMBDA_SDV_FM_DU*BETA_SDV
Real	LSDV_FC_DU_IN	LAMBDA_SDV_FC_DU*(1.-BETA_SDV)
Real	LSDV_FM_DU_IN	LAMBDA_SDV_FM_DU*(1.-BETA_SDV)
Real	LSV_CCF	LAMBDA_SV_DU*BETA_SV
Real	LSV_DU_IN	LAMBDA_SV_DU*(1.-BETA_SV)
Real	REP_LS	0.125
Real	REP_PSH	0.125
Real	REP_SDV	0.125
Real	REP_SV	1
Boolean	PSHi_KO (i=1,2,3)	false
Boolean	SDVi_FC_KO (i=1,2)	false
Boolean	SDVi_FM_KO (i=1,2)	false
Boolean	SVi_KO (i=1,2)	false
Boolean	LS_KO	false
Boolean	CCF_PSH_DU	false
Boolean	CCF_SV_DU	false
Boolean	FC_CCF_SDV	false
Boolean	FM_CCF_SDV	false
Boolean	TEST_PSHi (i=1,2,3)	false
Boolean	TEST_SDVi_FC (i=1,2)	false
Boolean	TEST_SDVi_FM (i=1,2)	false
Boolean	TEST_SVi (i=1,2)	false
Real	PSHs_PFD	ite(@ (2)((#1==0 #13==0),(#4==0 #39==0),(#7==0 #41==0)),1.0,0.0)
Real	LS_PFD	ite(#46==0,1.0,0.0)

Real	SDVs_SVs_PFD	ite(@2)((#26==0 #212==0 #313==0),(#54==0 #261==0 #345==0)),1.0,0.0)
Real	HIPS_PFD	ite(@1)(PSHs_PFD==1.,LS_PFD==1.,SDVs_SVs_PFD==1.),1.,0.)

Table 4.9: Variables used in the Petri net model

4.7.4. Synthesis of the results obtained and conclusion regarding the test case

Approaches	Analytical formulas	Fault tree	Petri net
<i>PFD_{avg}</i>	5.280E-4	1.639E-3	1.636E-3
<i>PFH</i>	5.465E-6	5.487E-6	5.471E-6

Table 4.10: Synthesis of the main numerical results

A quick examination of the contents of this table leads us to formulate several comments.

- This examination clearly shows that the *results from the application of analytical formulas are no longer conservative compared to the formulas obtained via the fault tree and Petri net models*, and are even optimistic” This effect is more sensitive for the *PFD_{avg}* than for the *PFH*. This observation is logical. It is explained by the fact that the unavailability of the components during their periodic tests is not taken into account in the analytical model because the duration of the tests for a given component is integrated in its *MDT*. Now, in our case, the simultaneous tests on the three sensors make the module to detect over-pressures unavailable and therefore “blind.” This has a negative impact on the overall unavailability of the SIS and therefore on its *PFD_{avg}*. This configuration is only acceptable for the low demand operating mode, taking into account the short duration of the tests (1 hour), but it is obviously not for the continuous operating mode. In the latter case, specific arrangements, such as staggering tests or even a brief controlled stop in production, manage to prevent a dangerous process from starting. We have taken this into account in our two modifications by making the sensors available in continuous operating mode. This explains why their unavailability has not had an impact on determining the *PFH*.
- To be more exact, we can note that the *numerical value of the PFD_{avg} obtained from the fault tree and Petri net models is 3 times greater than that given by the analytical formula* from the standard. This is a subject for questioning the “universal” relevance of the standard-based approach.
- The limited character of this approach is also illustrated by *its inability to model staggering for tests and certain “non standard” architectures such as the architecture for the valve sub-system*. Furthermore we have already highlighted this.

To conclude we might remember that the study, which we have just reported, concerns a simple example which cannot however be reduced to putting in series some of the typical architectures treated in volume 6 of the IEC 61508 standard. The main conclusion which we can draw is that the *application of analytical formulas proposed in this document can lead to non conservative results*. This is worrying.

It would be most sensible to reserve their usage to the study of SIS for which the three constituent sub-systems (sensors, logic unit, actuators) present *the aforementioned typical architectures and are mutually independent*. Any *extrapolated use* should previously involve a careful verification of their *validity* or a *demonstration* proving their conservative character.

This recommendation is corroborated by other declarations from different authors all in the same direction. So Julia Bukowski write: “Thus it is easy to incorrectly apply a simplified equation to a situation that does not fulfil the assumptions required for validity ” [Bukowski, 2005]. In the same way Jouko Järvi declared that “without explanation the users use the formulae without a full understanding of their meaning and limitations” [Järvi, 2007].

These reminders allow us to introduce the first subject dealt with in the next chapter. In fact, these warnings went out to several authors, of which some had contributed to the content of annex B of IEC 61508-6 and who had published controversial articles tending to prove that the Markov approach is incapable of correctly modelling the behaviour of repairable systems and particularly SIS and therefore of evaluating correctly the associated SIL [Gulland, 2002] [Simpson, 2002] [Baker, 2007].

We therefore propose to present what we think to be the approach followed by the aforementioned authors, which has let them, on the one hand, end up with the analytical models presented in the standard and, on the other hand to disprove the validity of the Markov models, which is wrong in our opinion.

We will then present our latest contributions to the critical analysis of the IEC 61508 standard.

Chapter 5

Four other subjects of interest for discussion (alternative approach, architectural constraints, spurious trip failures, PFD_{avg} and risk reduction factor)

5.1. Organisation of the chapter

This chapter groups together our reflections and the developments that they have given rise to on four points relating to the standard, but which have not been presented to a larger audience until now; at least to the best of our knowledge.

First of all we will present the approach which, in our opinion, was responsible for analytical formulas appearing in annex B of the IEC 61508-6 standard.

Followed by an observation relating to taking into account the architectural constraints recommended by the standard and relating to the use which follows from the safety failure fraction (*SFF*).

Then, finally, this last chapter examines the possible impact that SIS channel safe failures might have on its $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and its PFH , as well as the possible impact of spurious trip failures on the frequency of the undesired event for which the SIS should warn of the occurrence. Finally, we wanted to draw attention to the particular relationship which exists between the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ for a set of protection layers and the risk reduction factor that it procures.

5.2. Another way of obtaining analytical formulas from the standard

5.2.1. Problem

On the first page of annex B of the current IEC 61508-6 standard, the hypothesis is clearly formulated stating that the component failure rates are constant, whilst the nature of the law governing the repair durations is not explained. It only mentions an average re-establishment time. This time includes the time required to detect the failure in question, as well as the time required for its repair. It therefore corresponds, more or less, to the average duration of non operation after failure, known as *MDT*.

The problem is that this average time can be considered as the mathematical expectation that a random variable continues obeying, for example, an exponential law, or as constant value data.

The choice met by anyone who has to model the behaviour of a SIS is as follows:

- Either they choose the constant repair rate option, regardless of the support-model used (reliability diagram, fault tree, Markov graph, Petri nets...)
- Or they choose the constant repair duration option. But then, this person can no longer rely on either a combinatory model or a Markov model. They just have one analytical approach left to propose an explicit formulation for the $PF_{D_{avg}}$.

The first option was chosen in the vast majority of writings on modelling SIS. To the best of our knowledge, only the SGB (Simpson-Gulland-Baker) group worked with the second option.

Regardless of the chosen option, another important point is the number of repairmen to take into consideration. There are also two practices involved in this point.

- The first was chosen by the majority of authors opting for the constant repair rate option, namely considering that there are always enough repairmen available. This is

also the side taken in the current version of the standard: “several repair teams are available to work on all known failures.”

- The second practice is used by the SGB group who also announce that the number of repairmen available has no impact on the MDT for the $KooN$ architectures in question, nor on their PFD_{avg} . In this respect, we can see that this group has lasting influence on the writing team for IEC 61508 standard, because the next edition of this standard no longer mentions the clause for the ever-sufficient number of repairmen! This will lead to new problems!

So we firstly propose to explain what we think to be the approach which has allowed this group to end up with the analytical expressions for the PFD_{avg} and PFH proposed in the standard. Secondly, we will discuss the validity of disproving the Markov approach which came about as a result.

Taking into account what the SGB group is announcing, we can deduce that they also consider that the constitutive components of a $KooN$ architecture are independent.

5.2.2. Presentation of the approach

5.2.2.1. Statement and experimental verification of the basic assumptions

We will now review the two hypotheses on which the developments we are attributing to SGB group are based:

- The failure rate and the repair duration are constant for each component.
- The number of repairmen to consider is not important and has no influence on the desired results (MDT , PFD_{avg} , PFH).

As the mutual independence of the components within the $KooN$ architectures has already been admitted as far as their failures are concerned, we have to verify that it is also effective for their repairs.

To do this, we have modelled two different versions of each of the following representative architectures using Petri nets: 1oo1, 1oo2, 1oo3 and 2oo3. The first version has repair transitions for which the launch deadline is governed by an exponential law with parameter μ , whilst the launch time for each repair transition for the models relating to the second version has a constant value. Each of these architectures will be successively allocated one, two then three repairers. Finally, we will run these verifications for three different configurations: $KooN$ with only detected failures (DD), $KooN$ with only undetected failures (DU) before the next proof-test, $KooN$ with both types of failures. We can see that only the individual failures for the components are taken into account. The impact of the common cause failures will be considered last.

- Failures which are immediately detected and then repaired.
 - Parameters in question: $\lambda_{DD} = 1.10^{-3} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\mu = 0.125 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ or $\tau = MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$; observation period $T = 10000 \text{ hr}$; 10^5 trials.
 - Results: they are grouped together in table 5.1.

KooN architectures	Markov Hypothesis ($\mu = 0.125 \text{ h}^{-1}$)			Constant repair duration ($\tau = 8 \text{ h}$)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
1001	7.94286E-3	7.94286E-3	7.94286E-3	7.92887E-3	7.92887E-3	7.92887E-3
1002	1.23616E-4	6.12653E-5	6.12653E-5	6.44675E-5	6.40786E-5	6.40786E-5
1003	2.81765E-6	6.7032E-7	4.7434E-7	4.91878E-7	4.83159E-7	4.83050E-7
2003	3.77041E-4	1.87072E-4	1.86878E-4	1.91712E-4	1.87976E-4	1.87974E-4

Table 5.1: PFD_{avg} obtained in the case of immediately detected failures

- Comments: with the exception of 1001 architecture which is, as expected, insensitive to the effect of the repairers and to the type of law governing the repairs, we can see that the value obtained for the PFD_{avg} can be considered as independent of the number of repairmen available for all the architectures in the second option (τ). This is obviously not the case for the Markov models (μ). We can, however, note a very slight beneficial influence in the first case (τ), as soon as the number of repairers becomes equal to or greater than the number of faulty elements. This improvement logically stops growing beyond this threshold.
- Failures detected only during the proof-tests, then repaired
 - Parameters in question: $\lambda_{DU} = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\mu = 0.125 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ or $\tau = MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$; interval between tests $T_1 = 2190 \text{ hr}$ (3 months); observation period $T = 10^4 \text{ hr}$; 10^6 trials.
 - Results: they are given in table 5.2.

KooN architectures	Markov hypothesis ($\mu = 0.125 \text{ h}^{-1}$)			Constant repair duration ($\tau = 8 \text{ h}$)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
1001	2.55470E-2	2.55470E-2	2.55470E-2	2.55705E-2	2.55705E-2	2.55705E-2
1002	8.76094E-4	8.68893E-4	8.68893E-4	8.72557E-4	8.72398E-4	8.72398E-4
1003	3.62450E-5	3.46065E-5	3.45333E-5	3.68190E-5	3.68190E-5	3.68190E-5
2003	2.57098E-3	2.55639E-3	2.55514E-3	2.57070E-3	2.57019E-3	2.57019E-3

Table 5.2: PFD_{avg} obtained in the case of failures which are not immediately detected

- Comments: we can see the smoothing effect of latency T_1 which makes the values obtained for PFD_{avg} insensitive to the increase of the effect of the available repairmen and this, regardless of the repair mode in question (at a constant failure rate or duration (τ))
- Taking into account both types of failure

Only the 1003 and 2003 architectures were processed, as an example.

- Parameters in question: $\lambda_{DD} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{DU} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\mu = 0.125 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ or $\tau = MTTR = 8 \text{ hr}$; interval between tests $T_1 = 2190 \text{ hr}$ (3 months); observation period $T = 10^4$; 10^6 trials.
- Results: see after.

KooN architectures	Markov hypothesis ($\mu = 0.125 \text{ h}^{-1}$)			Constant repair duration ($\tau = 8 \text{ h}$)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
1oo3	2.63316E-6	2.60217E-6	2.59580E-6	2.88723E-6	2.88723E-6	2.88723E-6
2oo3	4.34862E-4	4.32258E-4	4.32248E-4	4.25153E-4	4.25112E-4	4.25112E-4

Table 5.3: $PF D_{avg}$ obtained for the general case (λ_{DD} and λ_{DU})

- Comments: the smoothing effect of T_1 is still demonstrated and this is easily understood. We can see that the number of repairers available has practically no impact on the values obtained for the $PF D_{avg}$ in the case of constant repair durations.

The experimental verification concerning the model with constant repair duration is conclusive. *We will therefore admit from now on that the different channels for a KooN architecture can be considered as mutually independent and that the values obtained for its $PF D_{avg}$ and its MDT do not depend on the effect of the available repairmen.*

We can also verify this statement on the following diagram, from [Simpson, 2003] which deals with the case of a 1oo2 system only submitted to failures which are immediately detected. C_1 and C_2 respectively indicate that channels 1 and 2 are in condition to work, \bar{C}_1 and \bar{C}_2 indicate respectively that they are faulty; MDT_i and MDT'_i represent the average component unavailability duration i when we have respectively several or just one repairman. The explanation is the same for MDT_s and MDT'_s relating to the 1oo2 system.

Figure 5.1: MDT and average vulnerability durations (V_S) of the system according to the number of repairmen available

We know that the unavailability of the system can only emerge when the channel which has been available until then becomes faulty during the unavailability of the first which is already faulty. We also know that on average the second failure appears part way through this first unavailability period, meaning at t_2 . In this case, we can actually see that the system unavailability duration remains equal to $MDT_i/2$, regardless of the number of repairmen available. This empirical observation is only valid if we take the probability that the system becomes faulty again during the so-called vulnerability periods (V_S and V'_S) as negligible. This is an acceptable hypothesis in general.

5.2.2.2. General expressions for PFH_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN}

If we consider a $KooN$ architecture of N identical and independent channels for which the probability of being in a state to operate at time t is p , we can classically express its unavailability as:

$$\bar{A}_{KooN}(t) = \sum_{i=N-K+1}^N C_N^i (1-p)^i \cdot p^{N-i} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\text{where } C_N^i = \frac{N!}{i!(N-i)!}.$$

The previous unavailability is therefore expressed in the form of the sum of K terms for a geometric succession for which the first term corresponds to $i = N-K+1$ and for which the reason q can be easily calculated. We therefore have:

$$q = \frac{C_N^{N-K+2} (1-p)^{N-K+2} \cdot p^{K-2}}{C_N^{N-K+1} (1-p)^{N-K+1} \cdot p^{K-1}} = \frac{K-1}{N-K+2} \cdot \frac{1-p}{p} \quad (5.2)$$

$$\bar{A}_{KooN}(t) = C_N^{N-K+1} (1-p)^{N-K+1} \cdot p^{K-1} \cdot \frac{1-q^K}{1-q} \quad (5.3)$$

As the value p is generally close to the unit, the value of q is much smaller. We can then deduce an approached value of the instantaneous unavailability of the $KooN$ system from it, meaning its $PFH(t)$.

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) \approx C_N^{N-K+1} (1-p)^{N-K+1} \quad (5.4)$$

We can see that limiting the unavailability to the previous expression returns to reducing all the failed states to the first among them which is affected, meaning to the critical failed state. This comment will be exploited in paragraph 5.2.4.

The $PFH_{KooN}(t)$ for the system can be determined according to the formula (4.5), given again below in (5.5), as its channels are independent:

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) \approx N \cdot I_B(KooN, c_i) \cdot w_i(t) \quad (5.5)$$

Now $I_B(KooN, c_i)$ is measured by the probability that the $KooN$ architecture is in a critical state due to channel c_i . We can therefore assimilate $I_B(KooN, c_i)$ to the probability that $(N-K)$ channels become faulty among the $(N-1)$ other than c_i still in an operating state.

$$I_B(KooN, c_i) = C_{N-1}^{N-K} (1-p)^{N-K} \cdot p^{K-1} \quad (5.6)$$

As $w_i(t) = \lambda \cdot p$, the equality (5.5) becomes:

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) = N\lambda \cdot C_{N-1}^{N-K} (1-p)^{N-K} \cdot p^K \quad (5.7)$$

Under the preceding hypothesis, we finally get:

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) \approx N\lambda \cdot C_{N-1}^{N-K} (1-p)^{N-K} \quad (5.8)$$

The members of the SGB group have not really tackled the expression for the Birnbaum importance factor to obtain their results, but they have doubtlessly reasoned directly using the KITT schema (Kinetic Tree Theory) [Vesely et al., 1970] [Kumamoto, 1996] applied on minimal cuts.

Working from the equalities (5.4) and (5.8) we can calculate the average respective values for PFH_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN} if we have the analytical expression of availability p for each channel. This point is tackled in the following paragraphs.

5.2.2.3. Expressions for PFH_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN} in the case of periodically detected failures which are repaired immediately

This case ($DC = 0$; $MTTR = 0$) corresponds to an architecture where the channels are tested periodically and possible repaired immediately.

We have, for $t \in [kT_1, (k+1)T_1]$ [avec $k \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$1-p = 1 - e^{-\lambda t} \approx \lambda t, \quad \text{if } \lambda T_1 \ll 1 \quad (5.9)$$

In these conditions, the equalities (5.4) and (5.8) are written:

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) \approx C_N^{N-K+1} (\lambda t)^{N-K+1} \quad (5.10)$$

$$PFH_{KooN}(t) \approx N\lambda \cdot C_{N-1}^{N-K} (\lambda t)^{N-K} \quad (5.11)$$

We can deduce the corresponding average values from them:

$$PFH_{KooN}(0, T_1) = \frac{1}{T_1} \int_0^{T_1} PFH_{KooN}(t) dt = C_N^{N-K+1} \frac{(\lambda T_1)^{N-K+1}}{N-K+2} \quad (5.12)$$

$$PFH_{KooN}(0, T_1) = \frac{1}{T_1} \int_0^{T_1} PFH_{KooN}(t) dt = C_N^{N-K+1} \lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot T_1^{N-K} \quad (5.13)$$

because $N \cdot C_{N-1}^{N-K} = (N-K+1) \cdot C_N^{N-K+1}$

The relationship (2.62) now gives us the general expression for the average unavailability duration for any $KooN$ architecture:

$$MDT_{KooN} = \frac{PFH_{KooN}}{PFH_{KooN}} = \frac{T_1}{N-K+2} \quad (5.14)$$

The specific case of $1ooN$ architectures is going to be useful. The expression of the corresponding MDT is given below.

$$MDT_{1ooN} = \frac{T_1}{N+1} \quad (5.15)$$

By virtue of a well known property ($A_n^p = p!C_n^p$) and (5.15), the equalities (5.12) and (5.13) can be rewritten in the following forms:

$$\begin{aligned} PFD_{KooN}(0, T_1) &= C_N^{N-K+1} \frac{(\lambda T_1)^{N-K+1}}{N-K+2} = \frac{A_N^{N-K+1}}{(N-K+1)!} \cdot \frac{\lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot T_1^{N-K+1}}{N-K+2} \\ &= A_N^{N-K+1} \lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot \frac{T_1^{N-K+1}}{(N-K+2)!} = A_N^{N-K+1} \lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^{N-K+1} \frac{T_1}{i+1} \end{aligned}$$

So:

$$PFD_{KooN}(0, T_1) = A_N^{N-K+1} \lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^{N-K+1} MDT_{1ooi} \quad (5.16)$$

$$PFH_{KooN}(0, T_1) = A_N^{N-K+1} \lambda^{N-K+1} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^{N-K} MDT_{1ooi} \quad (5.17)$$

5.2.2.4. Expressions for PFD_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN} in the case of periodically detected failures which are not repaired immediately

This case is similar to the previous one, but the repair for each channel requires a constant $MTTR$ duration. It follows that within the framework of the hypothesis of the constant repair durations, which we are looking at, the MDT is deduced from what is given in (5.14) or (5.15) by adding the $MTTR$ duration to it. So:

$$MDT_{KooN} = \frac{T_1}{N-K+2} + MTTR \quad (5.18)$$

$$MDT_{1ooN} = \frac{T_1}{N+1} + MTTR \quad (5.19)$$

The PFD_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN} are then obtained by carrying over the expressions (5.18) and (5.19) in (5.16) and (5.17) respectively.

5.2.2.5. Expressions for PFD_{KooN} and PFH_{KooN} in the case where both type of failures (detected and undetected) are taken into account

This is the case which is considered in the standard. It corresponds to $DC \in [0; 1[$. A “handcrafted” way of determining the analytical expression for PFD_{KooN} , in this case, is to graphically represent the possible sequences of successive failures which can be suffered by any architecture. Each branch of this graph (figure 5.2) represents the occurrence of a DD or DU type failure. It is identified by the rate corresponding to the failure which has emerged, as well as by the average duration required to put the architecture back into operation. This last value is obtained by complying with the schema, as seen in paragraph 5.2.2.2, according to

which all the architecture's failed states are summarised by its critical failure states. *This approximation is only valid if the rates of return from these states to an operating state (critical) are largely greater than the failure rates leading towards worsened failure states.* We have also shown the types of architecture involved on the right of each phase.

Figure 5.2: All possible failure sequences

Let us examine this tree. The parameter setting for the two extreme sequences is easily included. The one for the top sequence obeys the formula (5.19) and it reveals the same logic for the lower sequence, as shown in figure 5.1 relating to the 1oo2 architecture. The case of heterogeneous sequences is worth an extra explanation which is given below for the $(\lambda_{DU} - \lambda_{DD} - \lambda_{DU})$ sequence affecting a 2oo4 architecture, for example.

Figure 5.3: Determining MDT_{2oo4} for the sequence $(\lambda_{DU1} - \lambda_{DD1} - \lambda_{DU2})$

Let us consider an interval T_1 between two proof-tests. We know that, on average, the first undetected failure (DU1) emerges midway through, meaning at $T_1/2$. Then at a later moment t a second failure emerges, this time a detected type (DD1). The 2oo4 architecture is then in a critical operating state and it will remain there until $t + MTTR$, if no other failure occurs. On the other hand, the system fails if a third failure occurs between t and $t + MTTR$, regardless of whether it is DD or DU type. The average moment for this third failure to occur being $t + MTTR/2$, the average duration of unavailability of the architecture before restoration is therefore equal to $MTTR/2$.

Taking into account the low value of $MTTR$ compared to $1/\lambda_{DD}$ and $1/\lambda_{DU}$, the contribution of the overall MDT from the system of sequences containing an undetected failure can be negligible, as a first approximation, compared to those from the first two higher sequences. This is what the SGB group has done. In these conditions, the overall MDT for a $KooN$ architecture can be approximated by the weighted sum of the contributions from these two sequences. So:

$$MDT_{KooN} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{N-K+2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}} \cdot MTTR \quad (5.20)$$

We carry this expression in (5.16) and (5.17) to obtain them for $PF_{D_{KooN}}$ and $PF_{H_{KooN}}$ for the general case, which is what is considered in annex B in IEC 61508-6 standard. The relationship (5.16) applied to the 1oo3 architecture gives:

$$PF_{D_{1oo3}} = A_3^3 \lambda^3 \cdot \prod_{i=1}^3 MDT_{1ooi}$$

$$PF_{D_{1oo3}} = 6 \lambda^3 \cdot MDT_{1oo1} \cdot MDT_{1oo2} \cdot MDT_{1oo3} \quad (5.21)$$

As the preceding developments only deal with the individual failures of the architectures' channels, it is best to take it into account in the expression for the failure rate. (5.21) is then written as follows:

$$PF_{D_{1oo3}} = 6 \left((1-\beta_D) \lambda_{DD} + (1-\beta) \lambda_{DU} \right)^3 \cdot MDT_{1oo1} \cdot MDT_{1oo2} \cdot MDT_{1oo3} \quad (5.22)$$

with its MDT_i explained in compliance with (5.20). Being:

$$MDT_{1oo1} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR = t_{CE} \quad (5.23)$$

$$MDT_{1oo2} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{3} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR = t_{GE} \quad (5.24)$$

$$MDT_{1oo3} = \frac{\lambda_{DU}}{\lambda_D} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{4} + MTTR \right) + \frac{\lambda_{DD}}{\lambda_D} \cdot MTTR = t_{G2E} \quad (5.25)$$

We carry these three expressions into (5.22) we find the part concerning the individual failures of the formula given in the IEC 61508-6 standard in paragraph B.2.2.2.6, and for the one we ended up with in (3.44) in paragraph 3.5.1, by using an adapted Markov model.

We could then conclude that the Markov approach and the analytical approach, that we are attributing to the SGB group, lead to the same results concerning the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH . This observation is not currently shared by everyone and must be explained in more detail to be validated. This will be the topic of the next paragraph.

5.2.3. “The Markov fallacy”

The provocative title of this paragraph comes from an article by B. Gulland [Gulland, 2002] that D. J. Smith [Smith, 2002] presents thus: “Bill Gulland, ..., put it to me recently that the long established practise of using MARKOV modelling to quantify the unavailability of systems with repairs is flawed. He argues that since the repair activity is not random, the repair rate should not be treated (as its failure rate) as a random variable (sic!). Down times are more closely modelled as constant (although probably lognormal) and, ...”

In his article, Smith explains that “Ken Simpson and Mike Kelly took up this case and obtained the same answers as Bill Gulland, ...”

The reason evoked by these authors to refute the validity of the Markov approach is that it cannot correctly model the “true” nature of the repairs on the components. The duration of these repairs is not, in their opinion, a continuous random variable obeying an exponential law with parameter $\mu = 1/MTTR$, but a constant for value $MTTR$. The ‘particular’ logic of the previous reasoning comes from the fact that *there are actually two different problems* which seem to have confused the aforementioned authors. The first problem involves choosing the distribution law which governs the repair durations. The second involves choosing the right model likely to model the behaviour of the component equipped with the predefined repair type. Also, these authors' conclusion should not be that the Markov approach is wrong, but that it is not adapted to modelling constant duration repairs, which nobody denies! Our point of view is also shared by J. P. Signoret who reacted to the article by W. G. Gulland with an article with a humorous title: “Is Markov Fallacy fallacious?” [Signoret, 2003].

Another question that we share with him involves the relevance of the choice of a constant repair duration. If this choice might seem more realistic than that of exponential distribution [Pagès et al., 1980] in the case of components considered in isolation (for example a standard-exchange) and for well known types of failure, it seems that once integrated in a piece of equipment their repair becomes dependent on a large number of factors outside the component. The impact of these factors is translated by a certain distribution of repair durations.

Furthermore, in his answer, J. P. Signoret showed that out of all the distributions tested in a homogeneous 2oo3 architecture (Dirac, exponential, Weibull, normal-log, uniform) this is the first which provides the lowest values for the stationary unavailability of this architecture. This observation complies with what we could formulate from reading table 5.3 concerning the same type of architecture. However, numerous other experiments on varying architectures with different sets of data are required before this observation can be generalised.

To close this debate temporarily, we can formulate a reminder and one last question in the form of a conclusion.

- **The reminder**

We can only validly compare the results obtained via the two models on the list (constant repair duration or rate) if they are used in the same conditions. The major condition is that the components within the studied architectures are independent. They are also independent in terms of available repairmen. In the case of constant durations, we have seen that they are largely independent of the effect of the repairmen. It is therefore necessary that they are the same in the case of the repair rates. It is like this when this effective is always sufficient.

In these conditions and for the simple KooN architectures studied in the standard and the set of data proposed there, the two models actually provide comparable results.

- **The last question**

This looks at the proclaimed advantage of the constant repair duration model: the value obtained for the PFD_{avg} is the same, regardless of whether we have a single repairer or several.

This has been well identified in the first part of this chapter and by different authors, but only in the case considering just individual component failures. What is it when we take into account the common cause failures (CCF)?

Let us reformulate this question by explaining as follows: is the contribution of the CCF to the PFD_{avg} for a given KooN architecture, presented in annex B of IEC 61508-6 standard, correct?

Let us remember this formula, given for the 1oo2, 1oo3 and 2oo3 architectures:

$$\beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR \right) \quad (5.26)$$

If we think that this expression is acceptable for the first two aforementioned architectures, it seems formally wrong to us for the 2oo3 architecture and for all other KooN architectures with $K \geq 2$. We can justify our opinion by taking the example of the 2oo3 architecture.

In the case of CCF (DD or DU), the three channels fail simultaneously, the repair process starting immediately in the first case (DD) and just after the first test following the common failure moment, in the second case (DU). In all cases the system is operational again as soon as the first two channels are repaired. *This requires an average wait equal to MTTR after the start of repairs, if we have at least two repairmen, but a double wait if we just have one repairman.*

The values for MDT_{KooN} and PFD_{avg} are therefore affected. They are affected even more if the CCF are predominant. In the case we are looking at, the contribution of the CCFs should be expressed as follows:

$$2 \beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + 2 MTTR \right) \quad (5.27)$$

For any number of available repairmen (M), the CCFs' contribution to the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ can be generalised as follows:

$$PF_{KooN}^{CCF} = X \cdot \beta_D \lambda_{DD} \cdot MTTR + \beta \lambda_{DU} \cdot \left(\frac{T_1}{2} + X \cdot MTTR \right) \quad (5.28)$$

with:

$$X = \begin{cases} \frac{K}{M}, & \text{if } \frac{K}{M} \in \mathbb{N} \\ 1 + E\left(\frac{K}{M}\right), & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

where $E(Y)$ is the integer part of Y .

The fact that there is one or several repairmen therefore has a real influence on the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ for SIS, regardless of the distribution of the repair durations. From a numerical point of view the observation is in general less severe, as $MTTR \ll T_1$.

5.2.4. Conclusion relating to the original analytical approach

In this first part we have presented what we think to be the approach which has permitted one or several authors, members of the ad hoc commission, to propose analytical formulas for $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH for $KooN$ architectures presented in annex B of IEC 61508-6 standard.

This approach involves the following hypotheses and strong approximations:

- The number of repairmen available has no influence over the values obtained either for the MDT of the architecture in question, or for its $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH .
- The channels remain very available during each inter-test period.
- The unavailability of the studied architecture is reduced to its critical failed state(s).
- Only the undetected failures sequences are taken into consideration leading to the aforementioned critical states, possibly ending up in a detected failure.

Within the framework of these hypotheses and approximations, we have verified that the approach attributed to the SGB group can effectively lead to the analytical formulas presented in the standard, for the part translating the constitution of the individual failures. On the other hand, as far as the CCFs' contribution is concerned, the expression seems wrong in our opinion in the case of $KooN$ configurations with $2 \leq K \leq N$ with just one repairman.

We have also highlighted the preemptory and unjustified nature of the conclusions from this group according to which the results that it obtained show the Markov approach's inability to model the behaviour of repairable $KooN$ architectures.

In this respect, we have recalled some evidence: any theory or simply any approach is only valid within the framework of the hypotheses founding it. This should not be forgotten when using the analytical formulas proposed in the standard.

5.3. Architectural constraints

5.3.1. Reminder of the context

Determining the safety integrity value attributed to a safety function, covered in paragraph 1.5, results from a three stage approach where each can be run independently until comparing their results, at least for two of them.

The first, which we will look at, has traces of systematic hardware and software failures. As it does not enter into the framework of this work, it will not be considered further on.

The two other stages, however, will be studied because they tackle random hardware failures. However, they are different: one is probabilistic and the other is deterministic. In the first, allocating a safety integrity level to a safety function is conditioned by the value of the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ or the PFH of the SIS assuring this SIF. Let us remember that this relationship is illustrated by the content of tables 2 and 3 of IEC 61508-1 standard, reproduced below (tables 5.4 and 5.5).

Safety integrity level (SIL)	Low demand mode of operation ($PF_{D_{avg}}$)
4	$\geq 10^{-5}$ to $< 10^{-4}$
3	$\geq 10^{-4}$ to $< 10^{-3}$
2	$\geq 10^{-3}$ to $< 10^{-2}$
1	$\geq 10^{-2}$ to $< 10^{-1}$

Table 5.4: SIL in low demand mode

Safety integrity level (SIL)	Continuous or high demand mode of operation (PFH)
4	$\geq 10^{-9}$ to $< 10^{-8}$
3	$\geq 10^{-8}$ to $< 10^{-7}$
2	$\geq 10^{-7}$ to $< 10^{-6}$
1	$\geq 10^{-6}$ to $< 10^{-5}$

Table 5.5: SIL in high demand or continuous demand mode

However, this way is necessary, but not sufficient for the $PF_{D_{avg}}$, according to the IEC 61508 standard which imposes completing it with a second deterministic procedure, aiming to abide by certain minimum specifications in terms of architecture of sub-systems assuring a safety function, known by the name of *architectural constraints*.

Let us look again at this second procedure below.

The IEC 61508-2 standard states (paragraph 7.4.3.1) that, “in the context of the hardware’s safety integrity, the highest level of integrity which can be announced for the given safety function is limited by the hardware fault tolerance and the safe failure fraction for the sub-systems which carry out the safety function.”

We can firstly give or remember the definition of the two terms “fault tolerance” and “safe failure fraction” and then illustrate the step presented in annexe C of 61508-2 standard.

- A hardware fault tolerance of index N means that $(N+1)$ faults could cause a loss of the safety function.
- The safe failure fraction (*SFF*) for a sub-system is defined by the ratio between the *average* rate of safe failures, plus the detected dangerous failures (see chapter 2, paragraph 2.3.5) to the *average* total failure rate for the sub-system.

The adjective “average”, used twice in the second definition, is ambiguous. Does it suggest that it is necessary to calculate the average value of the failure rate for a sub-system or that it must be assimilated into its “stationary” or “asymptotic” value? In any case, it is not repeated in annex C of this same standard! This is why, when referring to what was said in paragraph 2.3.5 of this report, we can consider from now on that, *if the notion of SFF must be conserved, it can only be applied without constraint at component level, where the failure rate is constant, or for the element of a channel.*

In order to illustrate this idea, let us consider a SIS which must assure a SIF with a safety integrity level equal to 3. This imposes that each sub-system (input, solver, output) of the SIS has at least this SIL.

To verify this we can follow the next step for each sub-system.

- Firstly we consider that this sub-system is made up of a single element. Its tolerance to hardware faults is therefore at level zero. We calculate its *SFF* and we see that it is in the interval $[60\% ; 90\%[$.
- Both pieces of data are input data for table 2 or table 3 of IEC 61508-2 standard reproduced below (tables 5.6 and 5.7).

Safe failure fraction (SFF)	<i>Hardware Fault Tolerance</i>		
	0	1	2
< 60 %	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
60 % - < 90 %	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
90 % - < 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4
>= 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

A SIS can be considered to be type A if its behaviour in the presence of faults is well determined, if the failure modes of its constituent parts are well defined and if the data concerning their failures, from the feedback, are known with good reliability.

Table 5.6: Architectural constraints on type A SIS

Safe failure fraction (SFF)	<i>Hardware Fault Tolerance</i>		
	0	1	2
< 60 %	Unauthorised	SIL 1	SIL 2
60 % - < 90 %	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
90 % - < 99 %	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
>= 99 %	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

A SIS can be considered as type B if one of the three conditions governing type A is not satisfied.

Table 5.7: Architectural constraints on type B SIS

For each of the preceding tables, crossing these two orthogonal inputs gives the maximum value of the SIL that we can state for the element and therefore for the sub-system. SIL 2, in our case, if we suppose that this sub-system is type A.

- As this level is insufficient there are, in theory, two ways of improving it:
 - By redundancy, by moving horizontally across the table to SIL3. Obtaining this level requires index 1 fault tolerance, meaning that the initial element must be doubled. We can now verify whether the real architecture of the sub-system satisfies this minimum requirement or if it has to be reinforced.
 - The second line of improvement consists of conserving the initially considered 1oo1 architecture for which we will have improved the *SFF* to attain SIL 3. This returns to moving vertically up the first column of the SIL to SIL 3. We can deduce that the unique element constituting the sub-system in question must possess a *SFF* which is greater than or equal to 90%.

This second way of working, revolving around replacing the initial element with another which has a better *SFF*, rather than doubling it (redundancy) is not brought up in the standard.

The first procedure should be reiterated for each of the three sub-systems in the SIS. The overall SIL which must assure this SIS is obtained by applying the combination rules illustrated in sub-paragraph 7.4.3.1.6 of IEC 61508-2 standard.

We can see that it is admitted that this deterministic procedure is more restricting, in terms of SIL, than the one based on calculating the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ of the SIS in charge of the running the SIF and which, for this reason, is classified as probabilistic.

The SFF is therefore the key element of the deterministic procedure which has just been recalled, but is it a relevant element? We are going to attempt to answer this question in the new paragraph.

5.3.2. For or against the use of the *SFF*?

The well-founded introduction to the architectural constraints in IEC 61508-2 standard is not refutable *a priori*, as the objective is to obtain a sufficiently robust architecture, taking into account the complexity of the sub-system in question (note 1, page 42 of volume 2 of the standard).

We are not answering the chosen objective, but the fact that we must resort to the *SFF* to attain it. This opinion is not shared by B. Hoekstra [Hoekstra, 2005] who judges this resort as necessary: “The *SFF* is needed to determine the required hardware fault tolerance corresponding with the required SIL and, as such, it defines whether a single safety element can be applied or that redundant elements are needed in the safety architecture.”

However, following the example of J.P. Signoret [Signoret, 2006a], we still think that the SFF of any entity is representative neither of its safety, nor its availability, as shown in the following example. So what use is it?

Let us actually consider two proof-tested components C_1 and C_2 , for which the reliability characteristics are given below:

- C_1 ($\lambda_{1S} = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{1D} = \lambda_{1DU} = 6.10^{-8} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $T_1 = 4380 \text{ hr}$; type A),
- C_2 ($\lambda_{2S} = 5.10^{-8} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $\lambda_{2D} = \lambda_{2DU} = 5.10^{-8} \text{ hr}^{-1}$; $T_2 = 4380 \text{ hr}$; type A).

We can easily calculate their respective PFD_{avg} : $PFD_{avg1} = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $PFD_{avg2} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Table 2 of IEC 61508-1 standard tells us that these values correspond to a SIL 3. We can now calculate their SFF and we obtain: $SFF_{C1} = 0.9$ and $SFF_{C2} = 0.5$.

Consulting table 2 of IEC 61508-2 standard then shows us that taking into account the architectural constraints confirms the level 3 attributed to component C_1 , but limits to level 2 that of component C_2 . The latter is therefore more restricted, more penalised by its SFF than C_1 is, whilst it is slightly higher from the point of view of safety ($\lambda_{2D} < \lambda_{1D}$), and 10 times better, from the point of view of availability and therefore production ($\lambda_{2S} < \lambda_{1S}$).

The preceding example does not argue in favour of using the SFF. The alternative which is offered to us is clear: should we eliminate the SFF or replace it with something else?

As it seems difficult to impose its elimination, taking into account its already old circulation, we have to find an acceptable substitute. Several clues are possible, many of which are still being explored. We are going to present three of them.

5.3.3. Alternative Proposals

5.3.3.1. Proposal 1

This comes from Jean-Pierre Signoret who submitted it in 2006 to the members of the MT13 work group for the standardisation committee in charge of the IEC 61508, where he is a member.

The primary interest of this proposal is that it presents the same logic as the original based on the SFF but without resorting to this parameter, criticised with good reason. The latter is replaced by a new parameter which characterises, in a non-quantified but in-depth way, the element studied, as its value reflects all the knowledge that we have on the subject. This new parameter is called *CARS* (for Confidence in the Ability to Reach a SIL required for a given safety instrumented function). Following the example of what is done for the SFF , we also define four levels of *CARS* (High, Good, Medium, Low), as explained below.

Taking into account the architectural constraints aims, let us remember, to protect itself from the potentially harmful uncontrolled effects which sully both the reliability data used and the knowledge that we have on the real operation of the subsystems constituting the SIS. As opposed to the SFF which is “hit” via failure rates λ_S and λ_D , by the first category of uncertainties, the *CARS* frees itself, because we are defining the level from qualitative considerations relating to the feedback and the knowledge that we have regarding the hardware and its usage context, as indicated by notes 1 to 3 attached to table 5.8.

Scope	Sub-system		
	Quality proven by use	Quality partially proven by use Feedback available	New or unproven quality
Known	High	Good	Medium
New	Good	Medium	Low

Table 5.8: Evaluation of CARS level

Note 1 – The sub-systems, for which feedback is available but insufficient to be able to justify the label “quality proven by use” are considered to be more worthy of confidence that those which are new or with quality not proven by use.

Note 2 - A SIL certified sub-system will be given a new “High” *CARS* only if it is strictly used in compliance with what is indicated on its certificate.

Note 3 – If a detailed reliability test has been run on a sub-system and if all its weaknesses have been identified, the *CARS* level which was given to it initially can be re-evaluated and move up by one step (for example from Low to Medium, from Medium to Good and from Good to High). This will be done on the basis of a documented reliability file.

Once the *CARS* level has been defined, determining the definitive SIL to attribute to the studied sub-system is done in the same way as before with the *SFF* (see paragraph 6.2) as shown below in tables 5.9 and 5.10, slightly modified replicas of tables 2 and 3 of I EC 61508-2 standard.

SFF (%) or CARS (qualitative)	<i>Hardware Fault Tolerance</i>		
	0	1	2
< 60 % or Low	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
60 % -- < 90 % or Medium	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
90 % -- < 99 % or Good	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4
>= 99 % or High	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

Table 5.9: Architectural constraints on type A SIS

SFF (%) or CARS (qualitative)	<i>Hardware Fault Tolerance</i>		
	0	1	2
< 60 % or Low	Unauthorised	SIL 1	SIL 2
60 % -- < 90 % or Medium	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3
90 % -- < 99 % or Good	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
>= 99 % or High	SIL 3	SIL 4	SIL 4

Table 5.10: Architectural constraints on type B SIS

Although his sources of inspiration come from standard documents which have already been published (project for ISO 20815 / 1PI 17 N standard) and they constitute an interesting alternative approach to the original approach based on the *SFF*, the previous proposal does not seem to have received agreement from other members of the MT13 work group, for the paradoxical reasons that the key parameter on which it rests, *CARS*, is not quantified! *This is*

actually a surprising reason because the architectural constraints were rightly inserted in the standard to compensate for the probabilistic and therefore quantitative nature of determining $PF_{D_{avg}}$, judged as not very reliable, because based on uncertain or rather imprecise numerical data.

But we must not despair because, during a meeting of this group in Geneva December 2007, Jean-Pierre Signoret was asked to reconsider an alternative approach to the *SFF* and draw up a proposal in this respect. He did this and after numerous exchanges between different members, an advance version of this alternative proposal, entitled Route 2, will be presented to the whole MT13 group during a meeting planned for mid April 2008, in Pau.

We are not authorised to reveal the content, but we can simply quote a passage demonstrating the existence of this new line:

“In the context of hardware safety integrity, the highest safety integrity level that can be claimed for a safety function is limited by the design constraints which shall be achieved by implementing one of two possible routes :

- route 1 based on hardware fault tolerance and failure concept,
- route 2 based on reliability engineering recognized good practices and field feedback.”

Before being informed of this new option and having observed the negative reception reserved for Jean-Pierre Signoret’s first alternative proposal, we ourselves had started to present to other lines which, in one way or another, integrated the architectural constraints without resorting to the *SFF*. They are designated below, by proposals 2 and 3.

5.3.3.2. Proposal 2

In line with the spirit of the standard, the second alternative method proposed is applied to the complete SIS assuring a safety function and not to its sub-systems considered individually. It permits very simply to verify if the SIL obtained following determining the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ of the safety instrumented system can be confirmed in the state or if it must be dropped down a step. Its principle is illustrated by figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: Principle of the method for validation or non validation of the SIL

We cut each zone of the SIL into two disjointed parts known as ZONE 1 and ZONE 2. The first, corresponding to the interval $[1. 10^{-(i+1)} ; x . 10^{-(i+1)}]$, is the validation or acceptance zone for the SIL resulting from the value calculated for the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ of the SIS,

whilst the second, corresponding to the interval $] x \cdot 10^{-(i+1)} ; 1 \cdot 10^{-i}]$, is the non-validation zone and therefore the required improvement zone.

In fact, if the value calculated for the PFD_{avg} belongs to ZONE 1, we can think that even in the event of underestimating due to imprecise data, the real value of PFD_{avg} should not exceed the maximum threshold value of the SIL zone in question. This, on the condition that the value of x remains reasonable, meaning less than or equal to 5, for example. However, if PFD_{avg} belongs to ZONE 2, the risk of exceeding the threshold is more probable. As a safety measure, this leads to dropping the previously obtained SIL down a unit. It will therefore be necessary to improve the architecture of the SIS or the quality of its constitutive parts to be able to find the initial SIL.

We can see that we can differentiate the values to be attributed to x according to the type (A or B) of the SIS.

However, this method suffers from a disadvantage. This involves the choice of the value to attribute to x . This choice requires some expertise and will doubtlessly need adjusting after feedback.

However, we think that it is not an insurmountable task.

5.3.3.3. Proposal 3

Another possibility to avoid resorting to the *SFF* to validate or drop down the value obtained in a probabilistic way for the SIL of a system, whilst taking into account the uncertainties which affect it, is rightly to run this calculation by integrating these uncertainties into it. This procedure is known, but requires the use of dedicated software, which could damage its circulation for some users of the standard.

The striking points of this procedure are summarised below, where we consider, as an example, that the law of probability allocated to each basic event e_i of the fault tree is an exponential law of parameter λ_i (component failure rate linked to event e_i):

- We assimilate λ_i into a random variable X_i distributed following a log-normal law of parameters μ_i and σ_i which are going to be determined.
- We admit that X_i is generally going to fall in the interval $[X_{0.5}/FE_i ; X_{0.5} \cdot FE_i]$, where the median $X_{0.5}$ is taken equal to λ_i and the error factor FE_i is attributed a value chosen by the analyst (for example 3 or 10 or 30...).
- We can deduce the values for parameters μ_i and σ_i as follows:

$$\mu_i = \ln \lambda_i \text{ and } \sigma_i = (1/1,645) \cdot \ln (FE_i)$$
- For each e_i we pick out at random following a uniform law on $[0, 1]$ a couple of independent numbers $(x_{i,1} ; x_{i,2})$, which is the same as simulating following a reduced normal law the variable $u_i = (-2 \ln x_{i,2})^{1/2} \cdot \cos(2\pi x_{i,1}) = (\ln X_i - \mu_i) / \sigma_i$ and X_i following a lognormal distribution [Box, 1958]. We can thereby deduce the probability $p(e_i)$ of each e_i and calculate the corresponding value $p(S)$ of the probability of the peak event, which corresponds here to the instantaneous value $PFD(t)$ of the studied SIS.
- We repeat this process a large number of times N , which provides a significant sample $[p(S_1), \dots, p(S_N)]$ from which we can deduce interesting statistics magnitudes, such as average, standard-deviation, confidence interval...

What has just been explained for the $PF D(t)$ value is valid for the average value $PF D_{avg}$, calculated over any predefined period.

$PF D_{avg}$ is therefore itself a random variable which it is advisable to exploit. We now have two possibilities:

- Either we can determine its distribution via a histogram and deduce from it, for example, the probability that this $PF D_{avg}$ will exceed or not the upper limit of the SIL zone attributed initially to the studied system. If this probability does not exceed a redefined threshold value, we can confirm this SIL, if not we drop it down by a unit. In this case, we can resort to redundancy to satisfy the required SIL requirement.
- Or, we content ourselves with verifying that all or most (proportion to be set beforehand) of the confidence interval attached to the $PF D_{avg}$ is included in the SIL zone determined beforehand in a probabilistic way. In this case, the SIL is confirmed, but it is dropped down a unit, as before.

The overall procedure, which constitutes proposal 3, seems to us to be the most rigorous but gives the major disadvantage of still being probabilistic!

There are certainly other approaches working from the same “philosophy” as our proposal 3 but we only know about one of them. This is by Mohamed Sallak who proposes, in chapter 3 of his thesis [Sallak, 2007], a fuzzy probabilistic approach for the evaluation of the operating safety of the systems in the presence of imperfect reliability data. He particularly uses it to determine the $PF D_{avg}$ for an SIS and evaluate the SIL of the safety function it assures. This step is interesting, but requires handling “fuzzy probabilities” which can raise certain problems regarding choice of support model (fault tree, Markov graphs, Petri nets, ...) and induce calculation difficulties, in our opinion.

5.3.3.4. Conclusion relating to SFF

At the end of this section dedicated to the validity of the use of the *SFF* to constrain the probabilistic determination of the SIL, *it seems clear to us that this parameter is not relevant.*

The reasons given in paragraph 2.1.5 already raise a few questions and the short example reviewed in paragraph 6.3 shows that *the SFF is a magnitude which represents neither the safety of an entity nor its availability.* Furthermore, the fact that a strong value for *SFF* is advantageous, is likely to lead to *damageable behaviours* from certain manufacturers who might be tempted to artificially improve the *SFF* of their products by adding a module equipped with a significant safe failure rate.

In short, the alternative which we are confronted with concerning resorting to the *SFF* is always the same:

- Either we make its use optional, which would more or less be the same as eliminating it. This option seems to have been discarded.
- Or we substitute it or add another approach to it, and there the field of proposals remains open.

5.4. Spurious trip failures

5.4.1. Introduction

This last section of the last chapter of our thesis is actually the first draft of a specific study which will be dedicated to taking into account of the safe failures and the spurious trip failures when determining the SIL of a SIS.

If safe failures are defined in the IEC 61508-4 standard (see paragraph 2.4 of this report) and they are quoted, via their failure rate λ_s , in table B1 of standard IEC 61508-6, and play a role in calculating the SFF, they practically do not appear in the analytical formulas proposed in the latter document to evaluate the average values of $PF_D(t)$ and $PF_H(t)$ for the different architectures which are studied there. Only the 1oo2D architecture mentions it.

As for spurious trip failures, they are not even quoted!

We therefore propose to successively examine the possible impact of safe failures, in the standard-based meaning, might have on the SIS performance indicators meaning its $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and its PF_H , as well as the possible impact of spurious trip failures on the frequency of the feared event that the SIS should warn about.

To do this, we are firstly going to look back at our first thoughts on the nature of safe failures and spurious trip failures in paragraph 2.4, to try and define them more accurately. This will feature in the next paragraph.

Then we will show in paragraph 5.4.3, and on the basis of two simple examples, that integrating these failures in the SIS behavioural models barely modifies the values initially obtained for the $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PF_H during dangerous failures were the only ones taken into account. We should however explain that *this statement is only valid if we register it in the standard-based approach* for which, on the one hand, the low demand and continuous demand operating modes are examined separately and, on the other hand, the failures which start an evolution of the monitored system towards a safety status are safe failures.

However, the process to determine the frequency of the dangerous event (accident) must be reviewed if we maintain *the realistic hypothesis of a certain durability of the demand after it occurs*. This case is studied in paragraph 5.4.4.

5.4.2. Safe failures and spurious trip failures

Let us start by reviewing some conclusions emitted in paragraph 2.4, in hindsight, to confirm their validity or to adjust them.

- In the SINTEF classification, spurious trip failures constitute a sub-assembly of safe failures. In our opinion, this point of view is at least questionable, if we bear in mind the two counter-examples given at the end of paragraph 2.4.2 (airbag and inversion of thrust flux for an airplane reactor). In fact, spurious trip failures can, depending on the circumstances, take the EUC into a safe status or into a dangerous status. From this point of view, their domain partially recovers that of the safe failures and the dangerous failures.

- Whilst examining what we called “TOTAL classification” we wrote that another way of describing the preceding partition (between dangerous failures and safe or spurious trip failures) is to say that the first type (dangerous failures) tends to inhibit the SIS’s expected function *in the event of a demand*, whilst the second type tends to anticipate triggering this function, meaning *even before a demand appears*.

The reminder of the two preceding conclusions now leads us to the following comments:

- The fact the *spurious failure* is the translation given to the French phrase *défaillance intempestive* or even *défaillance inopportune* reveals, in our opinion, more of an interpretation than a faithful translation. So, a recent edition of the HARRAP’S New Shorter bilingual dictionary translates the adjective *spurious* as *faux* thereby bringing it closer to *erroneous*, whilst the common translation proposed for *intempestif* or *inopportun* is *untimely*, *inopportune*, *ill-timed*.
- This simple statement shows that this type of failure (*spurious failure*) is perceived from emerging *at the wrong time* and more precisely *prematurely*. This time connotation cannot be denied and the reference, explained to a certain extent, is that of the possible demand occurrence. The reference clearly appears in the conclusion that we have recalled regarding the “TOTAL classification” as well as in a recent article on this subject [Lundteigen et al., 2007]. In this latter article, the authors use the collective term of *spurious activation*, in which “*spurious indicates that the cause of activation is improper, false or non-genuine, while activation indicates that there is some type of transition from one state to another.*” Furthermore they distinguish several types of *spurious activation* (*spurious operation*, *spurious trip*, *spurious shutdown*), although all mentioning in their definition that they are produced “*without the presence of a specified process demand.*”
- The reference to a period before the occurrence of a demand or its absence clearly shows that, for most people interested in spurious trip failures, this only refers to low demand operating mode. This restriction has no justification, if only the fact that the continuous demand domain, and its associated *PFH*, were studied at less length than the low demand and its characteristic indicator *PFD_{avg}*.

It therefore seems useful to us to raise this restriction. We will do this below and in paragraph 5.4.4 by considering, with others [Sato et al., 2006], that *the demand state cannot be fugitive and last a certain time before the controlled system is led to a safe state. During this time, a SIS failure can occur and make it impossible to withdraw safely.*

We have illustrated this fact and aim to explain what we understand, more generally, by spurious trip failures, by taking two events as an example which could upset the planned operation of the HIPPS looked at in chapter 4 (see figure 4.4), which are considered independently from one another.

- The first event considered, which would be called *spurious operation* in [Lundteigen et al., 2007], involves total closure of one of the two shutdown valves SDV_i, in the absence of demand, meaning in the absence of any over-pressure.

This closing, which in *production phase* should only result in triggering the safety function assured by the HIPPS and intended to protect the downstream over-pressure circuit, occurs inopportune and causes this production to stop. In our opinion, this deserves the description of *inopportune failure*.

- The second event considered can occur after successful triggering of the preceding safety function, initiated by the sensors that detected a real over-pressure. As this over-pressure was always present in the upstream circuit, the HIPPS operating mode is now continuous demand. *Its safety function is from now on to keep at least one of the two SDVi valves closed to continue to protect the downstream circuit from any over-pressure.* Then an erroneous command occurs from the logic solver LS which results in inopportunoely opening the SDVi valves. This opening occurs between the over-pressure evacuation operations have been completed. This leads to the downstream circuit being submitted to a undesired over-pressure.

In our opinion, once again, this kind of failure of the logic solver, known as *spurious trip* in [Lundteigen et al., 2007], is worthy of the description *untimely failure*.

These two examples allow us to propose the following extended definition for this type of failure:

“A untimely failure can only be defined compared to a specified safety function. This results either in triggering the production of this safety function in the absence of any demand or cancelling the protecting effect of this function after successful triggering.”

We can note that the first part of this definition concerns the low demand mode of operation for the HIPPS which assures the safety function, and that the second looks at the continuous mode of operation for the same HIPPS.

Another point to highlight: in the first case, the spurious trip failure can be considered as safe (perhaps temporarily) whilst it is dangerous in the second configuration. In other words, this leads us to once again affirm that *spurious trip failures do not constitute a sub-assembly of safe failures, or dangerous failures for that matter.*

5.4.3. Determining $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH in the presence of safe failures

Once again we will look at the framework of the hypotheses and definitions retained in the IEC 61508-6 standard. The scope of this paragraph is to show that taking into account the safe failures barely modifies the numerical values obtained initially using formulas or models which only integrate dangerous failures for components. This is not surprising taking into account the failure rate values concerned and the limited duration of the failed states.

The following two simple examples illustrate this fact. They concern the 1oo1 and 1oo2 architectures respectively.

The set of parameters retained is given below:

$$\lambda = 2 \quad \lambda_D = 2 \quad \lambda_S = 5E-6 \text{ hr}^{-1}; \quad \mu_r = \mu_{DD} = 0.125 \text{ hr}^{-1}; \quad T_1 = 8760 \text{ hr}; \quad \beta_S = \beta; \quad \beta_{SD} = \beta_D.$$

5.4.3.1. 1oo1 Architecture

Figure 5.5: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo1 architecture integrating safe failures

Approaches DC (%)	Without safe failures		With safe failures	
	$PF_{D_{avg}}$	PFH	$PF_{D_{avg}}$	PFH
0	1.08899E-2	2.47277E-6	1.08896E-2	2.47272E-6
60	4.3870E-3	2.4890E-6	4.3869E-3	2.4889E-6
90	1.1142E-3	2.49720E-6	1.1141E-3	2.49717E-6

Table 5.11: Results relating to $PF_{D_{1oo1}}$ and PFH_{1oo1} with and without taking into account safe failures

As announced, we can see for this first configuration that taking into account the safe failures, in the sense of the standard and for λ_S values given by default in this document, practically does not modify the previously obtained values for $PF_{D_{avg}}$ and PFH when only dangerous failures were considered.

5.4.3.2. 1oo2 Architecture

Figure 5.6: Multi-phase Markov model relating to 1oo2 architecture integrating safe failures

Approach			Without safe failures		With safe failures	
			PFD_{avg}	PFH	PFD_{avg}	PFH
Markov multi- phase	0	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.223E-3	2.93E-7	1.2219E-3	2.929E-7
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.289E-3	5.33E-7	2.2888E-3	5.32987E-7
	60	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	4.592E-4	1.93E-7	4.591E-4	1.93044E-7
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	8.931E-4	3.65E-7	8.931E-4	3.6459E-7
	90	$\beta = 2\beta_D = 10\%$	1.114E-4	1.42E-7	1.114E-4	1.420E-7
		$\beta = 2\beta_D = 20\%$	2.211E-4	2.79E-7	2.211E-4	2.78874E-7

Table 5.12: Results relating to PFD_{1002} and PFH_{1002} with and without taking into account safe failures

Exploiting the model from figure 5.6 leads to the preceding results table. A second time we can see that integrating the safe failures into the model barely modifies the original results for the PFD_{avg} and PFH obtained in chapters 3 and 4.

5.4.4. Determining the accident frequency in the general case

In the following diagram, let us consider the generic behavioural model for a SIS integrating the demand emanating from the monitored EUC. The different states and transitions from the model are defined below.

- Each state is identified by three labels. The top and middle labels indicate the state for the SIS and EUC respectively. The lower label is just the number affected in the state.
- The parameter λ_d is the rate that the demand occurs, λ_D is the overall dangerous failure rate for the SIS, μ is the inverse of the mean down time (MDT) for the SIS, following the occurrence of a dangerous failure. μ_d is the inverse of the average latency duration for the demand and μ_r is the inverse of the average time taken to put the EUC back into operation after it was stopped by the SIS reacting to a demand.
- The meaning of μ_R is identical to what is given in paragraph 2.3.1.3.
- In compliance with the preceding conclusion, the safe failures (in the standard's sense of the word) which could lead the overall system of each from states 1 and 2 to state 4 are not taken into account.

In the same way there is a possible dangerous failure which would lead this same system from a safe state to the dangerous state 3. This type of *mutating failure* (initially safe then dangerous) was proposed by some authors [Langeron et al., 2007] and presents clear potential interest. However, it seems to us that its reality may be wrong and would have to be proven before integrating it into the model.

Figure 5.7: Generic states-transitions model for the system (EUC + SIS) integrating the demand

State 5 corresponds to the accident that the SIS is aiming to prevent in the case of demand. Let us determine the expression of the frequency of occurrence for this accident by resorting to the critical operating state method applied to the Markov graph in figure 5.7:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_{acc} &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T w(t) dt = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T (p_3(t) \cdot \lambda_d + p_2(t) \cdot \lambda_D) dt \\
 &= \frac{\lambda_d}{T} \cdot \int_0^T p_3(t) dt + \frac{\lambda_D}{T} \cdot \int_0^T p_2(t) dt
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.29}$$

Now, we know that under some conditions (see paragraph 2.3.3) we can approximate the average values of the probabilities of staying in different states for a model by their asymptotic values. In these conditions, (5.29) becomes:

$$w_{acc} \approx \lambda_d \cdot p_3(\infty) + \lambda_D \cdot p_2(\infty) \tag{5.30}$$

By explaining $p_2(\infty)$ and $p_3(\infty)$, by making the realistic hypothesis that $p_1(\infty) \approx 1$, we get:

$$w_{acc} \approx \frac{\lambda_D}{(\lambda_d + \mu)} \cdot \lambda_d + \frac{\lambda_d}{(\lambda_D + \mu_d)} \cdot \lambda_D \tag{5.31}$$

As the SIS initially works in low demand, λ_d is negligible before μ . This is the same for the duration of the demand ($1/\mu_d$) compared with the life duration for the SIS before the occurrence of a dangerous failure ($1/\lambda_D$). This can be translated as: $\lambda_D \ll \mu_d$. In these conditions, the equality (5.31) is simplified:

$$w_{acc} \approx \frac{\lambda_D}{\mu} \cdot \lambda_d + \frac{\lambda_d}{\mu_d} \cdot \lambda_D \quad (5.32)$$

now $\frac{\lambda_D}{\mu}$ and $\frac{\lambda_d}{\mu_d}$ respectively report the average value of the *PFH* for the SIS, PFH_{SIS} , and the average probability of the demand, $p(demand)$. If we also remember that λ_D and λ_d are respectively approximations of the *PFH* for the SIS and the frequency of the demand, the final expression of the accident frequency is given by (5.33):

$$w_{acc} \approx PFH_{SIS} \cdot w_{demande} + PFH_{SIS} \cdot p(demande) \quad (5.33)$$

Here are the two extreme cases of the SIS mode of operation:

- **Low demand mode**

In this case, $p(demand) \approx 0$ and (5.33) is reduced to:

$$w_{acc} = PFH_{SIS} \cdot w_{demande} \quad (5.34)$$

This corresponds to the following chronological sequence: *failure of the SIS followed by the occurrence of the demand*.

- **Continuous demand mode**

This time $p(demand) = 1$. Now this demand emanates from the EUC which is continuously outside its nominal state, meaning unavailable to all intents and purposes ($A_{EUC} = 0$). In these conditions $w_{demand} = \lambda_{EUC} \cdot A_{EUC} = 0$, and (5.33) is reduced to:

$$w_{acc} \approx PFH_{SIS} \quad (5.35)$$

This corresponds to the following chronological sequence: *sustainable presence of the demand followed by the occurrence of the SIS failure*.

The equalities (5.34) and (5.35) which return to equalities (2.40) and (2.33) only reflect specific cases. *An exhaustive analysis of the behaviour of any SIS should conclude that a SIS is as likely to fail before or after the occurrence of a demand and that each of these two mutually exclusive configurations can lead to the undesired event (accident)*.

In other more concise terms, the frequency of this accident must be calculated based on the formula (5.33) in which *the SIS failure modes to be taken into consideration to calculate the PFH_{SIS} and the PFH_{SIS} are different* (see paragraph 5.4.2).

5.4.5. Partial conclusion on spurious trip failures

During this preliminary study dedicated to safe failures and spurious trip failures, we have examined several aspects of this problem area. We will review them succinctly below, as well as the conclusions that we have come to on this matter.

- Definition of safe failures and spurious trip failures
 - A safe failure leads the SIS into a safer state than it was previously occupying, without however triggering the safety function, but coming close to it.
 - A spurious trip failure results either in triggering the production of this safety function in the absence of any demand or cancelling the protecting effect of this function after successful triggering.
- Impact of safe failures on PFD_{avg} and PFH values
 - If we look within the framework of the hypotheses which govern the standard's mathematical developments, this impact seems minimal, but it necessarily leads to values which are not at all optimistic.
 - These values would become clearly more optimistic, meaning clearly non conservative and therefore potentially dangerous, if the undetected safe failures over a significant duration affected some constitutive parts of the SIS.

As a consequence, it seems more prudent to calculate the PFD_{avg} and PFH by taking into account only dangerous failures. This calculation mode, used in the standard, is conservative, but penalising.

- Impact of the spurious trip failures
 - Taking into account the fact that this type of failure modifies the way of apprehending the occurrence frequency for the undesired event (accident) which the SIS must prevent. The “SIS failure + presence of demand” combination must no longer be reduced to a single sequence of order 2, but it must be considered as the union of two mutually incompatible sequences also of order 2.
 - A spurious trip failure can lead to the shutdown of the monitored process and putting it into safe state (impact on the production availability) in low demand mode or lead to the aforementioned undesired event in continuous demand mode (impact on safety).

5.5. PFD_{avg} and risk reduction factor

5.5.1. Reminder of the context and problem raised

This context, already evoked in paragraphs 1.4.2 and 1.5.1, involved reducing the risk obtained by interposing several layers of protection between the initiating event (demand) emanating from the monitored process and the target to protect (people, plant, environment). This protection technique is looked at in detail in annex F of CEI 61511-3 standard under the title of *LOPA* for *Layer Of Protection Analysis*. It has been abundantly presented, commented on, implemented, but too often unfortunately without remaining detached. This explains how many authors [Dowell, 1998] [Marszal, 2000] [Dowell et al., 2002] [Gowland, 2005] [Babu, 2007] are happy to loyally apply the procedure given in the standard, as we did first of all in chapter 1, with a warning at the end of paragraph 1.5.1.

In fact, in the case of an association (parallel assembly in reliability terms) of several independent protection layers (IPL for Independent Protection Layers), these authors have written that the risk reduction factor RFF_S provided by this association were the same as the product of the individual factors RFF_i for the layers making them up. So:

$$RRF_S = \prod_{i=1}^n RRF_i = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{PFD_i} \quad (5.36)$$

In other words, in their opinion, the PFD_S for the assembly is therefore equal to the product of the PFD_i for the constitutional layers:

$$PFD_S = \prod_{i=1}^n PFD_i \quad (5.37)$$

This is clearly false, if we remember that we are talking about average values. We have already shown (in paragraph 2.3.3.4) this type of error which is perpetuated!

In order to illustrate this problem specifically, we will look again below at the case for a simple association of two protection layers [Innal et al., 2008].

5.5.2. Illustration of a common erroneous procedure

The equation (5.38) which partially returns to equation (1.3) is correct, regardless of the protection system in question, whether it is reduced to a single layer or not.

$$RRF = \frac{1}{PFD_{avg}} \quad (5.38)$$

But in the latter case, it is imperative to consider all the protection layers together. This is what the following example is going to show.

Figure 5.8: Risk reduction carried out according to the standard by associating two protection layers

In compliance with the standard and current usage, Figure 5.8 illustrates how risk reduction is calculated resulting from the association of two protection barriers.

In order to simplify the demonstration, we can suppose that the first layer is a SIS with 1oo1 architecture and the second is a valve. The reliability parameters characterising the SIS and the valve are respectively $(\lambda_{DU1}, \lambda_{DD1}, MTTR, T_1)$ and $(\lambda_{DU2}, MTTR, T_2 = 2T_1)$, where

T_i ($i = 1, 2$) is the interval between tests. Now let us apply the standard-based approach, then the correct approach.

- **Standard approach**

On the basis of figure 5.8, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{RRF_{std}} &= \frac{1}{(RRF_1 \cdot RRF_2)} = PFD_1 \cdot PFD_2 \\ &= [\lambda_{DU1} \cdot (\frac{T_1}{2} + MTTR) + \lambda_{DD1} \cdot MTTR] \cdot \lambda_{DU2} \cdot (\frac{T_2}{2} + MTTR) \end{aligned} \quad (5.39)$$

The title “std” refers to “standard”.

Taking into account the respective values for T_1 , T_2 and $MTTR$, a good approximation of (5.39) is given below.

$$\frac{1}{RRF_{std}} = (\lambda_{DU1} \cdot \frac{T_1}{2}) \cdot (\lambda_{DU2} \cdot \frac{T_2}{2}) = \frac{\lambda_{DU1} \cdot \lambda_{DU2} \cdot T_1^2}{2} \quad (5.40)$$

- **Correct approach**

The approach which we recommend [Innal et al., 2008] [Signoret, 2007] requires considering the two protection layers together and therefore calculating the overall PFD_{avg} as follows:

$$PFD_{avg} = \frac{1}{T_2} \int_0^{T_2} PFD_1(t) \cdot PFD_2(t) dt \quad (5.41)$$

By approximating $PFD_1(t)$ and $PFD_2(t)$ by $\lambda_{DU1} \cdot t$ and $\lambda_{DU2} \cdot t$ respectively over their first interval between tests, and by $\lambda_{DU1} \cdot (t - T_1)$ and $\lambda_{DU2} \cdot t$ over the second interval, we get:

$$PFD_{avg} = \frac{\lambda_{DU1} \cdot \lambda_{DU2}}{2T_1} \left(\int_0^{T_1} t^2 dt + \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} (t - T_1) \cdot t dt \right) \quad (5.42)$$

So, after solving it:

$$PFD_{avg} = \frac{7}{12} \cdot \lambda_{DU1} \cdot \lambda_{DU2} \cdot T_1^2 = \frac{1}{RRF_{ex}} \quad (5.43)$$

“ex” refers to “exact”. Comparing (5.40) and (5.43) leads to:

$$\frac{RRF_{ex}}{RRF_{std}} = \frac{7}{6} \approx 1,17 \quad (5.44)$$

This last result shows that the standard approach leads to a slightly optimistic result in the case we looked at, and therefore non conservative. The deviation seen can be more

significant, which is not acceptable from a safety point of view. So, if we take $T_2 = T_1$, the preceding ratio is worth $4/3 \approx 1.33$.

5.5.3. Conclusion relating to the pair (*PFDAvg*, *RRF*)

The problem raised by this last section is the same that we have previously evoked when comparing equations (2.51) and (2.52). The conclusion which is now imposed regarding the standard method of calculating the risk reduction produced by associating several independent protection layers is the same. Let us look at it again: *this method is erroneous, because the average value of the product of mathematical functions (PFDAvg here) is not equal to the product of the average values for these functions.*

To finish off this section, we should explain that the “exact” method is valid, regardless of whether the different protection layers are independent or not.

General conclusion and perspectives

Having chosen to finish each chapter of this report with a specific conclusion, all that remains is for us to summarise the major points to propose a general conclusion for our thesis work, which we will complete by evoking a few perspectives which might extend it.

To refresh our memory, let us firstly remember the objectives for this work. Firstly we made a critical and commented reading of the IEC 61508 standard and more specifically of its volume 6, in order to highlight the positive aspects and the points arising from matters of comprehension or interpretation. We then had to propose other ways of accessing these points, which could raise ambiguities and omissions which mar them, particularly by explaining the hypotheses guaranteeing their validity.

The second objective that we were allocated was to group together and coordinate the developments made and the results obtained within the framework of the research attached to the first target, so it could be used as a basis to draw up a pedagogic and practical guide. This guide should contribute to better comprehension and easy implementation of the aforementioned standard, so it covers modelling the SISs and obtaining their performances in terms of PFD_{avg} and PFH .

To try and satisfy these two objectives, firstly in chapter 1 we aimed to mark clear boundaries for our research topic. Working from the general context of safety and its key-concepts, we have ended up, via functional safety and its standard-based framework, at the scope of our study, with safety instrumented systems and typical architectures making up the different parts.

Before studying the SIS in detail, we deemed it useful to find out more about the different operating modes and the performance indicators. So in chapter 2 we proposed to throw new light on these operating modes and a criteria to discriminate them, as well as a rigorous definition of the PFH . This chapter also reviewed the fact that the behaviour of any architecture made up of periodically tested components was not Markov, but piecewise Markov. We then showed that only multi-phase Markov models or models based on the simulation were capable of reporting.

We also verified in this same chapter and particularly in chapters 3 and 4 that the average unavailability of these architectures, calculated via a multi-phase model could be approximated by the asymptotic unavailability of a classic Markov model, deduced from the previous one.

The last contribution to chapter 2 lies in a first illustration of the applicative limits of the analytical formulas proposed in the IEC 61508-6 standard.

In chapter 3, we presented an approach, based on piecewise Markov models or their derived models, helping us to work back to analytical formulas giving the PFD_{avg} for some $KooN$ architectures from the standard and to explain the conditions to obtain them in.

It appeared that with these restrictive hypotheses, these formulas give results close to those provided by more elaborate holistic models which exhibit much wider application spectrum. It is therefore advisable to make sure that the hypotheses governing the use of these analytical formulas are properly met before resorting to them. This is not generally done.

Chapter 4 follows on from the previous chapter but looks at calculating the *PFH* which is done on the same models which were used to determine the *PFDAvg*. In order to confirm our observation regarding the restricted scope of the previous analytical formulas, we have applied them to a simple SIS, which cannot be reduced to an association of *KooN* architectures given in the standard. The severity of the observation regarding these formulas was reinforced.

Our last four contributions revolve around chapter 5. The idea of presenting what we think was the approach followed by some authors of volume 6 of IEC 61508 standard to obtain the analytical expressions for *PFDAvg* and *PFH* was imposed on us late. We specified it because, to the best of our knowledge, it had never been published in detail before. We then completed our initial analysis of the role of the *SFF* in determining the final value of the SIL to be attributed to a safety instrumented function. To do this we made two alternative proposals which were added to the proposal recently submitted by Jean-Pierre Signoret. Then we tried to target the nature of spurious trip failures better and we proposed defining them more completely, going beyond their generally attributed meaning. Finally, we think that it is useful to mention that the overall risk reduction factor resulting from an association of several protection layers is not obtained by simply multiplying the individual risk factors, as the majority of writings looking at this problem could lead you to believe.

This work, like any thesis, is not exhaustive. There are many subjects left to think about and research to be started or looked at in greater depth within IEC 61508 standard. We can give two examples. We would like, for example, to go further into what we have undertaken concerning modelling and evaluating the impact of spurious trip failures on the safety of a production system and on its availability. This would involve comparative analysis of the preventive and protective behaviour for n SIS category called HIPS (High Integrity Protection Systems). Another interesting perspective goes beyond the framework of the SIS, as it aims to get a better understanding of what common cause failures really are and tackle different models involving them, such as β , SINTEF and shock models. That is an ambitious project because the domain has already been widely explored and so it would be difficult to demonstrate something new.

For the time being we will remain modest, hoping however that our doctoral contribution will provide better understanding and reflected use of the IEC 61508 standard.

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Abstract

IEC 61508 standard is the reference text related to what is known as functional safety. Safety instrumented systems (SIS) are the core of this standard. Our work dealt with the analysis of its five main concepts, i.e., low and continuous modes of operation of SIS and their attributes known as probability of failure on demand ($PF_{D_{avg}}$) and probability of failure per hour (PFH). The fifth concept concerns the strong relation existing between the risk reduction factor (RRF) provided by a given layer of protection and the safety integrity level (SIL) of the latter. We propose a new interpretation of the first four concepts and will question the fifth and the idea of the safe failure fraction (SFF). Moreover we have proposed two suitable ways to demonstrate the analytical formulae given in the standard and to explain their underlying hypothesis. We have also studied the influence of spurious failures of a given SIS on the frequency of the accident it must prevent.

Keywords: IEC 61508 standard, functional safety, safety instrumented system, fault tree, piecewise Markov models, Petri nets with predicates.